

BRITISH RETAIL BANKING SHIPWRECK: IS 'REGULATED SALES-LED CULTURE' THE SOLUTION?

Name: Tahir Ahmed

Student ID: B00326075

Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of The Requirements
of The University of The West of Scotland
for the award of the Doctorate in Business Administration

May 2021

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This thesis would not have been possible without the support of various people, whom I wish to express my sincere gratitude. Writing this thesis for the last three years has been a rewarding experience. Initially, I would like to thank my parents for being their amazing selves and encouraging me throughout this process of DBA.

Secondly, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Eugene Kozlovski (my lead supervisor) for his guidance over the years, his patience to keep up with my never-ending ideas and most importantly motivating me throughout the study period to give my best in this thesis.

Next, I would like to thank my sister and brother-in-law who I live with for supporting me in the study process. The last few years had been very challenging for me and their emotional support pushed and motivated me throughout the DBA.

Finally, I would thank Dr Uma for her helpful feedbacks on my paper (to be submitted for publishing) and her ideas in improving my thesis throughout the taught period of DBA.

DECLARATION

I declare that the work in the thesis is entirely my own. Where I have consulted the work of others, this is always clearly stated.

Signed: Tahir Ahmed

Date: 02/05/2021

ABSTRACT

Retail Banking is an essential part of the UK financial system. Following the shift to Universal Banking Model in 1980, this sector relished increased profitability with the collective balance sheet accounting to 500% more than the UK GDP. However, the Financial Crisis of 2008 got this sector into crisis, where some banks failed while others had a near miss. Following the crisis, a period of learning and rectifying began but the manipulation of LIBOR scandal in 2012 baffled the public as despite the crisis, banks continued their unethical and immoral practises. Ever since the crisis, retail division had to pay £38.5bn in fines and these unethical practises got the complaints to Financial Ombudsman Services to as high as 400,000 post the crisis. The banks, regulators and policymakers were alarmed by these costly failures and set up an inquiry to find out what went wrong and what disinters was the aggressive sales culture that the banks operated in. Banks recently committed to change their culture back to being ‘customer-centric’. This proposal addresses various gaps in literature with regards to this cultural change. Banks are now committed to change their cultures; however, no researcher appreciated the whooping profitability this sector relished for three decades and yet no study highlighted the ignorance of regulators in this issue. Culture, despite being the major reason for the worst crisis in history has been left for the banks to execute. Regulators take a hands-off approach by stating that culture cannot be regulated and then trusts the same banks that were the reason of the worst economic turmoil to execute it themselves. The author aims to develop a strategy where regulators, policymakers, and banks work together for a healthy banking system. Also, the literature is limited with studies on the progress of banks after the cultural change, so this study aims to find out the effectiveness of the new culture.

The author proposes to use a Mixed-Method Approach for this study. Since the literature is limited with studies on culture, this study proposes to do an

exploratory research to analyse the culture with varying levels of depth and form a basis for future conclusive studies. And the author will use a causal research design as it helps to generalize the findings of a larger population (in this case the UK retail banks). This design would be an appropriate measure to investigate the effects of product diversification on the financial performance of UK Retail Banks.

The aim of this research is to explore an issue at the very heart of the Financial Crisis and the series of scandals like PPI that followed: ‘culture’ and propose a strategy for a safer, reliable and sustainable banking sector.

The author aims to develop a strategy where the banks, policy makers and regulators work together to revive the wrecked UK Retail Banking system.

Keywords: diversification, HHI, financial crisis, sales-led culture, profitability

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
CG	Corporate Governance
FP	Financial Performance
ROTA	Return on Total Assets
EBIT	Earnings before Interest and Tax
ROE	Return on Equity
NOI	Net Operating Income
NII	Net Interest Income
NONII	Non-Interest Income
HHI	Herfindahl-Hirschman Index

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENT.....	ii
DECLARATION.....	iii
ABSTRACT.....	iv
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	vi
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	vii
LIST OF TABLES.....	x
LIST OF FIGURES.....	xi
1.INTRODUCTION.....	12
1.1 Background.....	12
1.2 ROTAD TO A ‘CRISIS CULTURE’.....	14
1.3 UNDERSTANDING THE ‘SALES’ CULTURE.....	15
1.4 What is Culture?.....	17
1.5 FINANCIAL CRISIS- WHAT WENT WRONG?.....	18
1.6 ROLE OF CULTURE.....	20
1.7 RATIONALE BEHIND THE INITIATION OF CULTURAL CHANGE PROCESS.....	23
1.8 IMPLEMENTING THE CULTURAL CHANGE.....	26
1.9 POSSIBLE CHALLENGES.....	28
1.10 RESULT OF THE CULTURAL CHANGE.....	29
1.11 RATIONALE.....	30
1.12 RESEARCH QUESTION.....	37
1.13 AIM.....	37
1.14 OBJECTIVES.....	37
1.15 Structure of the thesis.....	38
2. LITERATURE REVIEW.....	38
2.1 Introduction.....	38
2.2 Understanding the effect of Product Diversification on the Financial Performance of UK Retail Banks.	39
2.3 Understanding the effect of Culture on the financial performance of UK Retail Banks.....	56
2.4 Conclusion.....	73
3. Conceptual Framework.....	74
4.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	78
4.1 Introduction.....	78
4.2 Research Onion.....	78
4.3 Research Philosophy.....	79
4.4 Research Approach.....	81

4.5 Research Methodology.....	83
4.6 Research Nature and Design.....	88
4.6.1 Multiple Sources of Data.....	90
4.7 Conclusion.....	96
5. DATA ANALYSIS.....	96
5.1 Introduction.....	96
5.2 Retail Banks in UK.....	98
5.3 Market Share.....	99
5.4 Increasing Complaints.....	101
5.5 Customer Satisfaction.....	105
5.6 Ethics in UK Retail Banking.....	107
5.7 Aggressive Sales pressure: increasing or decreasing?.....	109
5.8 Employee Satisfaction.....	112
5.9 Trust.....	113
5.10 Effect of Product Diversification on the Financial Performance of UK Retail Banks.....	114
5.10.1 Herfindahl- Hirschman Index.....	116
5.10.2 CORRELATION ANALYSIS.....	123
5.10.3 REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	129
5.11 Conclusion.....	137
6. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.....	137
6.1 Understanding the effect of product diversification on the financial and non-financial performance of UK Banks.....	137
6.1.1 Trust.....	140
6.1.2 Employee Satisfaction.....	142
6.1.3 Ethics in UK Retail Banking.....	143
6.2 FINANCIAL CRISIS- WHAT WENT WRONG?.....	150
6.3 Macro Culture.....	153
6.4 The phase of denial.....	155
6.5 The paths to reform.....	155
6.6 ROLE OF CULTURE.....	156
6.7 Transforming the culture.....	160
6.8 Challenges facing the cultural shift.....	163
6.9 Analysis of Problems.....	165
6.10 Conclusion.....	176
7. CONCLUSION.....	177
7.1 Background.....	177
7.2 Purpose of this research.....	178
7.2.1 AIM.....	179

7.2.2 RESEARCH QUESTION	179
7.3 Methodology	179
7.4 Key Findings.....	180
7.5 Limitations and suggestions for future research	184
7.6 Conclusion.....	185
8. RECOMMENDATIONS	185
8.1 Introduction.....	185
8.2 What have we learnt so far?	186
8.3 Recommendations to Regulators.....	189
8.4 Recommendation to Policymakers	192
8.5 Recommendation to Banks.....	192
8.6 Establishing an Independent Body.....	193
9. References.....	195
10. APPENDIX.....	198
10.1 CONSENT FORM	199
10.2 Information for Participants.....	200
10.3 QUESTIONNAIRE.....	201

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: The Lambert Report Recommendations of how to measure culture.....	23
Table 2: Financial Ombudsman: financial services new complaints in the UK 2011 -2020.....	102
Table 3: Customer complaints against banking services in the UK in H1 2020, by company	105
Table 4: Customer Satisfaction.....	106
Table 5: Which? Survey	111
Table 6: Herfindahl- Hirschman Index.....	117
Table 7: Mean diversification level (2008-2019).....	118
Table 8: Average Diversification Level and Profit.....	120
Table 9: Trends of Profits, NONII, NII and NOI 2008-2019	122
Table 10: ZERO-order Correlation of studied variables	125
Table 11: Partial correlation with NONII controlled.....	127
Table 12: Partial correlation with NII controlled.....	128
Table 13: Regression of HHI and NOI.....	129
Table 14: ANOVA for HHI and NOI.....	130
Table 15: Coefficients for HHI and NOI.....	130
Table 16: Regression of HHI and EBIT.....	131
Table 17: Regression of HHI and EBIT	132
Table 18:: Coefficients for HHI and EBIT.....	132
Table 19: Regression of HHI and ROTA	133
Table 20: ANOVA for HHI and ROTA.....	134
Table 21: Coefficients for HHI and ROTA	134
Table 22: Regression for HHI and ROE	135
Table 23: ANOVA for HHI and ROE.....	135
Table 24: Coefficients for HHI and ROE.....	135
Table 25: The Lambert Report Recommendations of how to measure culture.....	160

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2: Meta Model.....	24
Figure 3: Three levels of Culture.....	26
Figure 4: Conceptual Framework.....	77
Figure 5: Research Onion.....	79
Figure 6: The Deductive Approach.....	82
Figure 7: The Inductive Approach.....	82
Figure 8: Abductive Reasoning Approach.....	83
Figure 9: Leading Banks in UK.....	99
Figure 10: Market share of current accounts.....	100
Figure 11: Number of complaints regarding financial services 2010/11 to 2019/20.....	103
Figure 12: Problem of Ethics?.....	108
Figure 13: ethical banks: yes or no?.....	109
Figure 14: Average Level of Diversification (2008-2019).....	121
Figure 15: NONII, NII, NOI and Profits trends (2008-2019).	122
Figure 16: Causes of financial scandals.....	142

1.INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Retail Banking is the heart of UK economy. The greater part of the nation becomes a customer of the bank at a very early age and forms a relationship of trust with it. Traditionally, banks had a simple business model. Customers would rely on banks to access loans and other services while carrying out their day-to-day activities of making deposits and payments. However, due to excessive competition from the financial intermediaries who were tremendously profitable, UK banks decided to switch to the Universal Banking Model in order to be financially stable. German Banks who were still using traditional banking model were seen to be less profitable and less variable (Hoggarth, 1998).

The evolution to the universal banking was evident with an increase in the contribution of non-interest income to the banks' total earnings and by 2010 Q4 non-interest income accounted for more than 60% of the banks' earnings (Manning, 2010 Q4). UK banks' collective balance sheet accounted to more than 500% of annual UK GDP, making it second among G20 economies (Manning, 2010 Q4). The universal model proved to be a success with many scholars like (Templeton, The Effect of Nonbank Diversification on Bank Holding Company Risk, 1992), upholding that banks who diversify into non-banking activities tend to be more profitable and stable than banks who keep themselves to traditional means of generating income only. But does it bring increased risks?

The (Walker D. , 2009) identified governance as the material contributor of excessive risk taking which in turn lead to the financial crisis and recommended improved governance (remuneration, governance of risk, functioning of board

and evaluation of the performance) as a key to mitigate the chances of these events recurring.

Following the shift to a universal banking model, retail division faced immense coercion for higher profitability which made them develop an 'aggressive sales-led culture'. This culture brought increased profitability and greater access to loans but at the cost of economy. This culture soon became a culture of greed, dishonesty and rashness as banks became obdurate of the uncertainty in the kind of loans they were making. They were making loans to customers with poor credit history without verifying their means of income at a higher rate just to report higher profitability. (André Spicer J. P., 2016)'s report on the banking culture captures the essence of the aggressiveness of this sales-led culture. The report consists of interviews of employees of UK's leading banks. An employee of HSBC reported to have sold products to customers without catering to their needs in order to meet his targets. Whereas an employee of Halifax revealed the fear of embarrassment employees had to face if they didn't meet their targets. Where cash was given out for achieving targets, cabbages were publicly given for not achieving targets. An RBS executive went as far as to rename this culture as a monster. The interviews clearly highlighted the pressure employees faced to meet their targets and the coercion retail division faced to deliver increased profits which drove them to be immoral and unethical.

Which? Investigation of 500 front-line staff of the Big Five Banks revealed that 46% of the staff sold products to meet their targets and 40% sold irrespective of the customers' needs. The investigation further found the effect of this culture on customers, where 40% reported to have been offered a product that was not suitable and 25% of them felt pressurised to take it. These evidence were further validated by the studies that followed. (Lui A. , 'Greed, Recklessness, Dishonesty: and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK

banks between 2004 and 2009', 2015), confirmed the banks' shift to sales-led culture and the rashness in this culture during the studied period 2004-09.

Though the shift to this model brought increased profitability with UK Banks accounting to 500% more than annual UK's GDP but it was short-lived as the model was based on shaky foundations. The repercussions were seen in 2007 when the failure and near-miss of some of the major banks (through taxpayers money) and the miss-selling of Payment protection insurance (PPI) became public and agitated the public's confidence in banks and by 2012 got the British Retail Banks in catastrophe. These costly failures could not go unnoticed and led policy makers, banks, and regulators to ponder what went wrong. Various reports by Future of Banking Commissions, FSA and Salz comprehended that the root cause was a widespread aggressive sales culture. Scandals like LIBOR were climacteric for the banks which was followed by radical changes in the culture. Following the LIBOR scandal, Anthony Jenkins took over Bob Diamonds as chief executive of Barclays in 2012 and in the year 2014 in an interview to Financial Times, he revealed that *'they have remodelled the way employees are rewarded and that they are assessed on how well they serve customers'* (Arnold, 2014).

1.2 ROTAD TO A 'CRISIS CULTURE'

Banks traditionally were sighted as financial institutions' which take deposits from customers and/or make loans to them. However, during 1980s UK banks switched to a universal banking model to sustain their positions as financial intermediaries. This shift from traditional banking model was important to be financially stable. (Hoggarth, 1998), analysis sheds light on this where it was observed that German Banks (who were still traditional in their banking ways) were less profitable than banks in Britain and less variable.

As the banks reached out past the generally straightforward plan of action of the past, retail sector faced increased burden from shareholders for increased returns. As a response to this challenge, banks created an ‘aggressive sales’ culture. Banks started to forcefully promote new financial products to clients which in turn led to "tellers" inside bank offices beginning to consider themselves to be “sellers”. This shift without a doubt brought expanded benefits, more scope of commodities and increased access to borrowings. Nonetheless, this accompanied a cost. Banks became adamant of the risks in lending. They planned low quality products and promoted them to clients independent of its suitability. It wasn’t until 2007 that banks began to evidence the implications of this aggressive sales culture. The collapse and near-miss of some of the major banks (through public bailouts), the miss-selling of Payment protection insurance (PPI) and billions set aside in compensation and fines for wrong-practices shook the public’s confidence in banking system and by 2012 brought the British Retail Banks in crisis.

1.3 UNDERSTANDING THE ‘SALES’ CULTURE

One of the major reasons for the failure of the UK Banking System is the adoption of a ‘sales’ culture. This is a set of embedded organisational norms and practices where short-term goals are preferred over long terms i.e. encouraging employees to focus on making short term sales at the expense of longer term customer satisfaction (providing them with the products they actually need within the bounds of integrity and ethics).

Originated in 1980s as an ‘embedded’ culture to UK Retail Banks, senior executives were of view that front line colleagues were not sales driven and hence not selling the financial products that banks offered. So, the idea was to promote these products to customers in every transaction. Banks even went on to change the way their branches looked; newer branches were designed to make a conversation between a staff and customer more natural. Questions like

‘would you like something else’ came in and introducing clients to new banking products e.g., loans, credit cards and services like PPI. Banks started to use ‘incentives’ as a positive reinforcement to boost sales. Performances became public through whiteboards, where staff with leading sales was rewarded while laggards were punished. Retail Bank went on to declare their commitment to building a sales-led culture. The underlying assumption was that this sales-oriented culture would lead them to operate and sustain in an increasingly aggressive market, whilst maximising profits and increasing returns to shareholders.

Some of the examples of aggressive sales culture are listed below:

1. *“...we had daily targets to meet and were publicly shamed to have not met them”.*
2. *“...once I was heavily incentivised to mis-sell PPIs and home insurances...”*
3. *“...daily target meeting was a norm at start of the day and the day usually ended with shame walk, with name-calling and trash thrown on if the targets weren’t met”.*
4. *“...the atmosphere was hellish, we had to sacrifice our morals to keep our jobs...”*
5. *“...a few of us were told to cater customer needs and weren’t paid incentives while our peers were being paid to sell, **sell their morals!!**”*

Though these examples are only informal, there are research and evidence to prove that they are far from outliers. There have been numerous studies over the two decades that confirm the emergence and/or presence of ‘sales-led’ culture in

UK Retail Banks. (Lui A.), upheld both her hypotheses (1) shift from customer driven to sales driven (2) culture of greed and dishonesty between 2004 and 2009. A 2012 study by Which? Found the presence of sales culture (pressure on bank staff to sell financial products) despite demands of change from regulators and policy makers (Mortgage Strategy, 2012). In Which's survey of over 500 front line bank staff, conducted in September, 81% say the pressure to meet sales targets has stayed the same or risen while 66% say they are sometimes, or always, told to sell more. Some 41% say they thought there had been a decrease in the incentives available. Nearly half, 46%, say they know colleagues had mis-sold products to meet sales targets while 40% say they were expected to sell products even when it was not appropriate for the customer.

The evidence shows the emergence and/or presence of aggressive 'sales-led' culture within the Retail Banking in UK over the 2 decades, the repercussions of which became quite evident with the onset of Financial Crisis.

1.4 What is Culture?

Culture according to me is 'the set of embedded values within an organisation which provides a basis for employees to act upon'. (Hofstede, 2005) defines culture as the software of mind. To put it straight culture can be defined as 'the way we do things around here'. Culture is a driver to how individuals behave which in-turn affects the day-to-day practises within an organisation.

Ever since the Financial Crisis of 2008, the banking industry has gone through rigorous scrutiny to understand what went wrong and the fundamental cause that unearthed was the competitive environment the banking industry was operating in, which in turn lead to the widespread and 'aggressive sales culture' within the Banking Industry. This resulted in banks shifting their focus from being 'customer-centric' to being 'sales-led'.

1.5 FINANCIAL CRISIS- WHAT WENT WRONG?

The financial crisis without a doubt altered the dynamics of UK Retail Banking and made the problems evident to public, policymakers and regulators. We will look at the financial crisis in 3 stages:

- Immediate crises 2007-2008 (ensuring the continuity of banks),
- 2009-2012 (aggressive sales-led culture became evident), and
- 2012-present (continuity of bad behaviours (LIBOR) despite regulatory changes).

➤ **2007-2008**

Prior to the crisis, the UK financial institution relished a decade of continuous growth. Since the growth was based on a shaky foundation, it could not last long and the first disastrous impact was noticed with the failure of Northern Rock in 2007. This was followed by prolonged warnings from consumer groups and evidences of mis-selling of PPI. However, the disastrous impact was not limited to Northern Rock as Lehman Brother collapsed the following year, followed by a bailout of RBS and Lloyds by the UK government. This brought doubts on the funding positions of Universal Banks.

➤ **Journey from Crisis to 2012**

Following the crisis, a time of ‘learning and rectifying’ started. This included a progression of examinations and ensuing reports by the Future of Banking Commission, the FSA, the Treasury Select Committee, and the ICB. These reports identified issues that led to the collapse of a financially stable institution followed by remedial actions. In the meantime, fines started to show up. The inspection related with these fines disclosed the wrong behaviour inside the banks which went way past the mis-selling of PPI. This included poor handling of customer complaints, mis-selling of investment products and tax hedging

products and money laundering. It was clear that there is a fundamental problem within the roots of the banking culture and very little or no steps were taken to change their practises.

➤ **2012-present**

The news of manipulation of LIBOR rate left the public baffled because this time misbehaviour happened after the bailouts and the self-reflection period. It was evidence that despite all the fines and warnings banks have not changed their ways.

WHAT NEXT??

A clutch of important reports into the continuing crisis in banking appeared during this period. These incorporated the Salz audit of Barclays and the reports coming about because of the Parliamentary Commission on Banking Standards (PCBS). The last prompted a progression of new laws to direct UK banks. What's more, most of the UK banks propelled huge scale change programs. LIBOR was a turning point as banks started to accept that 'fundamental change' is needed.

An example of this change is reflected in an example of the interview of Antony Jenkins, chief executive of Barclays, after taking over from Bob Diamond in 2012 following the LIBOR scandal.

He told the Financial Times (Arnold, 2014) that *“completely overhauled the way performance is measured and how people are incentivised, and nobody is paid to sell anything in the branches anymore”*. *“They are assessed on how they serve customers”*. *“We have developed a system at Barclays to measure both what people have to deliver – based on our balanced scorecard – and how they deliver it. Overall compensation is a composite of the two and importantly*

if someone achieves their goals but does it in way that is not compatible with our culture then they will fail to hit their target.”

1.6 ROLE OF CULTURE

One of the main factors for the crisis of banks has been identified as ‘culture’. Aggressive sales culture within retail banking, lead to the mis-selling of financial commodities. Whilst there has been legislation in place to address the ‘harder’ issues, ‘softer’ systems like culture has not been addressed and left on banks to solve themselves.

➤ **THE CONFUSION**

The former chief executive of Barclays, Bob Diamond, defined culture as how employees behave “when no one is watching”. Culture is something that emerges from the tone that senior individuals set within an organisation”. There are many reports that addressed culture, but every report has a different understanding of culture. While some focus on norms, beliefs and values others focusses on areas such as governance and standards. Some linked it with incentive structure and how performance is measured. Though, all the reports agree that culture is the core reason, but it is difficult to interpret their definition of ‘culture’. However, looking at a more tangible aspect like remuneration structure is preferable.

➤ **LONG PROCESS AND THE RESPONSIBILITY OF BANKS**

According to Financial Conduct Authority ‘culture is a matter for banks not UK regulators’ and to further explain their stance they went on to says that regulators are responsible for sound financial system and not the day to day running of business. Reports do suggest that culture is the root cause of crisis but leaves it on to the banks to solve it themselves and its assessment to

Banking Standard Review Council. However, there is an agreement that this culture change is a long process, and it might take a generation to achieve it.

➤ **MISPLACED OPTIMISM**

Banks tend to be overconfident about their own institutions in compared to their peers. According to a survey by The Economist 71% of the executives think that their bank outperforms the industry and a survey by Deloitte found that executives assume that it would take their banks 2 years on average to address the cultural issues in their banks, whereas it will take 3 years on average for their competitors to do the same thing.

➤ **MULTIPLE LEVERS**

Reports identify a wide range of levers for change including governance, remuneration, code of conduct and many more diffusing levers which are outside the tool kit used in culture programmes such as HR and leadership. So in order to address the culture change in banks, conventional tools won't be enough. Attempts should be made to change more strategic issues like leadership, governance and risk management.

➤ **Top to Bottom OWNERSHIP**

Boards and senior executives are mainly responsible for cultural change. Report's place great stone on 'tone from top' and highlight the role of CEO as 'enablers of change. However, middle management should be responsible for embodying cultural change. Cultural change is mostly driven off-track by the staff in the middle of the organisation. Many banks have mission statements, code of conduct which is meaningless as they are not monitored. Culture must be enforced in the everyday behaviours through the line supervisors.

➤ **REGULATORS AS SUPPORTERS**

REGULATORS are not the drivers of cultural change, they are mere supporters. Regulation is not an answer. Regulators are there to set limits which should be maintained. Banks themselves are the drivers of cultural change and also institutions like BSRC.

➤ **UNCERTAIN METRICS**

While the reports identify the urge for cultural change, there was no understanding of how to measure it. There are no rigorous metrics to test culture. While some recommends using gender diversity, customer satisfaction and compliance as metrics to track culture, others recommend stakeholder surveys. BSRC recommends a set of areas in which metrics may be developed.

DIMENSIONS	DESCRIPTIONS
Tone from the top	Board and Senior Management are starting points for setting core values and expectations of risk culture, and their behaviour must reflect the values being espoused
Accountability	Relevant employees at all levels understand the core values of the institution and its approach to risk, can perform their prescribed roles, and aware that they are held accountable for their actions in relation to the institution’s risk-taking behaviour.

Effective Communication and Challenge	A sound risk culture promotes an environment of open communication and challenge in which decision-making processes encourage a range of views.
Incentives	Financial and non-financial incentives support the core values and risk culture at all levels of the institution

TABLE 1: THE LAMBERT REPORT RECOMMENDATIONS OF HOW TO MEASURE CULTURE.

Ever since 2008 banks have undergone significant changes. Despite the lack of responsiveness earlier, banks got in action lately. Regulators set out a list of regulatory and non-regulatory changes. Significant progress has been seen in areas like competition and remuneration. However, culture change remained an area to work on. All the reports agree that banks themselves are responsible for cultural change and the establishment of BSRC further reinforces banks to follow banking standards.

1.7 RATIONALE BEHIND THE INITIATION OF CULTURAL CHANGE PROCESS

One of the major drivers of change was broader micro-economic trends. The increased amount of default loans subsequently leads to the contraction of lending and in turn lead to a more risk-averse culture in banks. The financial crisis of 2008-09 saw the collapse of some major banks and a bailout of few like Lloyds and RBS. This meant that public and politicians were able to put pressure on these banks.

However, the turning point was the rigging of LIBOR and the mis-selling of PPI. This made the public realize that banks were adamant despite all the warnings and had not learnt from their mistakes. This lost confidence of public on the banks proved to be a turning point as banks started taking ‘culture’ as their fundamental problem which needed to be changed. Following these scandals were a new range of regulations (ring-fencing) in conjunction with previously introduced regulations which placed banks under significant pressure to change their approach. This added up to an important change to the industry.

META MODEL

ROBINMATTHEWS.COM

FIGURE 1: META MODEL

INNER DYNAMICS

The 'sales-led' culture which was considered to be the core reason for financial crisis obviously raised doubts in public's mind about the worthiness of these institutions. The collapse of major banks alarmed the public that their money is not safe. This culture adversely affected the banking reputation amongst general public. This adverse reputation was a **THREAT** to the banking system and banks had to shift their focus to being a Customer-oriented culture as an **OPPORTUNITY** to regain the lost confidence. There have been various regulatory changes ever since the financial crises and the establishment of BSRC to ensure the conformity of standards by banks (**STRENGTH**). Despite the regulatory changes, banks continued the sales-led culture and the LIBOR scandal raised public doubts of bank's non-conformity of regulations (**WEAKNESS**).

OUTER DYNAMICS

There are high barriers to entry, since it costs a lot to establish a bank leading to a lack of competition in the industry and lack of substitutes available (**PORTER'S FIVE FORCES**). Since the customers are not well informed (low financial capability), they are not able to select between products and identify the best deal for themselves.

PAY-OFFS

Shareholder's demand increased return on investments over a short term (3year investment cycle) meaning CEOs have relatively short decision-making horizons. This means that if the results of cultural change are not forthcoming in the next few years, they'll put increased pressure on executives to focus on more aggressive means to get increased returns.

Employees are low-paid and widespread job cuts increases their insecurity meaning staff might be under pressure of meeting increasing sales target in

order to sustain. Sales –based bonuses are just a way of enforcing a sales-led culture.

GRAMMAR

➤ **MACRO CULTURE**

The core reason for the failure of banks was identified as the rise of a sales culture within the banking industry. What’s intriguing is that this sales culture was not limited to one organisation; it was replete throughout the industry. Though it gave bankers a shared way of looking at the problems they faced, but they overlooked the long-term risks. Problems escalated and hence lead to financial crisis. Since the culture was so ingrained, seniors continued business as normal up until 2012 when LIBOR scandal raised doubts and a pressure on banks to address their culture. It is now recently that banks have abandoned this sales-led culture and seeking to switch to a better ‘customer-oriented’ culture.

1.8 IMPLEMENTING THE CULTURAL CHANGE

http://www.valuebasedmanagement.net/images/picture_schein_3_levels_culture.gif

FIGURE 2: THREE LEVELS OF CULTURE

The focus is on leaders at the top of the organisation to emphasize on creating common values. This would focus on creating a need for change, articulating common behaviours and working on leadership issues. In the cascade down program the need for senior leaders to get involved in the culture change process is emphasised and is focused on encouraging them to not forget humanity. So, when the need for change is inculcated in senior leaders, they will be able to cascade it down to the organisation. Transformational leadership workshop would be a great idea to engrave leadership standards in the senior leaders for them to pass on to their organisation.

Another approach would be reinforcement through everyday process (bottom-up to constantly reinforced culture). Instead of focusing on top leaders and expecting them to cascade down the new culture to organisation, it would be better to focus on all members of an organisation and seek to reinforce widely shared sets of values.

Third approach could be to build a culture from scratch. This would work for banks which were made up of parts of other financial organisations such as TSB and Virgin Media. E.g., Shawbrook's processes that would reinforce culture remained part of the business it is made up of.

TONE FROM THE TOP

Establishing tone from the top would ensure correct values are expressed and embodied by the CEO. It should also involve the senior management who should 'live the values'. In this way senior managers would become culture enablers who would cascade the value to the organisation. To do that senior managers would rely on experience designed to cut them off from the previous culture by looking at its dark side. Truth and reconciliation style workshops would be helpful where they would be shown videos of the wrong doings of

bank and encourage them to discuss the core values of bank and its significance to them.

A good way to move from a sales-led culture would be the change in remuneration package. Sales-based bonuses should be eliminated and more focus on customer satisfaction should be embedded. Customer surveys e.g. “how did we do?” and possibly reward the employees with maximum compliments with a bonus would drive the employees to be more customer focused.

It should be noted that employees should understand the culture of the bank instead of being reminded and forcefully made to follow. Customer-focused culture should be embedded in the banking culture not pervasive throughout the banks. e.g. Metro Bank’s workplace architecture to reward systems were designed to consistently reinforce a customer centric culture.

The use of ‘Balanced Scorecard’ to assess an employee’s performance would be a better approach. In the past, sales were an important aspect. Over the recent years, customer-orientation has taken over. It would be a good idea to work as a balance of both meaning the outlook of bankers is more likely to be balanced.

1.9 POSSIBLE CHALLENGES

The old culture is still embedded within the banks’ employees. They have spent decades working on a sales-led culture and a shift to being customer-driven makes it difficult for them to change their underlying beliefs and assumptions. It can create a sense of concern amongst employees, whether the skills they have gained over the years in a sales centric culture, would be relevant in a new culture of customers and integrity. Also, a large-scale shift often leads to job cuts or change management; this could lead to employees being uncertain about further culture change initiatives.

Banks may face integration challenges if they have merged with different parts following different cultures. Also, employees may not be willing to take responsibility for changes. This was seen when retail divisions were seen blaming investment divisions for their involvement in scandals like LIBOR.

Cultural change is not a fast process; it might take a generation to change it. Amidst all the scandals and crisis executives are seen focusing on cultural change. However, if their focus shifts, especially when shareholders demand increased returns, banks might return to their old culture of increasing short-term shareholder returns even before achieving the milestone it has worked for.

Banks have to follow certain rules and regulations post the crisis and it needs to be integrated in their activities, however it might overload the organisation and regulatory and compliance demands might actually lead to more rationalisation rather than a better culture.

1.10 RESULT OF THE CULTURAL CHANGE

Commenting on its successfulness is too early because it will take the British Retail Banks a generation to change the aggressive sales cultures which lead to the mis-selling of PPI and costed the industry £38.5bn in fines and compensation. A study by Cass Business School found that messages from the top executives about cultural change are still not reaching front line staff.

Pointing to a sharp rise in complaints about banks to the Financial Ombudsman Service from 75,000 in 2008-09 to more than 400,000 in 2013-14, the report says banks have a lot still to do.

Rebuilding trust in the industry will take time; it won't be long until the public restores their trust in the banking industry. However, banks need to make sure they do not get involved in further scandals like the one which has just come to light (manipulation of commodities and foreign exchange markets) because this

would not restore public trust. British Retail Banking has still a milestone to achieve.

1.11 RATIONALE

Culture according to me is ‘the set of embedded values within an organisation which provides a basis for employees to act upon’. (Hofstede, 2005) defines culture as the software of mind. To put it straight culture can be defined as ‘the way we do things around here’. Culture is a driver to how individuals behave which in-turn affects the day to day practises within an organisation.

Ever since the Financial Crisis of 2008, the banking industry has gone through rigorous scrutiny to understand what actually went wrong and the fundamental cause that unearthed was the competitive environment the banking industry was operating in, which in turn lead to the widespread and ‘aggressive sales culture’ within the Banking Industry. This resulted in banks shifting their focus from being ‘customer-centric’ to being ‘sales-led’.

One of the core reasons for the banks’ failure was their aggressive sales culture. There are evidence of a wide spread sales culture that rewarded staff for aggressively selling financial products irrespective of customer needs and the risks. This led to the initiation of some risky loans like sub-prime mortgages and the mis-selling of PPI. This shook the public confidence in banking system as a trusted institution.

Since culture is the reason for the bank’s failure, it is a worthwhile option to investigate the literature on Banking Culture. I will be breaking down this literature into three parts. Firstly, a review of literature on Financial Crisis to

analyse what went wrong and what to do about it. Secondly, reviews of crisis at individual banks like RBS to get an insight into the bank's culture. Finally, review of the academic literature on crisis which provides an independent analysis of what went wrong and what to do about it. These literatures will give a clear picture of the cultural problems in the UK banks. A look into the Salz Review (2013) commissioned by Barclays would be a good idea as it has a good review of the literature on UK Banking Culture and points out the problems and emphasises the lesson that can be learnt from it.

Banks were seen to be acting unethically and immorally pre and post the financial crisis period, examples being Mis selling of PPI, tax evasion and selling garbage for the price of gold. So, I will look into the literature on culture and unethical behaviour. The banking industry is not only about money: it also involves a lot of number crunching. And, research suggests, even basic math increase people's likelihood of engaging in unethical practises. Research (Wang, 2014) finds that number crunching put people in a "calculative mindset" that makes them more likely to focus on a quantitative approach to solving a problem, overlooking moral consequences. After engaging in a calculative task, people were more likely to succumb to the greed of higher margins by acting more selfishly or dishonestly. Thus, the mere act of calculating can activate a calculative mindset that outweighs moral concerns. (Trevino, 2014) summarises the literature on the causes of unethical behaviour in an organisation. It concludes that it is a leader who should play an important role in promoting a moral culture and promote its employees to take more ethical decisions when faced with temptation. This is in contrast with the existing culture of 'moral disconnection' where employees do not see their unethical behaviours as 'wrong' because they have to achieve their targets and whatever they do affects their pay which leads me to analyse literature on 'how pay effects performance' or how the 'pay-structure' effects performance.

UK banks had a 'sales-driven' culture and that means 'the more the sales the more the bonus'. This remuneration promotes unethical behaviour within the employees as they are driven to increase their individual wealth rather than the bank's wealth. (Obloj, 2014) in their study examines many loan decisions and concluded that the sales-based bonus is not in the financial interests of the bank. Employees were seen to be manipulating the sales in a way that reduces the bank's wealth but increases theirs. One example of such manipulation is offering the loan at a lower rate which would attract customers and thus improve their sales. They concluded that for banks with managers who have 'firm specific human capital', the losses are higher indicating 'adverse learning'.

Since this 'sales-driven' culture promoted unethical behaviour and also reduced wealth for the banks, it would be worthwhile to look at literature on culture and financial crisis. (Spicer, 2014), concluded that 'an aggressive sales culture' was a major contributor to the financial crisis. The report found out that regulators have left it on banks to change their culture themselves and the banks have responded to it by initiating the cultural change process. They have refocused their attention to being customer driven. This might take a generation to achieve and a consistency at all levels is necessary to keep this change intact. (Lui A. , 'Greed, Recklessness, Dishonesty: and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK banks between 2004 and 2009' , 2015) used a multiple case study approach to examine five UK banks: Northern Rock, the RBS, Barclays, Lloyds and HSBC between 2004-2009. In her paper she upheld both her hypothesis of the banks moving from a customer driven culture to a sales driven culture and that the UK banking culture between 2004 and 2009 was of greed, recklessness and dishonesty. (Fortado, 'The yin and yang of introducing a sales culture: the Amalgam Bank Case' , 2014), explored the introduction of a 'sales culture' at one of the top ten US banks (Amalgam Bank). Though the sales

increased but brought along slowed service and irritated customers. Sales quotas were unrealistic, and staffs were silenced by managers if they raised concerns. This resulted in unhappy and unmotivated staff, unhappy customers, and unfair management practises but increased sales.

Bank's unethical practises and sales-driven culture lead to financial crisis which in turn lead to the lost confidence among public. (Cohen, 'Governance as the driver of culture change and risk management', 2015), explores the governance failure that led to reputational damage and then discusses what the banks have to do to restore the lost trust. She suggests the importance of cultural change and corporate governance process to support it. She recommends pervasive adherence to a set of values which sets pay and promotion and continuous monitoring of the process of embedding values. This monitoring would make the banks stay focused on their cultural change regime and not get distracted to making short-term gains.

Some of the books provide an insight on the individual banks and the crisis. (Fraser, 2014), investigates RBS by interviewing its employees to find out what went wrong. The investigation found out the bullying arrogance of its chief executive, coward board of directors and the worthless oversight of regulators and independent risk analysts as the key reasons for RBSs failure. RBSs failure raises questions on its corporate governance. Though the leadership style of CEO Fred Goodwin is to be blamed but the failure of regulators is to be criticised as well. The book clearly makes a point that his leadership style lead to its train wreck and the failure of regulators raises serious doubts on the regulators' efficiency. Other books study the on-going cultural problems at UK banks. (Brummer, *Bad Banks: Greed, Incompetence and the Next Global Crisis*, 2014), suggests that there has yet to be significant cultural changes in the banks. Crisis like PPIs and sales-driven bonuses still exist, and reforms are still needed. The books find that the culture was the driver of financial crisis and

that banks should refocus on being ‘customer-driven’, ethical and moral to ensure their stability.

(Salz Review 2013) identified cultural shortcomings as a problem that led to the LIBOR rigging scandal. The review insisted a transformational change to restore the lost confidence and reputation amongst the public. Barclays had become too sales and profit driven and overlooked the interests of customers. Barclays lost its purpose and there was a strong drive to win as the bank got dominated by investment banking business which possessed a culture of winning. This reinforced focus on short-term financial performance which formed the basis of bonus in remuneration. ‘The more the sales, the more the bonus’ cliché took over serving customer interests. The report however recommends steps to rebuild reputation: setting high standards and transparency; board’s effectiveness; new culture and values; strong, value-driven incentivised staff and risk culture framework and control functions.

Trust is a key component of the long-term performance of the banks. However, scandals like PPI, rigging LIBOR and tax evasions have undermined the public’s confidence in the banking industry. (Alain Cohn, 2014), suggests that the ‘sales-driven’ culture weakens the honesty norm meaning that measures to re-establish an honest and moral culture is very important. Evidence from the employee of HSBC says that ‘they had to sell whether the customer wanted it or not; they were not concerned about customers’ needs as they had a target to achieve and thus sold whatever they could’. This is an example of dishonest behaviour of banks. If banks become oblivion of the fact that they do not cater customers’ needs, then it would be very difficult for public to restore their confidence in the banking system.

Some of the reports provide evidence of ‘sales-driven’ culture by the employees of some of the major banks. Former RBS executive reported the ‘sales-based bonuses has been created which is leading to intense competition amongst

employees to meet targets and sell products to customers even if they do not need it'. Whereas an employee of Halifax reported the 'introduction of cash or cabbage day where employees who meet their targets were incentivised and those who could not were made embarrassed in front of everyone by giving them cabbages'. This form of incentive leads to competition amongst employees and more specifically an 'unhealthy' competition. Being competitive is good but when the competition gets unhealthy then results take over morals thereby leading to unethical practises in an organisation. The evidence suggest that it was the culture that led to the UK banking system's train wreck. The increased competition drove employees to sell more to increase their wealth instead of banks and this is why it is recommended that indeed there should be competition but 'healthier'. Banks should shift from being 'sales-driven' to being 'customer-driven' and then introduce competition, but this competition would focus on 'who served better?' 'Who provided what the customer needs'? and any unethical or immoral practises should be immediately penalised. This would promote a healthier competition which in turn would lead to a safer and stable banking system.

The literatures and examples of evidence above highlight the adoption of 'sales culture' within the banking system and how it triggered the Big Bang of Financial Industry. Literature shows that this sales-led culture only created havoc and should be erased from the grammar of the banking industry.

Literature recommends banks to go back to being 'customer-centric' and prefer morals over results. This would ensure a safer and stable banking system that would benefit both the customers and the UK Banking Industry.

Every major policy document and researchers of financial crisis highlighted culture as a root cause and addressed the need for change but there has been little or no research on the culture of the British Retail Banking itself. The reports highlighted the adversities of the sales-led culture but none of them

pointed out three decades of profitability that this very culture brought to the British Retail Banking. There is little literature on understanding the banks' sales-led culture which might have helped in identifying the triggers to the banks' failure. The literature that exists only identified the presence of sales-led culture and the presence of greed. The author aims to bridge the gap in literature with this thesis.

Though all the reports unearthed culture as the fundamental cause of failure, yet the policy interventions only addressed structural issues like ring-fencing (Edmonds, 2011) and left 'cultural' change for the banks to execute themselves. This was introduced to put an end to universal banking and required retail and investment to be carried out by different banks. However, this was never enacted as banks would have to restructure their products as many of their products had elements of both investment and commercial banking packaged together e.g. credit default swaps and loans.

Regulators took a hands-off approach by laying the responsibility of cultural change (the prime reason of banks' debacle) on the banks' themselves because they believed that regulators are supporters and not drivers of cultural change. There have been no reports on the progress that has been made since 2008 which could prove that this cultural change was much needed. The author after bridging the first gap in literature aims to analyse if this cultural change was really needed and if so, what role could regulators have played instead of taking a hands-off approach.

Following the crisis, government had to step in and bail out banks. RBS and Lloyds received £20bn and £17bn respectively leaving the taxpayers holding 63% and 41% stake respectively in each bank. It is bizarre how private institutions that are immoral and cause nothing but social loss and private gains have to be bailed out by the taxpayers' money. There have been debates on

nationalising the banking system but is it the solution? Nationalisation is a two-edged sword. State and banks have both proved to be inefficient. Where banks were immoral, the state too initiated this ‘aggressiveness’ by annulling the Glass-Steagall Act which was the main reason for fading walls between commercial and investment banks. Yet the literature has no studies of nationalisation as a solution and if not what else could be a possible solution. The author aims to fill this gap by finding a way regulator, policy makers and banks could work in order to prevent the UK economy from facing yet another Great Depression and/or Financial Crisis.

Apart from filling the gaps in literature and current practises, this thesis associates the author’s career aspiration of working in one of the Big Five Banks as a Senior Banker and hence an in-depth knowledge of the past and current bank practises and recommending renovations to the current practises will increase the author’s chances of success as a Senior Banker.

1.12 RESEARCH QUESTION

How could a ‘regulated sales-led’ culture save the British Retail Banking from yet another Financial Crisis?

1.13 AIM

The aim of this research is to explore an issue at the very heart of the Financial Crisis and the series of scandals like PPI that followed: ‘culture’ and propose a strategy for a safer, reliable, and sustainable banking sector.

1.14 OBJECTIVES

1. To understand the sales-led culture, banks were operating in and identify the triggers to banks’ failure.
2. To evaluate how a sales-led culture-initiated product diversification and its effect on the financial and/or non-financial performance of UK retail banks.

3. To compare and contrast results from objective (2) with the financial and/or non-financial performance of UK retail banks after the cultural shift to being ‘customer-centric’.
4. To propose a strategy where regulators, policy makers and banks work together to build a strong and stable financial system.

1.15 Structure of the thesis

- Chapter 1 looks at the history of the industry, initiation of the sales-led culture, rationale, aim and objectives of this thesis.
- Chapter 2 identifies the existing literature on culture, product diversification and the banking stability.
- In Chapter 3 we provide a conceptual framework for this thesis.
- Chapter 4 looks at the research methodology used for this thesis to analyze the said phenomenon.
- Chapter 5 and 6 reports the findings and analysis of the data collected through interviews, and secondary sources and the progress made in reforming culture.
- Chapter 7 concludes the thesis by identifying author’s contribution to build a stable and strong financial system.
- In Chapter 8, the author recommends the resolutions for the various issues highlighted in chapter 5 and 6.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The sales-led culture banks operated in, though led to one of the worst crises of history yet there is very limited existing literature that studies the culture of British Retail Banking. However, this sales led culture triggered product

diversification and banks were seen to be entering into non-traditional financial activities in order to maintain their positions as financial intermediaries. The impact of diversification on bank's performance and financial stability remains an ongoing area of debate since diversification is one of the important subjects of study in the financial literature. The literature has a variety of studies that analyses diversification and its impact on bank performance. This section therefore looks at the relevant journals to highlight the contribution towards this study.

2.2 Understanding the effect of Product Diversification on the Financial Performance of UK Retail Banks.

The impact of diversification on bank's performance and financial stability remains an ongoing area of debate since diversification is one of the important subjects of study in the financial literature. The literature has a variety of studies that analyses diversification and its impact on bank performance. This section therefore looks at the relevant papers to highlight the contribution towards this study.

With diversification, banks intend to increase their credit portfolio and hence reduce their credit portfolio risk. One such important study was performed by (Acharya V. H., 2002) . They analysed 105 Italian Banks to study the effects of focus (only relying on loan portfolio) against diversification and concluded that diversification does not provide any greater safety for banks and nor does it guarantee to produce any superior performance to that of focused banks. However, the answer depends on the risk-taking behaviour of a bank. For banks who take on higher risks, diversification accompanies reduced bank returns and increased volatility. While, for the banks who take on low risk, diversification does produce a marginal improvement. (Evelyn Hayden, 2005-2006) , results too oppose the traditional theory that banks should be as diversified as possible meaning focusing increases bank's profitability.

Diversification tends to lower returns for banks in Germany and the impact of any diversification on bank's returns depends on the risk levels. Statistically positive relation between diversification and increasing bank's returns was only found in the case of medium risk levels and industrial diversification. (Kamp, 2004), studied period saw increasing diversification is mainly driven by a large number of German saving banks and corporate banks. Big banks on average neither diversified nor focused while regional and subsidiaries of foreign banks chose to focus on their loan portfolios. (David, 2005), analysed the loan portfolios of banks in Sweden and investigated the strategy behind loan portfolio diversification of banks. (Schertler, 2006), found that the growth of domestic lending depends on the characteristics of banks. Lending by smaller banks, savings banks and cooperatives including their regional institutions reacts positively to domestic sectoral growth, while lending by regional and big banks do not.

(Busch, 2009), examined the German banks and its income diversification. It was found that banks with a more diversified income base exhibit a more favourable risk-return profile meaning higher risk adjusted ROTA and ROE (return on asset and return on equity respectively), whereas for commercial banks higher ROTA and ROE accompany higher risks (volatility). (Goetz, 2012), results indicate that a competitor's diversification is positively correlated to the non-diversified (focused) bank's risk taking behaviour. Also, a bank's risk-taking behaviour increases when it itself diversifies across the markets. Hence, a focused bank can have indirect effects of diversification too, where a competitor's diversification can affect the non-diversified bank's risk-taking behaviour. (Fang, 2011), concluded that a bank's performance has a positive relationship with asset diversification and a negatively relationship with loan diversification.

(Stiroh K. a., 2006) (Stiroh K. , 2004a) (Stiroh K. , 2004b) , results contradict with each other in terms of diversification. (Stiroh K. , 2004a), found little evidence of diversification benefits between wide activity classes but considerable benefits within traditional and non-traditional activities. Whereas, (Stiroh K. , 2004b) found large diversification benefits in the form of more stable profit or income. (Chiorazzo, 2008) , found that for Italian Banks a shift towards non-interest income produces favourable risk-adjusted returns which differs from US banks who do not seem to have a positive correlation between risk adjusted returns and diversification. However, results also found that the returns diminish as the bank size increases meaning big banks do not see many improvements in their returns as a result of diversification as much as small banks do. (Cotugno, 2012) , found a positive correlation between revenue and geographic diversification to bank's performance. They also conclude how diversification helped in the bank's performance in the post financial crisis period.

(D'Souza, 2003), examined big five chartered banks in Canada and found that regional and business-line diversification is good for bank's efficiency whereas, industrial diversification is not significant for bank's efficiency. They also conclude that bank size have nothing to do with bank's efficiency, in fact it is the business line that matters. (Böve, 2010), analyses if the monitoring abilities of German Bank increases with their specialisation on certain industry sectors and finds that the sectoral specialisation on cooperative and savings banks can gather significant monitoring benefits especially for cooperative banks. (Deng S.(E.)and Elyasiani, 2008), found that geographical diversification enhances the value of bank holding company and reduces the risk. Also, increased distance between branches and bank holding companies due to diversification reduces the value of bank and increases the risk. (Tabak, 2010) found that Brazilian Bank's loan portfolios are on average more

concentrated than those of developed countries like Germany, US and Italy . Also, this concentration improves both the returns of Brazilian Banks and its risk. (Bebczuk, 2008), found that diversification significantly benefited larger Argentine banks more than the smaller ones especially during the financial crisis. Also, the big and foreign banks were found to be more diversified than the small and national banks.

Some other studies show how diversification affects the bank's performance. (Cabiles, 2012), found that securitisation has a positive relation with the loan portfolio diversification meaning banks who securitize more have a relatively bigger loan portfolio size and thus riskier assets alongside higher returns. They therefore conclude that through securitization (diversification) banks take on greater risk to attain higher returns. (Mason, 2005), analysed the diversified financial institution and established a potential to diminish a significant amount of risk. (Berry-Stölzle, 2011), analysed the businesses' diversification status working in same line and found that insurers operating in volatile businesses do not diversify more meaning no risk pooling considerations. (Arora, 2009) (Bandyopadhyay, 2010) , analysed the significance of the determinants of diversification for banks in India and the credit portfolio composition of large and medium-sized public sector banks in India respectively. (Bandyopadhyay, 2010), found that large banks do not benefit from risk diversification as much as medium-sized banks and that the portfolio risk depends on the regional and sectoral performance of credit.

The empirical literature on how diversification affects the bank's performance produces mixed results. (Saunders A. W., 1994), reviewed 18 studies to analyse whether a shift towards noninterest activities for banks lead to better performance and reduced risk. However, the study could reach to no consensus as 9 answered yes, 6 answered no while the remaining 3 could not reach a conclusion. Some other studies examined bank's performance with varying

degrees of focus and diversification. These studies oppose the traditional view that diversification improve performance and gives out a common conclusion that diversification accompanies higher risk and lower returns. (DeYoung, 2001), found that a shift towards non-interest income follows reduced returns and increased volatility for the commercial banks. (Stiroh K. , 2004b) , finds that trading revenue (non-interest income) produces increased risk and reduced profits after adjusted for risk for the commercial banks. The paper by (Acharya V. H., 2002) comes to a similar conclusion that diversification does not improve performance of Italian Banks and nor does it reduce risk. Another study (Morgan, 2003), analysed how geographical diversification affects the bank's performance and came to a similar conclusion which was negative meaning no reduced risk or higher returns that is higher ROTA or ROE. (Stiroh K. a., 2006), concluded that revenue diversification does increase the profits after being accounted for risk but these profits cancel out with the cost of getting exposed to non-interest means of income. (Sibel Yilmaz Turkmen, 2012), too comes to a similar conclusion that diversification have a negative impact on Turkish banks' performance for the studied period. (Pilloff, 2000) , concluded that banks which are geographically diversified do not have an advantage over banks which are not; meaning no additional returns due to diversification. (Demsetz, 1995), found that diversification lead to BHC take on riskier loans whilst having greater leverage and even though large BHCs have greater diversification benefits, they do not render into reduced risk because BHCs shift towards riskier activities. (Roland, 1997) , found that even though earnings from non-banking activities were relatively higher than earnings from banking activities; they were not as persistent as earnings from loans and deposits. (Baele, 2007), examined European Banks and found that diversification increases bank's returns as well as the systematic risk. Another study by (Stiroh, 2006) , concluded that a shift towards fee based income does not increase the bank's returns, but does increase the market risk. (Mercieca,

2007), concluded that a shift towards fee based income negatively effects the financial stability of banks within and no diversification benefits within and across the business lines.

The above mentioned studies portray the dull side of diversification; however literature does have various studies that contrast the darker view and brings forward a brighter side to expanding into non-interest based activities (diversification). (Templeton, The effect of nonbank diversification on bank holding companies., 1992), concluded that banks who diversify tend to be in a less risky position than banks who only involve in banking i.e. interest based earnings. The paper also concludes that banks do not necessarily have to involve in extensive diversification to be in a less risky position. Smaller amount of diversification achieved a considerable risk reduction for BHC (bank holding companies). (Cornett, 2002), found that the revenues generated from the non-banking activities improved the commercial banks' performance post the establishment of Section 20 subsidiary. (Kwan, 1998), found that commercial banks may benefit from diversification because of the low return correlation between securities and bank subsidiaries. (Santomero, 1992), analysed 123 BHC and 62 non-bank firms and concluded that bank's expansion into non-banking activities reduces risks. (Mester, 1992), found a proportionate saving in cost as a result of mixing non-banking activities with banking activities, i.e. a bank can originate loan (banking) and then sell loans or buy products (non-banking). (Canals, 1993), analysed the profits of banks and found that the increased profit and hence improved performance was due to the increased revenue from other business units (non-banking activities). (Radecki, 1999), analysed BHC's data and found that fee-based earning is important to the banking industry. (Lepetit, 2008), found a negative relation between interest margin and fee-based income in the European Banks for the studies period. (Chiorazzo, 2008), found that income diversification (non-

interest income) does increase the profits (risk-adjusted) for the Italian Banks. (Reichert, 2008), found increased gains and reduced risk when non-bank commercial and industrial sectors diversify. (Smith, Staikouras, & Wood, 2003), found that the non-interest based income did stabilise the profitability of some of the European Banks for the studied period, however interest income was found to produce more stable profits. (Gallo, 1996), found that mutual fund assets to total assets of BHC over the studied period accompanied greater profits and reduced risks.

These studies provide a mixed impression of diversification on bank's performance, while some oppose diversification; others find a brighter side to it. There are numerous studies on diversification, however not many international studies have been found which could be due to the difficulty in obtaining data and comparing them to different countries. (Sanya, 2011), analysed how non-interest income could affect the performance of banks in emerging countries and found that income diversification reduces insolvency risk and increases profits. (Buch, 2010), in their study argued that banks are likely to benefit by lending internationally due to the country specific risk diversification. However, domestic lending is preferred over international lending implying that political risk affects the composition of bank's portfolio. (Kılıçhan, 2004), studied how the diversification of credit portfolio affects the Turkish Bank's performance. However, due to data limitation their study was restricted to two years and found that diversification reduces the returns, hence showing a negative relationship between diversification and performance of Turkish Banks for the studied period.

Chathoth, (2002) used the sub sample of 128 firms from Rumelt's (1974) study and did not find any significant difference in the financial performance of related diversified, unrelated diversified and non-diversified categories of firms. Aggarwal et al, (2003) analysed the time series data of Beatrice company

since its inception in 1891 to its growth as a food conglomerate and reported that the related product diversification of the firm produce value whereas unrelated product diversification could not contribute in terms of value addition of the firm. Aggarwal et al, (2003) created a random sample of 246 Fortune 500 firms to study the relationship of product diversification with risk and return. They found a U-shaped graph for the relationship between corporate product diversification and stock return as well as risk. Ramaswamy et al, (2002) selected a sample of 2,637 US firms for the period 1981-90 to study the difference in financial performance between diversified and undiversified firms and reported that the undiversified firms outperformed the diversified firms. However, in the context of risk, the undiversified firms have a higher risk as compared to diversified firms. Researchers remained divided on the product diversification effect in the first decade of the 21st century. Lins and Servaes (2002) used a sample of over 1,000 firms from five emerging economies to study whether a diversified firm's shares were traded at a premium or a discount and found that the diversified firms' shares were traded on a discount of 7% as compared to undiversified firms' shares.

Horizontal Diversification Horizontal Product diversification relates to the acquiring or developing new products or offering new services that could appeal to the company's current customer groups. In this case the company relies on sales and technological relations to the existing product lines. For example a dairy, producing cheese adds a new type of cheese to its products. Horizontal diversification consists, instead, of corporate expansion into more than one industry across businesses not necessarily related to each other. With respect to vertical integration, the theoretical grounding behind horizontal diversification is less clear-cut. Two partially competing explanations are at work. Another possible way to go is horizontal diversification. This can be described as the introduction of new products which, while they do not contribute to the present product line in any way, cater to missions which lie

within the company's know-how and experience in technology, finance, and marketing (Igor, 2002). Three studies provide a broad overview of the general effect of horizontal diversification and do not leave much doubt about its financial consequences. Morck, Schleifer, and Vishny (1990) show that acquiring firms, engaged in takeovers, experience negative returns as an immediate value adjustment to their future expected performance, when they announce unrelated acquisitions; while Lang and Stulz (1994) and Berger and Ofek (1995) find that, in most cases, diversified firms trade at a discount relative to a portfolio of single-segment firms in the same industries. Numerous studies indeed confirm this and, specifically, show that horizontal expansion often results in lower firm performance because of various agency problems. For instance, these include incompetent or irrational managers, competent but self-interested managers, wasteful spending in general and wasteful investment in poorly performing divisions and, finally, the inability of the internal economy of the firm to correctly signal to managers good investment opportunities (Rajan, Servaes and Zangales, 1999). There is no significant effect of horizontal diversification on the financial performance

Vertical Product Diversification Vertical Product diversification occurs when the company goes back to previous stages of its production cycle or moves forward to subsequent stages of the same cycle - production of raw materials or distribution of the final product. For example, if you have a company that does reconstruction of houses and offices and you start selling paints and other construction materials for use in this business. This kind of product diversification may also guarantee a regular supply of materials with better quality and lower prices (Hill and Jones 1992). On vertical integration, Coase (1937) sets the foundation of the theory of the firm. Corporations and markets are alternative choices with respect to production organization, and transaction costs are the cornerstone. Corporations vertically expand until the marginal cost of internalizing production equals the marginal cost of outsourcing it in

the market. For instance, when buyers incur sunk costs to manage repeated transactions, they develop an incentive to (upward) internalize suppliers into their firm, to avoid potential losses linked to the latter's opportunism. Similarly, sellers are inclined to downward internalize distribution when exposed to potential losses because of high concentration among their customers. By leveraging on this general rationale, various authors have further discussed the factual consistency of firm expansion. Bain (1956, 1959) points out that vertical integration, like the integration of separate activities along a value chain, reflects the creation of market power. Tirole (1988) sees it as a profitable response to the cost of contiguous monopolies (Tirole 1988). Others think it may facilitate price discrimination (Perry, 1978) or it can be used to raise rivals' costs by increasing their costs of entry in the industry (Hart and Tirole, 1990). Finally, Stigler (1951) advances a life-cycle theory arguing that, in an infant industry, vertical integration is more likely because the demand for specialized inputs is too small to support their independent production. In general, contractual incompleteness, combined with asset specificity, complexity, and uncertainty, play a central role in driving transaction costs and in the increase of the probability that opportunistic behaviour may plague market relations (Carlton, 1979). So, as Joskow (1998) points out, 'There is clearly no shortage of theories identifying potential incentives for vertical integration.' With this abundance of hypotheses, empirical studies have obviously thrived and have attempted to assess the factual importance of various factors as principal drivers of transaction costs. Most industrial organization surveys are product-based and focus on single products or services. Among them, studies deal with automobile components (Klein 2000) with coal: (Kerkvliet 1991); with aerospace systems: (Masten 1984); with aluminium (Stukey 1983, Hennart 1988); with chemicals: (Lieberman 1991); with timber: (Globerman and Schwindt 1986)); with carbonated beverages: (Muris, Scheffman and Spiller 1992); with pulp and paper: (Ohanian 1994);

with property-liability insurance: (Regan, 1997). In all these studies, the evidence significantly supports the role of transaction costs in driving vertical integration. Conglomerate Product Diversification Maksimovic and Gordon (2002) collected the 3,74,339 segment observations of the US firms for the period 1975- 92 to study the optimal size of conglomerates and their growth across different industries. They found higher growth in the conglomerates in similar industry as compared to different industry. Recently, Villalonga (2004), using a new data source of Business Information Tracking Series (BITS), found that diversified firms are traded at relatively larger premium than the firms engaged in specialized businesses. Concentric and conglomerate product diversifications are the two product diversification strategies that they may follow (Tongliet al, 2005; Stimpertet al, 1997; Singh et al, 2003; Nayyar, 1992). Entering unrelated areas or industries is referred to as the conglomerate product diversification through which corporations aim to reduce the overall risk exposure and expand growth opportunities. Related product diversification, on the other hand, refers to expanding beyond the existing product lines and/or market of the current industry (Nayyar, 1992; Myers, 1984; Lins et al, 2002). Related product diversification is believed to lower the profitability rate in developed countries or economies. Focusing on core competencies are suggested over the conglomerates for the western economies. In conglomerate product diversification the company is moving to new products or services that have no technological or commercial relation with current products, equipment, distribution channels, but which may appeal to new groups of customers. The major motive behind this kind of product diversification is the high return on investments in the new industry. Furthermore, the decision to go for this kind of product diversification can lead to additional opportunities indirectly related to further developing the main company business - access to new technologies, opportunities for strategic partnerships. Finally Corporate Product diversification involves production of

unrelated but profitable goods. It is often tied to large investments where there may also be high returns. Therefore, this study fills the gap not covered by these previous studies by investigating the effects of product diversification on financial performance. This is important as it adds value to these past studies. It provides more evidences on the importance of product diversification on firm performance, shareholder value creation, firm growth all of which are performance indicators. So, product diversification may be linked to these performance indicators so is the need for this study to explore if in the process of these performances, there is financial performance.

The changing roles that banks have adopted can broadly be described as an exploitation of growth strategies available to them in the market and effectively incorporating such strategies in enabling them to grow and expand in terms of market share while at the same time ensuring that their presence is felt in the industry. Theoretically, the banks are in essence adopting the Ansoff Matrix theory espoused by Ansoff and McDonald (1990) which brings into fore the four main growth strategies namely market penetration, product development, market development and diversification. Market Penetration refers to where an organisation takes increased share of its existing markets with its existing product range (Wheeler and Hunger, 2008). An organisation builds on the existing strategic capabilities and does not require the organisation to venture into uncharted territory, essentially maintaining the scope. Moreover, greater market share implies increased power vis a vis buyers and suppliers (in terms of the five forces), economies of scale through more efficient manufacturing, distribution, purchasing power and overhead sharing and lastly experience curve benefits (Johnson et al, 2008). Product development is where an organisation delivers modified or new products (or services) to existing markets. This in essence entails a limited extension of organizational scope (Johnson et al, 2008). In practice market penetration will probably require

some 9 product development, but product development involves a greater degree of innovation to come up with solutions for the market specific needs (Keller and Kotler, 2006). Miles and Snow (1987), describes market development as offering existing products to new market though limiting the extend of the scope. This strategic decision directs the firm to either new segments or even new users of their products. The strategies applied often try to lure clients away from competitors or introduce existing products in foreign market or introduce new brand names in a market (Keller and Kotler, 2006). Mintzberg and Ghoshal (1999) views diversification as strictly a strategy that takes the organisation away from both its existing markets and its existing products radically increases the organisation's scope. The strategy essentially may be in the form of concentric or conglomerate but a good deal of diversification in practice involves building on relationships with existing markets or products. Frequently too, market penetration and product development entail some diversifying adjustment of products or markets (Johnson et al, 2008). Pearce and Robinson (2007) acknowledge that as organisations move from their starting point of existing products and existing markets, then the more the organisation has to learn because diversification is just one direction for developing the organisation, and needs to be considered alongside its alternatives. The drivers of diversification, its various forms, and the ways in which it is managed in relation to firm performance forms the foundation of this study. Product Diversification Strategies In the application of product diversification strategies, a good opportunity can be found outside the present businesses (Kotler, 2006). A good opportunity is one in which the industry is highly attractive, and the company has the mix of business strengths to be successful. Ansoff (1990) in the market grid notes that on the other hand diversification strategies can also decrease risk because a large corporation can spread certain risks if it operates on more than one market. Product diversification strategies are broadly classified into related diversification

(different lines of products are linked) or unrelated diversification (no links between 10 products). Related diversification is diversifying into businesses that possess strategic fit. Strategic fit exists when businesses has sufficiently related value chains that give rise to important opportunities for example, transferring skills and expertise from one activity to another (Johnson and Whittington 2008). It involves developing beyond ones product but still within the confines of the industry (Kotler and Keller, 2006). Related diversification as well refers to getting into a new business activity in a different industry that is related to a company's existing business activity by commonalities between one or more components of each activity's value chain. These commonalities are mainly marketing, manufacturing or technological. Gains arise from the transferring and leveraging of competencies and from the sharing of resources (Johnson and Whittington 2008). Lepetit et al (2007) suggests that the ideal concentric diversification occurs when the combined company profits increase strengths and opportunities, as well as decrease weaknesses and exposure to risk. Product diversification may also take the form of unrelated (conglomerate) diversification that is entry into industries that have no obvious connection to any of a company's value chain activities in the present industry. The chief focus is to increase profitability by exploiting general organization's competencies however, it is difficult to transfer or leverage competencies and to realize economies of scope (Griffin and Pasta, 2010). Occasionally a firm, particularly a very large one, plans to acquire a business because it represents the most promising investment opportunity available. Hamel and Prahalad (1998) states that the principal and often sole concern of the acquiring firm is the profit pattern of the venture and thus there is little concern given to creating product market synergy with existing businesses, unlike the approach taken in concentric diversification. Miles and Snow (1987) states that firms adopting a concentric diversification are seeking a balance in their portfolios between current businesses with cyclical sales and acquired businesses with counter-

cyclical sales, between high-cash/low-opportunity and low cash/high-opportunity businesses, or between debt-free and highly leveraged businesses. Since conglomerate diversification involves seeking new businesses that have no relationship to its current technology, products or markets, this gives an impression that 11 firms can be involved in businesses that are completely in a different industry for example banks venturing into hospitality industry. However, in its quest to diversify its products in unrelated industries, the firm may encounter significant challenges. A question therefore arises: “To what extent can firms diversify into non-core industries?” That is, are there businesses that firms should not engage in, possibly because of conflict of interest, lack of adequate expertise, among other constraints that may arise? (Pearce and Robinson, 2007).

2.4 Empirical Literature on Product Diversification

Berger and Ofek (2010) in their study on diversification effect on firm value describe diversification as the entry of a company into new lines of activity through a process of internal development or through acquisition, which entails changes in its administrative structure, system, or other management procedures. Any modification of a current product that serves to expand the potential market implies that the company is following a strategy of product diversification. Product diversification strategy is different from product development in that it involves creating a new customer base, which expands the market potential of the original product. This is achieved through brand extensions or new brands, but in some cases the product modification may create a new market by creating new uses for the product. The study suggested that related product diversification achieves competitive advantage for firms through economies of scale and other synergies from using the firm’s resources and capabilities across different product lines. Luo (2009) adds that such synergies from product diversification are more likely to be realized when firms expand into related lines of business or industries. Furthermore, product related diversification emphasizes on operational synergy (economies of

scale), that is, increase on competitiveness beyond what can be achieved by engaging in two markets or activities separately. This translates to firms benefiting from declining unit costs by leveraging on product relatedness and thus expand the firms' performance gains. Kiyohiko and Rose (2008) did a study on Japanese firms and established that most of these firms appear to have shifted their operational focus from developing growth-enabling core competencies to reducing organizational costs through diversification. Most Japanese firms experienced extensive Mergers & Acquisitions (M&A) activity at earlier points in their corporate histories. According to Kiyohiko and Rose (2008) the recent flurry of M&A's in global market is nothing new, but rather a resurgence of past practices in a bid to allow rapid downsizing and increased scale of economies while avoiding massive layoffs. Rowley and Baum (2009) from their study on 40 Canadian firms with special focus on the financial industry developed the theory that brokerage and investment activities that financial firms are recently engaging in allow them to have a greater discretion in choosing syndicate partners and together can provide access to timely and non-redundant information to investors. Lepetit et al (2007) in their research in the financial industry states that the banking industry is consolidating at a rapid pace, with integration of related financial services (insurance, credit card) along with input services (cheque clearing payments, electronic funds transfer and money transfer services) into the parent companies. This in effect results to the banks acquiring operational synergy. The study points that product related diversification "essentially putting one's eggs in similar baskets" has emerged as a balanced way to both reduce risk and leverage synergy. When diversification involves the addition of a business related to the firm in terms of technology, markets, or products, it is concentric diversification. With this type of strategy, the new businesses selected possess a high degree of compatibility with the current business, thus the acquiring company needs to search for new businesses with products, markets, distribution channels,

technologies and resource requirements that are familiar but not identical, synergistic and not wholly interdependent. This diversification mode therefore means seeking new products that have technological or marketing synergies with existing product lines, even though the products themselves appeal to a different group of customers. The study suggested that concentric diversification, as a strategy, may be more logical for service firms than for product firms because many offerings of new core services by a firm are not compatible with the existing line or existing market segments. A study conducted by Hitt, Hoskisson and Kim (2011) shows that firms that have diversified into products that use the existing internal resources or capabilities of the firm will benefit from economies of scale thus earn higher returns. The study asserts that the payoff created by diversification may be magnified when Multi-national corporations capitalize on economic rents derived not only from product and market diversity but also from the various advantages embodied in foreign activities such as knowledge acquisition, capability development, risk reduction and complementary synergies. Yaser (2010) on a study on competitive strategies and firm performance acknowledges that while unrelated diversification helps firms achieve economies of scope, the benefits of this strategy might be offset by several disadvantages when implemented in international markets. International diversification into unrelated product areas means a broadened scope of operations, which implies that additional costs may be incurred because the transferability of a competitive advantage between countries can be inhibited by institutional and cultural barriers. Diversifying into unrelated product areas in foreign marketplaces also frustrates corporations due to the difficulty of applying existing product experience to unfamiliar market conditions. By contrast, related diversification allows multinational corporations to realize economies of scale and since foreign markets represent additional sales outlets for existing products, potential profit gains are made possible. According to Matsusaka (2010) study

on Chinese firms, related diversification strategy is preferable because it enables subsidiaries of MNCs to export more products to international markets through their foreign parents' distribution channels and global networks. It also helps local firms upgrade technological skills and managerial expertise. This institutional effect reduces transaction costs and operational uncertainty and is thus beneficial to subsidiary performance.

These studies provide a mixed impression of diversification on bank's performance, while some oppose diversification; others find a brighter side to it. However, the literature only accounts for financial perspective and not the non-financial perspective. Non-financial perspective will make us better understand the essence of culture that the banks operated in and how are the banks' overdoing themselves non-financially if not financially than the sales-led culture which supposedly led to the wrecked banking system, so this thesis aims to fill this gap.

2.3 Understanding the effect of Culture on the financial performance of UK Retail Banks

Culture is considered to be one of the main reasons for banks' debacle; it is therefore important to understand what the literature says about it. (Lui A. , 'Greed, Recklessness, Dishonesty: and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK banks between 2004 and 2009', 2015), confirmed the banks' shift to sales-led culture and the rashness in this culture during the studied period 2004-09. As highlighted above banks went past their morality in order to relish profits and put the economy at risk. So, it is important to consider what persuades them to be unethical, as (Trevino, 2014) concludes that it is a leader who motivates his/her employees to be ethical and/or moral. However, this contradicts the sales-led culture which was 'morally straying' because

employees saw their tactics as mere target achievers and not unethical since it affected their pay. This brings the author down to analyse how remuneration and incentives affects the morality and ethicality of employees.

Since the culture was driven by sales, it becomes evident that the bonuses will be directly related to the sales. The bonuses that form part of remuneration drive employees to increase their earnings rather than the banks' meaning individual gains outweigh the social gains. This was further analysed by (Douglas H. Frank, 2014), and found that a large number of loan decisions were made for the individuals' financial interest. It was also found that leaders with higher firm specific human capital are more productive in selling and manipulating loans to increase their payouts. (Fortado, 'The yin and yang of introducing a sales culture: the Amalgam Bank Case', 2014), investigated the sales-led culture in Amalgam Bank and found a culture driven by sales which brought increased sales followed by upset customers who were forced to buy products irrespective of their needs. Banks unethical and immoral behaviours lead to one of the worst crisis of history which shook the publics' confidence on the banking system and the only way suggested to restore trust was cultural change (Cohen, 'Governance as the driver of culture change and risk management', 2015).

Books like (Brummer, *Bad Banks: Greed, Incompetence and the Next Global Crisis*, 2014) and (Fraser, 2014), investigated banks and provided an insight to crisis and discussed the cultural problem at UK Banks. (Fraser, 2014), by interviewing the employees of RBS found leadership to be the reason for unethical and immoral behaviour of employees which raises serious questions on its corporate governance and the failure of regulators. (Brummer, *Bad Banks: Greed, Incompetence and the Next Global Crisis*, 2014), recommends customer driven culture to restore ethical and moral behaviour amongst employees.

(Anthony Salz, 2013), in their investigation highlighted culture as the main reason for scandals like LIBOR and begged for a transformational change to revive the banking sector. The report recommended transparency, new culture, and control function to restore confidence and revive the banking sector.

The literature on banking culture and the UK financial crisis can be divided up into three parts. Each of these is informative in its' own way. First, there are the formal reports on the crisis (such as the 2009 Walker Review and the 2011 Independent Commission on Banking). These often involve in depth analysis of what went wrong and what to do about it, considering of the views of multiple actors within the system. Second, there are some excellent histories of the crisis at individual banks (such as RBS, Lloyds, and HBOS), which often give some insight into the inner workings of banks and the individual decision makers within them. Finally, there are academic studies of the crisis, which attempt to provide genuinely independent analysis of what went wrong and what to do about it. Each of these sets of literature gives a fairly consistent picture of the cultural problem in UK banking. In this section we begin by examining the academic literature, and then discuss some of the books. We will cover some of the formal reports in the case studies, the Salz Review (2013), which was commissioned by Barclays. Indeed, the Salz Review has a very good review of the literature on culture itself, which emphasises the general lessons that can be drawn from it and how these specifically apply to banking. It is worth noting that there is also a general literature on culture and unethical behaviour. See for example, Trevino et al. (2014) who summarise the literature on what causes unethical behaviour in organisations. Among the many insights of the behavioural literature relevant to banking, is the significant role that leaders play in shaping behaviour; the need to align published codes of conduct with assessments of performance (or risk them having a negative impact); and the capacity for 'moral

disconnection' whereby individuals don't see their 'bad' behaviour as wrong. There is also evidence that pay affects performance. Banking is notable for its substantial use of individual sales-based bonus payments to staff both in its retail and investment banking arms. The empirical evidence does support the view that group-based incentives are better for corporate culture than individual based incentives. For instance, Blasi et al. (2016) examine the 100 best companies to work for, over the period 2005-07. They find that group pay incentives are associated with more information sharing, higher trust in supervisors and a more positively rated work environment. Frank and Obloj (2014) show that individual employee sales incentives are not necessarily in the financial interests of the bank, by examining many loan decisions. They find that bank employees at a retail bank can use their in-depth understanding of the sales incentives to manipulate their sales in ways, which improve their bonuses while reducing the overall return to the bank (e.g. by making the loan interest rate lower to improve their loan sales). They show that for managers with better knowledge of the bank in question (what they call higher 'firm specific human capital') the losses are higher. They attribute this to 'adverse learning'. There have been some excellent academic studies on culture and the financial crisis. Spicer et al. (2014) report on the results of 57 interviews with executives and front-line staff in 11 retail banks. They find that 'an aggressive sales culture' was a major contributor to the financial crisis. They discuss how regulators and governments have delegated much of the 'softer' cultural change agenda to the private initiative of the banks themselves. Banks have largely responded to this with culture change processes, but these remain 'fragile' and prone to failure. They also report a widespread view that culture change will take a generation and that significant change will take until at least 2019. The paper suggests that consistency all the way down the organisation (i.e., not just change at the top) and long-term commitment are necessary. Lui (2015) examines the cultural

reasons behind the crisis, by examining the behaviour of Northern Rock, RBS, Barclays, Lloyds and HSBC in the period 2004-2009. She finds evidence in support of her two hypotheses, namely: that the banks changed from having a customer focussed culture to sales driven one; and that there was evidence of ‘greed, recklessness and dishonesty’ in both retail and investment banking the run up to the crisis. In line with this, Fortado and Fadil (2014) offer an in-depth study of the introduction of a sales driven banking culture. They conduct interviews with the staff of Amalgam Bank in the US (one of the top ten largest banks). They find evidence consistent with the detailed observations of what happened in the UK. Thus, giving front line branch staff sales incentives reduced the quality of the customer experience (because customers had to spend longer in the branch), sales quotas were perceived as unrealistic and caused tensions between managers and staff. The result was unhappy staff, increased turnover of employees and unfair management practices. Cohen (2015) discusses what financial institutions need to do to restore the trust they have lost in the crisis. She suggests that it is important that corporate governance processes support culture change. She develops a set of suggestions to help do this. These include pervasive adherence to a set of values, which are then used for setting pay and promotion, and regular monitoring of the process of ‘embedding’ the values. As we discuss below, this is something that our case study banks are attempting to do. There have been a good number of books on individual banks and the crisis. Fraser (2014) is based on interviews with approximately 120 employees of RBS. This includes a documentation of the culture of RBS, which was much too deferential to its crisis CEO, Fred Goodwin. This book presents the story of RBS as a classic morality tale of an overreaching bank, driven by the ambition of its CEO and hubris he created around him (among senior staff, outside directors and major shareholders), which caused external voices not to be raised against his strategy. This view is supported in Martin

(2013) who discusses how a ‘previously modest, Presbyterian, cautious Scottish institution...went bust’. Again, a significant amount of blame is heaped on Fred Goodwin, but the role of the regulator, the Financial Services Authority (FSA), is also criticised for its ineffective regulation. Fallon (2015) discusses the Lloyds takeover of HBOS. This book documents how Lloyds, which had previously been the most conservative of the big 4 British retail banks, was persuaded to takeover HBOS in late 2008. HBOS had been fully nationalised in October 2008. The result was Lloyds-HBOS (now the Lloyds Banking Group, LBG) ended up being 43.4% owned by the taxpayer by early 2009, as the full extent of the losses at HBOS became clear. Lloyds undertook the merger partly under government pressure, but also because it allowed to fulfil its long-held ambitions to expand its retail business in a way that never would have been allowed in normal circumstances. This story has a prequel, which is discussed in Perman (2012), which is the story of HBOS itself, which had been a merger of two venerable institutions Bank of Scotland and Halifax. As the Amazon.co.uk introduction to the book puts it: ‘In 1995 Bank of Scotland celebrated 300 years as Britain’s oldest commercial bank...Voted ‘most admired bank’, respected by competitors, applauded by investors, and trusted by customers...less than 15 years later it was bust...’ Perman’s thesis is that ‘simple’ banking rules were ‘ignored’, rules that had kept the bank in business for 300 years. The rules that were ignored are documented in Moore (2015). Paul Moore was HBOS’s head of group regulatory risk from 2002-2004 and was fired for blowing the whistle on HBOS’s move into the high-risk strategy that eventually caused its failure. Other books document the on-going cultural problems at UK banks. Brummer (2014) suggests that there has yet to be significant cultural change in UK banking, the bonus culture still drives behaviour and there are on-going crises such as PPI. He suggests that radical reform is still needed. Tett’s (2015) general book is also relevant on this as she highlights the

tendency for big banks to suffer from ‘silo’ effects, whereby the various bits of banks (such as risk management and sales) do not communicate effectively, and obvious warning signs are ignored.

There is a significant body of existing academic literature looking at the process of culture change in banking. To provide a solid background for our research, I undertook a systematic review of the literature on this topic.

There are 25 studies exploring culture change in banks which I thought were relevant. Each of these studies used a range of different methods including surveys, historical and archival analysis and extended participant observation. The findings of the studies are extremely varied (See Table). However, I think there are five themes which cut across these studies:

- **The rise of a sales culture.** Many of these papers track the shift from a more stable ‘welfare’ oriented culture with-in banking towards a sales culture. They point out this shift mirrored a broader shift in society where society became more consumerist, a culture of ‘enterprise’ became widespread, and there was a willingness by customers to take on more debt. In addition, these studies point out the rise of sales culture gave rise to profound changes in the way bankers thought about themselves at work. In the words of one book, they started to think about themselves as ‘sellers’, not as ‘tellers’.

- **Bankers become cut off from society and their own bodies.** A number of studies, particularly in the investment banking context, found the hard-driving culture had some profound personal implications for bankers. It meant they began to ignore other demands or issues in society which could not be put into strictly economic terms. It also meant they began to ignore their own bodies and would often become ill or troubled through overwork.

- **Trying to create a single uniform culture is wishful thinking.** Another finding cutting across many studies is that banks which gave different

branches and divisions some freedom to translate a culture to fit with their own specific concerns tended to be more successful in driving through culture change initiatives. People were most loyal to their location or branch, not to the bank as a whole. Banks which insisted on a single uniform culture throughout the bank tended to face a far more difficult challenge. Often these uniform change initiatives would be derailed.

• **Culture change sparks resistance and politics.** A number of studies we looked at documented how culture change initiatives often sparked intense political jockeying and resistance. Often change initiatives were undermined through many processes of resistance within the bank. One study of large UK bank found that multiple change initiatives created a ‘culture of complaint’. People were actually bound together by a common fondness for complaining about the most recent managerial initiative.

References	Methodology	Findings
(Dietz, 2004)	Survey of 160 branches of a US bank with 2,616 employees and 17,480 customers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive correlation between customer contact and customer satisfaction. • The idea that there is a unified organizational service climate is refuted – the service climate is different across different branches. • It was recommended that bank should focus on individual branches not the

		<p>overall organizational approach to service.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees who deal with customers have stronger relationships with customer attitudes. • Banking service is about forming a relationship.
(Saparito, 2004)	A survey of 217 bank managers and 1093 customers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust is the key in order to maintain a good customer relationship and to prevent customers from switching to competitors.
(Smith V. , 1990)	Interviews with middle line managers and corporate trainers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top managers using middle line managers as scape goat and blaming them for their poor strategic decisions. • Middle line managers played an important role in the productivity of banks' performance whereas, senior managers attempt to increase

productivity lead to lack of job security.

(Weeks, 2004)	Eight month observation and 6 years fieldwork at one UK bank.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bank employees' were not fond of bank being risk averse, too bureaucratic and not at all customer focused.• Employees however remained loyal to their jobs due to their love for their respective branches and not the bank itself.
(Schneider, 1980)	A survey of a subset of a bank in the USA and 2060 customers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Branch employees took service quality much more seriously than the bureaucratic top management.
(Ho, 2009)	An observation period of 17 months and over 100 interviews in	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bank was short term focused instead of long-term which led to job insecurity and volatility. Bank was operating on a strategy of no strategy and had no long term plans.

	one of New York's Investment Bank.	
(Michel A. , 2012)	An observation period of 9years which included 600 interviews at 2 US investment banks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banks espoused autonomy and work-life balance. However, there was habitual self chosen overwork. • Initially the bankers were socialized into a culture of hard-work and long hours. Overwork caused conflict between bankers and their bodies. After 4 years body breakdowns threatened their performance. • By year 6 bankers learnt to 'listen to their bodies'. Inadvertently, this closer relationship with their body led to unquestioning loyalty to hard work. It was only by accepting natural limitations that the work regime was sustainable.
(Buono, 1985)	Survey of 2 banks pre and post merger.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a significant issue of culture shock between the two banks during merger where culture was only seen as a foundation for providing symbols and meanings.

(Wright, 1990)	Interview and Survey conducted in USA with 264 bank tellers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For non-career-oriented tellers, a supervisory style was needed for job satisfaction and organizational commitments. • Whereas, for career-oriented tellers, a people-oriented supervisory style was needed where they could participate in decision making.
(Knights D. &., 1998)	Observation of 25 staff at a bank going through organizational change and document analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong leadership or good communication do not fix the problems relating to change and leads to organizational politics.
(McCabe, 2009)	Observation at a UK retail bank and interviews with 82 employees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiation of sales-led culture due to increased competition and deregulation. Branches became selling places due to proliferation of call centers.

and 54
managers.

(Michel A. (., 2014)	An observation period of 2 years at 2 investment banks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bank 2 were market leaders whereas Bank 1 struggled to change and react to the market.• Bank 2's ability to change credit goes to the fact that staff at lower level were successful in adapting to market changes and not wait for top managers to plan or strategize.
(Chreim, 2006)	Interviewing 46 employees at 2 federal banks in Canada.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Explored the introduction of sales-led culture and employees' resistance.• Opposition from employees' regarding the changed culture which encouraged aggressive sales culture.
(Kerr, 2012)	Published Accounts of RBS, academic papers, financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The old guard in Scottish banking consisted of paternalistic and conservative notions that reproduced the local Scottish identity of prudence and caution.

	<p>press and newspapers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rise of a new disposition influence by USA business culture. Senior management gaining MBAs from US business schools. • Led to changes to branches that saw them become sales outlets. This process of modernizing saw staff transformed from professional advisors embedded in the community into salespeople with targets to meet. • A ‘culture of fear’ proliferated.
<p>(Nayak, 2008)</p>	<p>Secondary data and 11 interviews.</p>	<p>Change in culture to creating confident customers.</p> <p>Banks are now more focused towards shareholder value creation.</p> <p>Employees must learn customer service skills which are monitored and reinforced through performance related pay and appraisals.</p> <p>Successful achievement of targets is crucial for managers. Their salary, bonus, career progression, status and job security rely on their ability to</p>

achieve required results within the performance culture.

(Hargie, 2010)	Analysis of the testimony of 4 CEOs in response to the 2008 crisis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Senior leaders were culprits but expressions like regrets were used to avoid it.
(Knights D. &, 2012)	Analysis of secondary data and empirical research on financial service board in UK and Sweden.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The crisis was a result of aggressive masculine behavior.• Masculine behavior combined with personal interests one of the major triggers to the crisis.• High salaries and bonuses serve as a proxy for the social recognition that is so elusive and precarious in the banking industry.
(Knights D. &, 1997)	Case studies and company visits. 55 insurance companies, 15 banks and 26	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Changing the culture is not an easy job.• New agendas needed and senior management needs to lead by example also improving bonuses and

	building societies.	rewards and keeping in touch with how staff perceive the policies.
(Carretta, 2010)	Text-analysis approach Sample: national regulators (Italy), Italian banks and Basel Committee.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a significant difference in culture between regulators and banks. This is indicated in the language they used in organizational statements.
(Harris, 2002)	Interviews relating to new technology projects in the UK banking industry 43 bank managers and consultants and 5 case studies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning from past mistakes, or even building upon past successes, continues to be the exception rather than the rule. • There is a reluctance to disseminate lessons learned throughout the organization. • As a result, the full potential offered by new technologies will continue to elude banks. • ‘Banking Culture’ is an attitude of complacency amongst the major

players based upon historical success rather than commercial reality.

Banking culture tended to reduce their perceived need to learn from past mistakes and hence inhibited the potential of new technologies

(Knights D. &, 1997) Multi-method study. Case study, observation and interviews at 2 UK branches implementing TQM.

- Top-down culture and quality assurance was difficult due to difficulty in controlling the employees since customer satisfaction is intangible.
- There was a resistance in cultural change as tellers solved issues through tacit skills and not reporting to managers.

(Benkhoff, 1997)	A survey of 340 employees in Germany.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bank's branch performance is highly correlated with employee commitment and hard work.
------------------	---------------------------------------	--

2.4 Conclusion

Literature provides us with evidence of how culture affected banks' stability but overlooks the positives of this culture. The literature neglects the role leaders played towards this crisis and blamed everything on culture. Regulators too took a hands-off approach and watched the banking sector coming towards this dead-end. The author believes bad leadership and regulators' hands-off approach as one of the drivers of the Financial Crisis and therefore aims to do a detailed analysis of this sales-led culture and instead of literatures' recommendation of deleting this culture from the grammar; wishes to find the triggers that caused the crisis.

While there are many other quantitative tools for studying culture, they will often only give you a 'thin' understanding of culture within an organization. To develop a 'thick' and more in-depth understanding of a culture, qualitative research methods are needed. All the best studies of organizational cultures have involved some use of ethnographic methods. These involve periods of extended participant observation whereby a researcher spends time observing and to some extent participating in the daily life of the organization. This will allow the research to get beyond the attitudes of employees and espoused values of senior managers. Instead they will be able to identify the artefacts that are important to organizational members, what the range of espoused values are

within an organisation, and most importantly what the underlying assumptions are within an organization. Undertaking an ethnographic study involves an extended period of observation which is recorded in field notes and then written up into an ethnographic account. Ethnographic research is time intensive but can yield insightful in-depth accounts of a particular culture.

One recent approach to ethnographic research which could prove useful in studying banking culture is ‘in-house ethnography’. Instead of having a trained ethnographer come into an organization and learn the culture from scratch, people who are already embedded within a culture are trained in ethnographic methods so they can record their own culture. This approach has some significant benefits – it overcomes access problems and means the researcher is already seen as an insider. However, it possesses a significant challenge – often the in-house ethnographer finds it difficult to get significant distance from their own organization to begin to see its unique and strange characteristics. To achieve this, they need to be provided with some basic training in concepts of culture and ethnographic methods. They also typically need ongoing support and supervision which ensures they are able to effectively ask questions and gain some degree of perspective on their own organization. This can be facilitated by working alongside other in-house ethnographers in other similar organisations.

3. Conceptual Framework

Retail Banking is an essential part of the UK financial system. Following the shift to Universal Banking Model in 1980, this sector relished increased profitability with the collective balance sheet accounting to 500% more than the UK GDP. However, the Financial Crisis of 2008 got this sector into crisis,

where some banks failed while others had a near miss. Following the crisis, a period of learning and rectifying began but the manipulation of LIBOR scandal in 2012 baffled the public as despite the crisis, banks continued their unethical and immoral practises. Ever since the crisis, retail division had to pay £38.5bn in fines and these unethical practises got the complaints to Financial Ombudsman Services to as high as 400,000 post the crisis. The banks, regulators and policymakers were alarmed by these costly failures and set up an inquiry to find out what went wrong and what disinters was the aggressive sales culture that the banks operated in. Banks recently committed to change their culture back to being ‘customer-centric’.

Banks are now committed to change their cultures; however, no researcher appreciated the whooping profitability this sector relished for three decades and yet no study highlighted the ignorance of regulators in this issue. Culture, despite being the major reason for the worst crisis in history has been left for the banks to execute. Regulators take a hands-off approach by stating that culture cannot be regulated and then trusts the same banks that were the reason of the worst economic turmoil to execute it themselves.

Every major policy document and researchers of financial crisis highlighted culture as a root cause and addressed the need for change but there has been little or no research on the culture of the British Retail Banking itself. The reports highlighted the adversities of the sales-led culture but none of them pointed out three decades of profitability that this very culture brought to the British Retail Banking. There is little literature on understanding the banks’ sales-led culture which might have helped in identifying the triggers to the banks’ failure. The literature that exists only identified the presence of sales-led culture and the presence of greed.

Though all the reports unearthed culture as the fundamental cause of failure, yet the policy interventions only addressed structural issues like ring-fencing and

left 'cultural' change for the banks to execute themselves. Regulators took a hands-off approach by laying the responsibility of cultural change (the prime reason of banks' debacle) because they believed that regulators are supporters and not drivers of cultural change.

Retail Banks in UK have pledged to change their existing culture and recognised this as a necessary approach to re-gain public trust and improve profitability. It is not enough that we know that **what** banks have done to mitigate the crisis, but it is more important to know **how** banks achieve this. The author is taking an inside-out approach to analyse and understand banks' strategic responses post the crisis and therefore emphasising on the **how** aspect.

Banks have recognised **customer-centric culture** as a necessary approach to regain public trust and improve profitability. However, the author proposes a **regulated sales-led culture** following the understanding of strategic changes in Retail Banking.

This study aims to answer the following central question:

How could a 'regulated sales-led' culture save the British Retail Banking from yet another Financial Crisis of 2008?

A **Balanced Scorecard along with a process oriented** strategic framework is outlined in Figure 3. The proposed framework presents a mix of internal and external controls for a safer, reliable and sustainable banking sector. The proposed framework attempts to synthesise the multiple aspects in the literature into a single framework which will be the basis of investigation in the analysis section which follows.

The framework studies how the Financial Crisis affected the financial and non-financial performances Retail Banks in UK and how a **regulated sales-led culture** (amalgamation of pre- and post-crisis culture) could bring greater profitability and stability in the banking sector. The new proposed culture is a

hybrid where both customer needs and shareholder needs are kept in perspective and a regulatory body (gap) can oversee and provide feedbacks for a safer and reliable banking sector.

FIGURE 3: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

SOURCE: (AUTHOR, 2021)

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to discuss the methodology used in this study and to provide a rationale for using a relevant case study approach based on the research aim and objectives. The author will use process “onion” (Saunders, 2003) to discuss research design, research philosophy and data collection methods in this study.

4.2 Research Onion

In this study, the author will use (Saunders, 2003) research ‘onion’ to justify the research methods used. The research process ‘onion’ provides clear steps to follow in order to develop the research process of this study. Its usefulness lies in its adaptability for almost any type of research methodology and can be used in a variety of contexts (Bryman, 2012). (Saunders, 2003) noted that while using research onion one must go from the outer layer to the inner layer. When viewed from the outside, each layer of the onion describes a more detailed stage of the research process (Saunders, 2003). (Saunders, 2003) sees research process as unwrapping of an onion layer by layer, for the inner layer to be seen the outer layer must be unwrapped first. For a goal to be achieved the right steps must be taken accordingly, this applies in research, cover one step first before proceeding to another. The layers of research onion are as follows:

- Research Philosophy
- Research Approach
- Research Methodology
- Time Horizons

➤ Data Collection Methods

The relevant research philosophy, research approach, research methodology, time horizons and data collection methods used are highlighted in the Figure below.

FIGURE 4: RESEARCH ONION

Source: (Saunders, 2003)

4.3 Research Philosophy

(SAUNDERS, 2003) IDENTIFIED FOUR RESEARCH PHILOSOPHIES:

- Positivism
- Realism
- Interpretivism

➤ **Pragmatism**

➤ **Positivism**

Positivism comes up with the research questions and hypothesis that we can test. (Fisher, 2003) defines positivism as having accurate and value-free knowledge regarding what is possible. Positivism relies on quantitative methods to conduct research. It aims to measure key concepts and test hypothesis on relationship between two or more concepts asserted in the theory (Curran, 2001).

➤ **Interpretivism**

Interpretivism helps in interpreting how people participate in the social and cultural life. (Neuman, 2000) defines interpretivism as detailed observation of people in a natural setting in order to interpret how people create and maintain their social worlds. Interpretivism holds a contrasting view than positivism as they believe that the world is subjective. Interpretivism argues that it is difficult to generalize a situation or matter. Interpretivism relies on qualitative methods to conduct research.

➤ **Realism**

Realism is based on a belief that a reality exist which is independent of human thoughts and beliefs (Saunders, 2003). Realism and Positivism are quite similar, however realism believes that we need to do continuous research without hesitating to use new methods to find reality. It relies on a unity of scientific methods to conduct research.

➤ **Pragmatism**

Pragmatism is an approach that evaluates theories or beliefs in terms of the success of their practical application. It can rely on both qualitative and/or quantitative methods to conduct research. Pragmatism is an amalgamation of both positivism and interpretivism approaches and can be used within the scope of a single research.

The author believes that Pragmatism will be a significant philosophy for this research. The author aims to develop a regulated sales-led culture for a stronger and sustainable banking sector and that requires an in-depth analysis of the ‘pre- and post-financial crisis’ banking culture whilst analysing their financial performances during that eras. The literature has various studies choosing either positivism or interpretivism philosophy and that according to the author is a gap. A sound financial system cannot be built unless what is wrong with the existing practise is not identified, so it’s significant to support inductive approach with deductive thinking to provide a balanced perspective.

4.4 Research Approach

In order to conduct a research, there are two reasoning methods widely used:

- The deductive approach,
- The inductive approach, and
- The Abductive Reasoning approach.

➤ **The Deductive Approach**

(Trochim, 2006) the deductive approach starts from a researchers’ theory of interest which is then tested with hypotheses that emerged from that theory.

This is then tested with observation and data which either upholds or reject the original theory.

Figure 5: The Deductive Approach

Source: (Trochim, 2006)

➤ **The Inductive Approach**

(Trochim, 2006) the inductive approach begins by the collection of data and observation which is relevant to his or her topic of interest. The researcher then find a pattern or regularity in his data which could develop a theory. So, the inductive approach works opposite to deductive approach which moves from data to theory.

FIGURE 6: THE INDUCTIVE APPROACH

SOURCE: (TROCHIM, 2006)

Since most of the studies in the literature either used Inductive Reasoning or Deductive Reasoning in their research, there is a gap in literature and an Abductive Reasoning Approach could therefore fill this gap.

The author is taking **Abductive Reasoning** approach for this research because there is possibly more than one explanation of the highlighted phenomenon (aggressive sales-led culture) and the author wishes to observe and test all the explanations if they are true in order to generate the best strategy for a safer, reliable and sustainable banking sector.

FIGURE 7: ABDUCTIVE REASONING APPROACH

SOURCE: (TROCHIM, 2006)

4.5 Research Methodology

In order to choose research methodology (Trauth, 2001), argues that research problem should be the main factor. This means that if a researcher wants to

study his/her area of interest, they should first determine how to learn it. (Trauth, 2001) further states that what the researcher aims to study will determine the research question and objectives and the questions posed will depend on the stage of knowledge accrual regarding the highlighted phenomenon.

There are a number of research methods available:

- Experiment
- Survey
- Case Study
- Grounded Theory
- Action Research
- Ethnography

• **Survey** is the method of gathering data from respondents thought to be representative of a specific portion of the population, using an instrument composed of closed structure or open-ended questions (Garson, 2001). (Kraemer, 1991) asserts survey research has three distinctive characteristics: first, survey research is used in quantitative research, requiring standardised information about the subject being studied. Second, the main way of collecting information is by asking people structured and predefined questions. Third, information is only collected for a fraction of the population, but it is possible to make generalisations. Usually, the sample is large enough to do extensive statistical analysis.

- **Grounded theory:** grounded theory is an inductive, theory discovery methodology that allows the researcher to develop a theoretical account of the general features of a topic while simultaneously grounding the account in empirical observations or data (Martin and Turner, 1986).
- **Experiments** have a long tradition in psychology and education. They involve a hypothesis and selection of samples. These samples are to be tested using standardised procedures to hold all conditions constant except the independent variable. This standardisation ensures high internal validity is achieved in the test results (Morrison, 2010).
- **Action Research.** (Gilmore, 1986) argues action research aims to contribute both to the practical concerns of people in an immediate problematic situation and to further the goals of social science simultaneously. Thus, there is a dual commitment in action research to study a system and concurrently to collaborate with members of the system in changing it in what is together regarded as a desirable direction. Accomplishing this twin goal requires the active collaboration of researcher and client, and thus it stresses the importance of co-learning as a primary aspect of the research process.
- **Ethnography or ethnographic research** comes from the discipline of social and cultural anthropology where an ethnographer is required to spend a significant amount of time in the field (Myers, 1999).

One recent approach to ethnographic research which could prove useful in studying banking culture is 'in-house ethnography'. Instead of having a trained ethnographer come into an organization and learn the culture from scratch, people who are already embedded within a culture are trained in ethnographic

methods so they can record their own culture. This approach has some significant benefits – it overcomes access problems and means the researcher is already seen as an insider. However, it possesses a significant challenge – often the in-house ethnographer finds it difficult to get significant distance from their own organization to begin to see its unique and strange characteristics. To achieve this, they need to be provided with some basic training in concepts of culture and ethnographic methods. They also typically need ongoing support and supervision which ensures they are able to effectively ask questions and gain some degree of perspective on their own organization. This can be facilitated by working alongside other in-house ethnographers in other similar organisations.

While there are many other quantitative tools for studying culture, they will often only give you a ‘thin’ understanding of culture within an organization. To develop a ‘thick’ and more in-depth understanding of a culture, qualitative research methods are needed. All the best studies of organizational cultures have involved some use of ethnographic methods. These involve periods of extended participant observation whereby a researcher spends time observing and to some extent participating in the daily life of the organization. This will allow the research to get beyond the attitudes of employees and espoused values of senior managers. Instead they will be able to identify the artefacts that are important to organizational members, what the range of espoused values are within an organisation, and most importantly what the underlying assumptions are within an organization. Undertaking an ethnographic study involves an extended period of observation which is recorded in field notes and then written up into an ethnographic account. Ethnographic research is time intensive, but can yield insightful in-depth accounts of a particular culture.

The author believes ethnographic research will be the ideal methodology for this study. However, this is time-intensive and due to the complexity of the highlighted phenomenon a **Case Study Methodology** would be ideal.

Case study is an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident. It is suitable for studying complex social phenomena (Yin, 2002). (Hartley, 1994) explains that case study research consists of a detailed investigation, often with data collected over a period of time, from one or more organisations, or groups within organisations, with a view to providing an analysis of the context and processes involved in the phenomenon being studied. Case study is a method of learning about a complex instance through extensive description and contextual analysis. It has been widely used as an essential research method in social sciences and management (Chetty 1996). It is considered more appropriate when dealing with the complexity of business and management research issues at master's and doctoral level. Case study typically examines the interplay among variables to provide comprehensive understanding through a thick description process which describes, in depth, the entity, circumstances and characteristics being evaluated. Case study can transcend the local boundaries of the investigated cases; capture new layers of reality and result in developing novel, testable and empirical (Zonabend, 1992) states case study research is done by giving special attention to complexities in observation, reconstruction, and analysis of the cases under study and is done in such a way that it incorporates the views of the actors in the case under study. Case study methods are considered appropriate for studying ongoing processes in business and financial institutions. Many research papers on business management and organisation behaviour have adopted case study as their main methodology (Eisenhart, 1989; Pettigrew and Whipp, 1993). (Proenca and Castro, 2005) study the interaction process, short-

term behaviours and motives in long-term relationships between banks and their corporate clients by collecting data from four Portuguese case studies. (Barroso, 2012) conduct an exploratory analysis of 37 Spain's savings banks to study corporate social responsibility. (Condosta, 2012) uses multiple case studies to identify how Italian banks are supporting local economies facing the current financial crisis. (Yin, 2009) identifies that a case study design should be considered when:

- 1) The type of the research question is typically to answer questions like “how” or “why” or an exploratory “what” question;
- 2) The researcher has little/no possibility of controlling events; and
- 3) The aim is to study contemporary phenomenon in a real-life context.

(Maxwell, 2005) argues that the goal of understanding a phenomenon from the point of view of the participants and its particular social and institutional context is largely lost when textual data is quantified. A very important advantage of the case material lies in the richness of its detailed understanding of the reality. Case study is not intended to study the whole organisation. Instead it focuses on a particular issue, feature or unit of analysis. (Patton, 1987) also argues case study becomes particularly useful where one needs to understand some particular problem or situation in great depth, and where one can identify cases rich in information. Case study can generate significant empirical insights into the culture of UK Retail Banks.

4.6 Research Nature and Design

(Creswell, 2007), defines research design as procedures for collecting, analysing, interpreting, and reporting data in research studies.

This study will adopt a **Mixed Method Approach** for understanding and analysing the highlighted phenomenon. The conceptual framework for this study is constructed keeping both financial and non-financial perspective in mind and a combination of both qualitative and quantitative method will fill the gap literature has and attempt to understand the effect of **proposed regulated sales-led culture** on both financial and non-financial performance of studied UK retail banks.

To answer the first objective, an in-house ethnographic research methodology would be ideal as it will help the author to have a better understanding of the problem with UK Retail Banks. Since a lot of studies have been conducted to understand the old and existing culture of banks, the author wishes to explore the topic with varying levels of depth, which will form the basis of future conclusive research. This research will be carried out in the UK Retail Banks (Barclays, HSBC, Lloyds and RBS). The author initially wanted to interview senior managers, middle managers and sales-floor employees to get an essence of culture. The interviews will consist of open-ended questions and then using Delphi technique the author aimed to come up with a strategy for the banks, regulators and policy makers to reach a consensus and work together.

However, due to the pandemic this was not possible. The author did manage to get some interviews over Skype but this did not meet the criteria for Ethnographic Research Methodology.

This was also not possible because the UK banking system is still reeling from the effects of the Financial Crisis. Banks' profitability is still below what it was at 2007 and the revelations about bad practices even after the crisis continue. The banks are still going through criminal investigations which has made banks understandably resilient to speak with outsiders.

Due to these reasons, the author had to refocus his research and decided to use a combination of his original bank interview approach, public statements, third-party interviews, and published reports understanding the banks' culture (like Salz Review and the Lambert Report) to arrive at 5 case studies presented in the next chapter.

The author is extremely grateful to all the interviewees who agreed to speak and helped him in understanding the highlighted phenomenon. The interviews gave many good ideas for positive cultural change which will be highlighted in the recommendations.

4.6.1 Multiple Sources of Data

➤ **Primary Data collection process**

The scope of this research depends primarily on the cooperation of banks that participated in this study. It is worth noting that it had been difficult to secure interviews with staff working at the retail division of banks.

Initially, the author sent out an email to the relevant banks alongside introductory letters for interviews. After 2 months of sending out emails to HSBC, Barclays, RBS and Lloyds and 3 out of 22 respondents replying in affirmative, the author decided to commence their data collection.

The author even contacted their colleagues from the previous university who are working in HSBC and Lloyds respectively to help with the information required after getting confirmation from their managers.

The author realised that it was not possible to secure face-face interviews and/or do an ethnographic research with senior bankers because of the following reasons:

- The nature of survey,
- The seniority of bankers,

- The sensitivity of the crisis, and
- The worldwide pandemic.

This study aims to investigate the triggers of the Financial Crisis and wanted to understand the sales-led culture the banks were operating in, thus the questions in interview are viewed as sensitive information by the respondents. This made the author understand banks' reluctance to participate in this topic.

The author started conducting interviews through his personal contacts and his contacts with the local branches of the said bank to secure interviews. They introduced 2 more managers who they have worked with earlier in their career. Some interviews were conducted with the author's colleagues and their co-workers. Eventually the author managed to secure 12 Front-line colleagues, 4 middle-line managers and 1 senior manager's interview.

All the interviews were conducted in London between 2020 and 2021 under Chatham House rules. The author is free to use any information from the interview for this research purpose however maintaining the anonymity of the interviewees, their role, and the banks they work for.

During the interviews, a questionnaire was used as a framework to ensure the highlighted phenomenon is covered and consistent across all the stated banks.

The research questionnaire was presented to the interviewees prior to the interviews, giving them a choice to decide if they want to participate and be more prepared for the interviews. It was at this point that one out of two senior bankers opted out and hence only one was interviewed.

The interview started with the author seeking permission from the interviewees to record the interviews for their subsequent analysis thereby increasing the validity of the study. The author then briefly introduced the purpose of study and assuring all the respondents of their anonymity. The author made it clear that all information will be treated as confidential and will only be used for this

research purpose. Each interview lasted from 40-60 mins and the abstracts of interviews were reviewed by respondents to ensure they were correct. This formed a basis for in-depth analysis in the next chapter.

- **Secondary Data Collection process**

(Yin, 2009) emphasised that one of the advantages of case study data collection is that we can use multiple sources of data which exceeds any other research methods like experiments or surveys etc. Therefore, in addition to the primary source of data we will use secondary data as well.

The secondary data used includes:

- Interviewed Banks' official websites
- Interviewed banks' annual reports
- Journal articles and research reports from professional bodies
- Newspapers (Financial Times, Economist)

A list of reports used are included in references.

This multiple way of data collection enhances the reliability and validity of this study.

To answer the second and third objectives, an explanatory (causal research) design would be used to understand the effect of one thing on another or according to (Dooley, 2007), this is used to understand the effect of one variable on another. A causal-comparative research identifies a causative relationship between a dependent and independent variable (Kumar, 2009). Therefore, a causal research design is chosen as it helps to generalize the findings of a larger population (in this case the UK retail banks).

The cause is the independent variable (why something happens), and the effect is the dependent variable (what happens as a result). Product diversification means banks relying on more than one income stream for greater profitability.

As established earlier, due to shareholders demands for higher short-term returns and due to excessive competition from the financial intermediaries who were tremendously profitable, UK banks decided to switch to the Universal Banking Model in order to be financially stable. Banks adopted an aggressive sales-led culture which initiated product diversification and thus led to increased profitability. Therefore, it can be established that any change in profitability is the (effect) of product diversification (cause) and not the other way round. This design would be an appropriate measure to investigate the effects of product diversification on the financial performance of UK Retail Banks.

Herfindahl - Hirschman Index, Correlations and Regression (using SPSS programme at 95% and 99% significance) will be used to answer these objectives. Product diversification will be analysed using Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI). This study adopts an Adjusted HHI approach (Acharya V. H.), as shown;

$$HHI=1-\left\{\left(\frac{NII}{NOI}\right)^2+\left(\frac{NONII}{NOI}\right)^2\right\}$$

Where:

HHI = level of product diversification,

NII = Net Interest Income,

NONII = Non-Interest Income,

NOI=Net Operating Income, and

1 is a unit.

The sum of squared interest and non-interest income is deducted from 1 so that product diversification level increases with the level of diversification which takes on values between $0 < HHI < 0.75$. Product diversification is indicated by HHI.

HHI is adopted because it is a measure of the size of the firms in relation to the industry they are in and an indicator of the amount of competition among them. The author also used it because of its simple calculation method and the small amount of data that is easily accessible. HHI is a simple and efficient way of finding out how diversified the banks are with easily accessible and reliable information. This index is mainly used in competition law just like a diversity index is used in ecology.

Regression model is a statistical method used to estimate the relationship between dependent and independent variable. Beyond that it helps to understand how much of the total variability in the data is explained by the model using statistical measurements like R-squared. It helps in determining which predictors in the model are significant alongside giving confidence intervals for each coefficient it estimates.

It is a simpler and time effective model which makes the interpreting of results much simpler whilst helping to evaluate all the required information needed for analysis.

The regression model to be used is as follows:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

y = financial performance indicator (dependent variable);

β_0 = y-intercept;

X_1 = production diversification level (HHI) as an independent variable;

β_1 = coefficients; and

ε = error term.

The financial performance measures to be used for regression are ROTA, ROE, NOI and EBIT.

1. **Return On Assets**= $\beta_0+\beta_1(\text{HHI})+\varepsilon$
2. **Return On Equity**= $\beta_0+\beta_1(\text{HHI})+\varepsilon$
3. **Net Operating Income**= $\beta_0+\beta_1(\text{HHI})+\varepsilon$
4. **Earnings Before Interest and Tax**= $\beta_0+\beta_1(\text{HHI})+\varepsilon$

The F-value is used to test for significance.

The incomes banks earn are heterogeneous as it is a mix of income from traditional activities (NII) and from fee-based activities (NONII). This means that both related and non-related activities provide a different level of diversification (HHI), so for this purpose constructing a HHI for NII and NONII would be preferable.

$$\text{HHI (NII)} = 1 - \left\{ \left(\frac{L}{\text{NII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\text{GOVT}}{\text{NII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\text{OII}}{\text{NII}} \right)^2 \right\}$$

Where;

L= Loans and advances;

GOVT= Government securities

OII= other interest income

and

$$\text{HHI (NONII)} = 1 - \left\{ \left(\frac{FL}{\text{NONII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{OF}{\text{NONII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\text{ONONII}}{\text{NONII}} \right)^2 \right\}$$

Where;

FL= fees on loans and advances

OF=other fees

ONONII= other non- interest income.

4.7 Conclusion

This chapter discusses the research methodology used in this study. The onion process identified the following design process:

- Research Philosophy: **Pragmatism**
- Research Approach: **Abductive Reasoning**
- Research Methodology: **Case – Study**
- Data Collection Methods: **open-ended question interviews and secondary sources.**

5.DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

Banks traditionally were sighted as financial institutions' which take deposits from customers and/or make loans to them. However, during 1980s UK banks switched to a universal banking model in order to sustain their positions as financial intermediaries. This shift from traditional banking model was important in order to be financially stable. (Hoggarth,1998), analysis sheds light on this where it was observed that German Banks (who were still traditional in their banking ways) were less profitable than banks in Britain and also less variable.

Diversification, in its literal sense means a bank entering into an activity (fee-based), other than its traditional means of earning (loans and deposit-taking) to generate income. Common wisdom holds that diversification would bring bank increased revenue and reduced risk, but does it? This reduced risk and increased revenue/profit is a result of the positive relationship between the different activities or business lines. So, when banks diversify across other lines of business; there is still a degree of expertise present. This means that

when banks diversify, they actually use their current resources to expand into other activities. So when banks diversify they get a competitive advantage through economies of scale and by using banks current expertise and abilities across non-identical or dissimilar product lines. The assumption that diversification brings increased revenue is probably more attainable when banks expand into homogenous lines of business.

As the banks reached out past the generally straightforward plan of action of the past, retail sector faced increased burden from shareholders for increased returns. As a response to this challenge, banks created an ‘aggressive sales’ culture. Banks started to forcefully promote new financial products to clients which in turn lead to "tellers" inside bank offices beginning to consider themselves to be “sellers”. This shift without a doubt brought expanded benefits, more scope of commodities and increased access to borrowings. Nonetheless, this accompanied a cost. Banks became adamant of the risks in lending. They planned low quality products and promoted them to clients independent of its suitability. It wasn’t until 2007 that banks begin to evidence the implications of this aggressive sales culture. The collapse and near-miss of some of the major banks (through public bailouts), the miss-selling of Payment protection insurance (PPI) and billions set aside in compensation and fines for wrong-practises shook the public’s confidence in banking system and by 2012 brought the British Retail Banks in crisis.

One of the major reasons for the failure of the UK Banking System is the adoption of a ‘sales’ culture. This is a set of embedded organisational norm and practises where short term goals are preferred over long terms i.e. encouraging employees to focus on making short term sales at the expense of longer term customer satisfaction (providing them with the products they actually need within the bounds of integrity and ethics).

Originated in 1980s as an ‘embedded’ culture to UK Retail Banks, senior executives were of view that front line colleagues were not sales driven and hence not selling the financial products that banks offered. So the idea was to promote these products to customers in every transaction. Banks even went on to change the way their branches looked; newer branches were designed to make a conversation between a staff and customer more natural. Questions like ‘would you like something else’ came in and introducing clients to new banking products e.g. loans, credit cards and services like PPI. Banks started to use ‘incentives’ as a positive reinforcement to boost sales. Performances became public through whiteboards, where staff with leading sales was rewarded while laggards were punished. Retail Bank went on to declare their commitment to building a sales-led culture. The underlying assumption was that this sales-oriented culture would lead them to operate and sustain in an increasingly aggressive market, whilst maximising profits and increasing returns to shareholders.

5.2 Retail Banks in UK

The UK banking market constitutes 157 banks based in UK, 177 banks based overseas and 46 building societies. Most of these institutions are very small and account for less than 1% of the UK Retail Banking Market.

Leading banks in the United Kingdom (UK) in 2019, by total assets (in billion GBP)

Leading UK banks 2019, by total assets

FIGURE 8: LEADING BANKS IN UK

5.3 Market Share

Retail Banking in the UK is highly concentrated. As shown in the table below that the top 5 banks (Lloyds, Barclays, RBS, HSBC and Santander) accounts for 85% of the current accounts in the UK. The remaining market is made up of Nationwide, TSB and Co-operative Bank accounting for 12% of the UK Retail Banking Market. There are some new challenger banks in the market like Metro Bank which accounts for 0.24% of the market and is slowly and gradually establishing its mark in the domestic Retail Market.

As evident, although the market is made up of many players; the top 5 banks bring most of the business to the market. Since, these banks have dominated the current account market for years, the Current Account Switch Guarantee was introduced in 2013 by the Government to make it simpler for consumers to switch current accounts and also to increase the competition between the banks. There have been 6 million current accounts switches since the service was introduced in 2013.

For years, the Retail Market had been lacking the competition and the Current Account Switch Guarantee was introduced to provide a simple, reliable and stress-free way to make the switch. This ensured that consumers have multiple choices and the banks to do their best to retain old customers while creating incentives to attract new ones.

Market share of current accounts of leading United Kingdom (UK) banks in 2019

Account market share of leading UK banks in 2019

2 **Note(s):** United Kingdom: 2019
 Further information regarding this statistic can be found [page 8](#)
Source(s): New City Agenda ID: 387098

statista

FIGURE 9: MARKET SHARE OF CURRENT ACCOUNTS

Following the crisis, the UK Retail Banks have started working towards a sound and stable financial system. An analysis of tier one capital ratios by the Bank of England and the Prudential Regulatory Authority found that all the major UK banks now have improved their balance sheet and now exceed requirements by having 3% of end-point tier one capital, and 7% of common tier one capital. This was increased in 2019 by the Bank of England where all systemically important banks were required to hold up to 4.05% tier one capital, with an additional buffer of 0.9% during upswings in the economic cycle. However, there continues to be debate about whether 7% is an appropriate level of tier one capital or even whether risk-weighted capital requirements give a realistic assessment of a bank's solvency. Some commentators argue that the amount of tier one capital needs to be much higher – some suggesting up to 25%. Along with increasingly healthy balance sheets, UK banks have reasonably healthy credit ratings which indicate they are investment grade assets. Only the Co-op Bank has a rating below the investment grade level. This indicates that following the significant uncertainties of the financial crises, UK banks are better capitalised, have higher credit ratings and are by implication increasingly safe from a prudential stand-point. Finally, UK banks appear to be increasingly safe in the face of extreme circumstances. Two annual stress tests by the European Central Bank found that the four major UK banks appear to have sufficient capital to weather adverse economic conditions.

5.4 Increasing Complaints

Although from a prudential stand-point most banks have shown improvement, there have not been similar progress in terms of customer complaints. The number of complaints increased exponentially between 2010 and 2014 where the maximum complaint received for financial services was 512,167 in the year 2013/14. The complaints did go down in the years following 2014

however it has still not reached the pre-crisis era which was 123,089 and 127,471 complaints in 2008/09 and 2009/10 respectively.

Financial Ombudsman: financial services new complaints in the UK 2011-2020

Number of complaints regarding financial services received by the Financial Ombudsman in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2010/11 to 2019/20

2010/11	206,121
2011/12	264,375
2012/13	508,881
2013/14	512,167
2014/15	329,509
2015/16	340,899
2016/17	321,283
2017/18	339,967
2018/19	388,392
2019/20	273,026

TABLE 2: FINANCIAL OMBUDSMAN: FINANCIAL SERVICES NEW COMPLAINTS IN THE UK 2011-2020

Number of complaints regarding financial services received by the Financial Ombudsman in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2010/11 to 2019/20

Financial Ombudsman: financial services new complaints in the UK 2011 -2020

FIGURE 10: NUMBER OF COMPLAINTS REGARDING FINANCIAL SERVICES 2010/11 TO 2019/20

In the first half of 2020, it is evident that the most complaints opened were for 4 of the top 5 banks HSBC, Barclays, Santander and Natwest almost amounting to 53% of the total complaints received. The total complaints received were 829,870 out of which 83% is related to advising, selling, and arranging of protection services.

Despite a rising number of complaints to Financial Ombudsman Services, it is evident that most of the banks have been increasingly efficient in resolving the queries. It is noteworthy that an increase in complaints to Financial Ombudsman Services does not necessarily mean that there is a deterioration in the quality of services provided by banks. Up until 2015 almost 66% of the complaints were associated to past misconducts like PPI which have been resolved. In the first half of 2020 almost 83% of the complaints were related to inquiry about protection services while the remaining complaints were mostly associated to general administration complaints and information regarding charges on product performance.

The increasing complaints may be a result of lack in trust but most of the interviewers were reported saying ... *“an increase in complain is not proportional to poor conduct”* and *“...consumers are now more aware of their ability to complain due to the increase in adverts and ongoing promotions by claims management companies”*

However, it is evident that complaints are going down and it might go further down if banks continue to resolve queries the way they claim to be doing and improving their practises.

Customer complaints against banking services in the UK in H1 2020, by company		
Number of banking & credit cards services customer complaints in the United Kingdom (UK) in the first half of 2020, by company (in 1,000s)		
	Complaints opened	Complaints closed
HSBC UK Bank Plc	146.4	149.53
Barclays Bank UK PLC	125.27	129.47
Lloyds Bank PLC	97.63	89.55
National Westminster Bank Plc	92.34	92.26
Santander UK Plc	76.04	76.15
Bank of Scotland plc	63.89	61.11
Nationwide Building Society	46.06	46.51

TSB Bank plc	34.42	33.95
Clydesdale Bank Plc	30.24	30.61
Monzo Bank Ltd	24.96	24.44
Royal Bank of Scotland Plc, The	24.54	26.11
Capital One (Europe) plc	23.36	23.57
Marks & Spencer Financial Services Plc	16.39	16.66
Tesco Personal Finance PLC	15.22	15.22
Bank of Ireland (UK) Plc	13.11	13.12

TABLE 3: CUSTOMER COMPLAINTS AGAINST BANKING SERVICES IN THE UK IN H1 2020, BY COMPANY

5.5 Customer Satisfaction

As part of regulatory requirement an independent survey was conducted by Competition and Markets Authority (2019) to ask 860 customers of the personal current account providers and if they would recommend services to friends and family. The results represent the views of consumers who took part in the survey.

BANKS CURRENT
ACCOUNTS
(CUSTOMER
SCORE)

METRO BANK	82%
-------------------	-----

FIRST DIRECT	82%
NATIONWIDE	74%
BARCLAYS	66%
LLOYDS BANK	64%
HSBC	62%
SANTANDER	61%
NATWEST	61%
BANK OF SCOTLAND	59%
RBS	46%

TABLE 4: CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

SOURCE: COMPETITION AND MARKETS AUTHORITY

As seen in the table above, Metro Bank stands at the first place along with First Direct with 82% customer score. This was followed by Nationwide with a 74% customer score. It is noteworthy that the top 5 banks are further down on the League Table with RBS being at the bottom not even meeting the average score, scoring only 46%. The other 4 of top 5 banks hit above average scores but considerably lower than the banks on top in the league table. Barclays scored 66%, Lloyds scored 64% while HSBC and Santander just managed to get above average scored of 62% and 61% respectively.

The scores show that despite the claims of top 5 banks improving their customer service, their customer satisfaction is either below average (RBS) or barely above average (HSBC and Santander). What is interesting is that these scores go in line with the number of complaints received by Financial Ombudsman Services which goes on to show that the customers of top 5 UK Retail Banks are receiving either average or below average customer services. However, both the results go against the claims of interviewer who claimed that the increase in complaints could be a result of increased ads from claim companies. It is recommended to top 5 banks to take a deep look at Metro Bank, First Direct and Nationwide who are scoring high in their levels of customer services despite not holding major market share of UK Retail Banks.

5.6 Ethics in UK Retail Banking

Following the crisis of 2008, one of the major concerns that unearthed was the ethics in the banking system. A survey conducted in 2013 with 4,207 respondents regarding the ethical standards in British Banking found that 65% agreed that there is existence of ethical problems in the UK banking system, whereas 30% were unsure. Despite the claims by most banks to have developed better ethical standards, the public faith was not restored as the survey also found that 36% of the respondents disagree that banks were switching to more ethical culture and 52% of the respondents were unsure if that was actually happening.

When asked to the interviewees about their opinion on ethical standards in their respective banks, one interviewee responded “...*the atmosphere is too fast-paced. There is a race to meet targets which often results in mis-selling*”.

Another interviewee added “...*the pressure to meet targets has doubled. We did focus on customer needs for few years after the crisis but have reinstated to aggressive selling to meet the targets*” ...

However, another interviewee had a different response “...*following the crisis, the focus shifted to serving customer needs, sales targets were discarded and customers’ needs became priority...*”

Do you agree or disagree with the statement "There is a widespread problem of ethics in the British banking industry"?

Opinion on the existence of ethical problems in the UK banking system in March 2013

6 Note(s): United Kingdom; January 2013; 18 years and older; 4,207 respondents; UK adults
 Further information regarding this statistic can be found on [page 60](#)
 Source(s): YouGov; ID: 293776

Ethical banks and investments **statista**

FIGURE 11: PROBLEM OF ETHICS?

Do you agree or disagree with the statement "UK banks are changing and becoming more ethical"?

UK survey: Opinion on banking sector ethics in March 2013

7 Note(s): United Kingdom; January 2013; 18 years and older; 4,207 respondents; UK adults
 Further information regarding this statistic can be found on [page 61](#)
 Source(s): YouGov; ID: 293800

Ethical banks and investments **statista**

FIGURE 12: ETHICAL BANKS: YES OR NO?

Though the responses from the interviewees were mixed, a survey by the Ethical Consumer Magazine (2013) opposed the claims of UK bank being ethical. Their scorecard ranked banks based on honesty, customer service and ethical standards. The top 5 banks were at the bottom of the league table whereas challenger banks like Metro Bank and Nationwide topped the league table with exceptional scores of 77 and 76. Despite the top 5 banks claims to be ethical, they were in the lower quartile of the league table meaning majority of the public was receiving below average customer service as well as unethical despite having a majority 85% market share of UK Retail Banking.

The results raise serious concerns about the efficiency of the British Banking system as 85% of the banking operates on unethical culture and provides below average customer services to most of the population. The top 5 banks will benefit well if they learn from challenger banks like Metro Bank and Nationwide.

5.7 Aggressive Sales pressure: increasing or decreasing?

One of the major causes that unearthed following the 2008 crisis was an aggressive sales-led culture. Though the banks claim to have work on resolving the issue, there have been various studies suggesting that little may have changed following the crisis. A study was conducted in 2012 by Which? that mirrored the results of 2011 study by FSA (increased mis-selling to meet targets). The major finding of Which? was that *“selling is inherent to the job and pressure to sell is a fundamental part of banks’ culture.”*

Despite the banks’ claim to have cleaned up following the crisis, Which?’s survey with frontline staff from top 5 banks unearthed that 40% of the bank

staff have had a personal sales target to meet whereas 60% reported to have financial incentive once the targets were met. Though setting targets is not an issue but 65% of the respondents reported increased pressures from managers to meet their targets. 75% of the staff reported day to day bickering from managers to meet targets and 50% of the staff reported that even though the targets were met, they were forced to sell more. 42% of the staff reported that following the crisis, financial incentives were reduced to show that the banks' have shifted their focus to customer needs, where in reality the sales targets still existed but with lower or no incentives than the prior years.

The results are interesting as they mirror the author's interviewees' responses. Few front-line interviewees reported:

6. *"...we had daily targets to meet and were publicly shamed to have not met them".*
7. *"...once I was heavily incentivised to mis-sell PPIs and home insurances..."*
8. *"...daily target meeting was a norm at start of the day and the day usually ended with shame walk, with name-calling and trash thrown on if the targets weren't met".*
9. *"...the atmosphere was hellish, we had to sacrifice our morals to keep our jobs..."*
10. *"...a few of us were told to cater customer needs and weren't paid incentives while our peers were being paid to sell, **sell their morals!!**"*

The study by Which? compared the results of widespread selling in top 5 UK Retail Banks. This is shown in the table below:

	Lloyds	RBS	HSBC	Barclays	Santander

Pressure of selling by culture	56%	35%	41%	33%	29%
Pressure of selling by manager	46%	31%	33%	30%	25%
Sales target drive to sell against will	45%	43%	35%	39%	23%
Colleagues mis-sold to meet targets	47%	51%	53%	37%	31%
Uncomfortable with bank's approach to sales	37%	32%	33%	27%	14%
Focus on sales over customer service.	39%	28%	32%	20%	18%

TABLE 5: WHICH? SURVEY

The 2012 study found that the top 5 banks were still operating in an “aggressive sales-led” culture. Some of the key findings were:

- 56% of Lloyds staff reported to be **pressured to sell because of culture**, where RBS reported 35%, HSBC 41%, Barclays 33% and Santander 29%.

- The **pressure to sell by manager** still existed in Lloyds 46%, RBS 31%, HSBC 33%, Barclays 30% and Santander 25%.
- Employees were **pressured to sell against will** in Lloyds 45%, RBS 43%, HSBC 39%, Barclays 35% and Santander 23%.
- **Employees were uncomfortable with bank's practices** in Lloyds 37%, RBS 32%, HSBC 33%, Barclays 27%, and Santander 14%.

The study showed that the aggressive sales-led culture was engraved within the British Banking Industry and how despite the claims from top 5 banks to have reformed, the progress of change was not visible in the studied year and subsequently resulted in lack of public trust.

Following the increased pressure to sell, FCA issued guidance on financial incentive to sell in 2013 identifying the characteristics of poor practise. This included sales incentive based on sales volume, hard to manage incentive schemes, and a lack of punishment for poor quality sales. It even identified the incentive system to decrease the likelihood of mis-selling, rolling sales targets and balanced scorecard. However, a subsequent study in 2014 found that all banks have significantly changed their practices and the increased pressure to sell which existed earlier was dealt with performance management of staff.

This study opposed from the recent interviews conducted by the author who found that the pressure to sell and performance-based incentives still exists.

5.8 Employee Satisfaction

Although there are no standardized surveys within the UK Banking industry, yet how satisfied are employees can be found through various studies by Which? and interviews of various employees in many cultural change studies.

Which? studies showed that employees were pressured into selling against their morals and will where 37% of the respondents were not comfortable with the pressure to sell and 43% did not enjoy the challenge of selling. The study showed that more than 50% of the employees in top 5 banks were pressured to sell either by culture or their managers which shows immense displeasure with their jobs. This is explained by the absence of retail banks in Sunday Times top 100 companies to work for.

This mirrors with the author's interviewees who pointed out their discomfort in being pressured to sell and doing things against their morals.

5.9 Trust

According to Which? study, 80% of the respondents felt that things have worsen than the prior years and that bankers do not act in consumer's best interest. Since culture is left on the bankers to change, 62% of the consumers feel that the banks will be ineffective in bringing cultural change. 30% of the customers felt that banks put sales over services by offering unwanted products and services leading to a culture of mis-selling. 43% of the respondents were reported saying that there is a greater emphasis on selling rather than customer service every time they visit a branch.

Which? Investigation of 500 front-line staff of the Big Five Banks revealed that 46% of the staff sold products to meet their targets and 40% sold irrespective of the customers' needs. The investigation further found the effect of this culture on customers, where 40% reported to have been offered a product that was not suitable and 25% of them felt pressurised to take it. These evidences were further validated by the studies that followed. (Lui A. , 'Greed, Recklessness, Dishonesty: and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK

banks between 2004 and 2009', 2015), confirmed the banks' shift to sales-led culture and the rashness in this culture during the studied period 2004-09.

Following the crisis, a period of learning and rectifying began but the manipulation of LIBOR scandal in 2012 baffled the public as despite the crisis, banks continued their unethical and immoral practises. Ever since the crisis, retail division had to pay £38.5bn in fines and these unethical practises got the complaints to Financial Ombudsman Services to as high as 400,000 post the crisis. This suggests the public continue to distrust banks and if the banks want to rebuild this trust, a mixture of government regulation, greater transparency about products and changes to internal processes are needed.

5.10 Effect of Product Diversification on the Financial Performance of UK Retail Banks

With diversification, banks intend to increase their credit portfolio and hence reduce their credit portfolio risk. One such important study was performed by (Acharya V. H., 2002) . They analysed 105 Italian Banks to study the effects of focus (only relying on loan portfolio) against diversification and concluded that diversification does not provide any greater safety for banks and nor does it guarantee to produce any superior performance to that of focused banks. However, the answer depends on the risk-taking behaviour of a bank. For banks who take on higher risks, diversification accompanies reduced bank returns and increased volatility. While, for the banks who take on low risk, diversification does produce a marginal improvement. (Evelyn Hayden, 2005-2006) , results too oppose the traditional theory that banks should be as diversified as possible meaning focusing increases bank's profitability. Diversification tends to lower returns for banks in Germany and the impact of any diversification on bank's returns depends on the risk levels. Statistically

positive relation between diversification and increasing bank's returns was only found in the case of medium risk levels and industrial diversification. (Kamp, 2004) , studied period saw increasing diversification is mainly driven by a large number of German saving banks and corporate banks. Big banks on average neither diversified nor focused while regional and subsidiaries of foreign banks chose to focus on their loan portfolios. (David, 2005), analysed the loan portfolios of banks in Sweden and investigated the strategy behind loan portfolio diversification of banks. (Schertler, 2006), found that the growth of domestic lending depends on the characteristics of banks. Lending by smaller banks, savings banks and cooperatives including their regional institutions reacts positively to domestic sectoral growth, while lending by regional and big banks do not.

(Busch, 2009) , examined the German banks and its income diversification. It was found that banks with a more diversified income base exhibit a more favourable risk-return profile meaning higher risk adjusted ROTA and ROE (return on asset and return on equity respectively), whereas for commercial banks higher ROTA and ROE accompany higher risks(volatility). (Goetz, 2012), results indicate that a competitor's diversification is positively correlated to the non-diversified (focused) bank's risk taking behaviour. Also, a bank's risk taking behaviour increases when it itself diversifies across the markets. Hence, a focused bank can have indirect effects of diversification too, where a competitor's diversification can affect the non-diversified bank's risk taking behaviour. (Fang, 2011) , concluded that a bank's performance has a positive relationship with asset diversification and a negatively relationship with loan diversification.

To understand the effect of product diversification on the financial performance of UK Retail Banks, a causal research design would be used in order to understand the effect of one thing on another or according to (Dooley,

2007), this is used to understand the effect of one variable on another. A causal-comparative research identifies a causative relationship between a dependent and independent variable (Kumar, 2009). Therefore, a causal research design is chosen as it helps to generalize the findings of a larger population. This design would be an appropriate measure to investigate the effects of product diversification on the financial performance of UK Retail Banks. This thesis involves the top 5 registered UK Retail Banks.

The audited financial statements of these banks is mainly used for this study especially the balance sheets and the income statement. Balance sheets provided me with information regarding the change in total assets whereas Income statements provided information regarding changes in income (net and gross). These information are useful quantitative sources for evaluating historical, confidential and publicly available data.

5.10.1 Herfindahl- Hirschman Index

Banks	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Barclays	0.4	0.4	0.41	0.41	0.42	0.44	0.45	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.48	0.48
HSBC	0.35	0.36	0.37	0.37	0.36	0.38	0.38	0.4	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.42
Lloyds	0.47	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.49	0.5	0.5	0.51	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52
RBS	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.47	0.47	0.49	0.49	0.5	0.5	0.51	0.51
Santander	0.44	0.49	0.49	0.5	0.5	0.52	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.54	0.54	0.55

	Ba nks	200 8	200 9	201 0	201 1	201 2	201 3	201 4	201 5	201 6	201 7	201 8	201 9
N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Mean		0.42 40	0.43 80	0.44 20	0.44 60	0.44 80	0.46 20	0.47 00	0.48 00	0.48 60	0.48 80	0.49 20	0.49 60
Std. Devi ation		0.04 930	0.05 586	0.05 070	0.05 505	0.05 805	0.05 495	0.05 788	0.05 000	0.04 827	0.05 070	0.05 070	0.04 930

TABLE 6: HERFINDAHL- HIRSCHMAN INDEX

The mean diversification level of the UK Retail Banks over the studied period is shown. It can be seen that on average the studied banks are moderately diversified i.e. $0.25 < HHI < 0.75$.

Most of the banks on individual level are seen to be moderately diversified as well over the studied period. On aggregate, retail banks in UK are moderately diversified and is increasing over the studied period.

<i>Year</i>	<i>No. of banks</i>	<i>Industry</i>	<i>Large</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Small</i>
2008	5	0.42	0.4	0.38	0.32
2009	5	0.44	0.41	0.36	0.38
2010	5	0.44	0.43	0.41	0.36
2011	5	0.45	0.43	0.40	0.37
2012	5	0.45	0.45	0.40	0.35
2013	5	0.48	0.48	0.41	0.35

2014	5	0.48	0.48	0.41	0.35
2015	5	0.48	0.48	0.42	0.38
2016	5	0.48	0.48	0.42	0.38
2017	5	0.49	0.49	0.43	0.38
2018	5	0.49	0.49	0.43	0.39
2019	5	0.50	0.50	0.43	0.39

TABLE 7: MEAN DIVERSIFICATION LEVEL (2008-2019)

The table 2.2 shows the mean diversification level of the industry, and the mean diversification level of the banks according to sizes: large, medium and small. This shows various levels of diversification with large commercial banks having HHI of 0.46, which is same as the industry's HHI level of 0.4667. Medium commercial banks have the HHI of 0.41 which is less than the industry average and the small commercial banks falls below the industry's HHI to 0.37. This implies that all commercial banks (large, medium and small) are moderately diversified on average ($0.25 < \text{HHI} < 0.75$). Large commercial banks appear to be more diversified on average than the medium and small commercial banks. It can be interpreted that large banks could take riskier projects and entertain economy of scale which medium and small banks cannot.

The regression model used is as follows:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

y = financial performance indicator (dependent variable);

β_0 = y-intercept;

X_1 =production diversification level (HHI) as an independent variable;

β_1 =coefficients; and

ε =error term.

The financial performance measures to be used in this regression are ROTA, ROE, NOI and EBIT.

5. $ROTA = \beta_0 + \beta_1(HHI) + \varepsilon$

6. $ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1(HHI) + \varepsilon$

7. $NOI = \beta_0 + \beta_1(HHI) + \varepsilon$

8. $EBIT = \beta_0 + \beta_1(HHI) + \varepsilon$

Where;

ROTA= Return on Total Assets;

ROE= Return on Equity;

NOI= Net Operating Income; and

EBIT= Earnings before income and tax.

The F-value is used to test for significance.

The incomes banks earn are heterogeneous as it is a mix of income from traditional activities (NII) and from fee-based activities (NONII). This means that both related and non-related activities provide a different level of diversification (HHI). This is shown in Table 3. We would now construct HHI for NII and NONII.

$$\text{HHI (NII)} = 1 - \left\{ \left(\frac{L}{\text{NII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\text{GOVT}}{\text{NII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\text{OII}}{\text{NII}} \right)^2 \right\}$$

Where;

L= Loans and advances;

GOVT= Government securities

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
HHI(NONII)	0.48	0.49	0.49	0.51	0.52	0.53	0.55	0.55	0.56	0.58	0.6	0.6
HHI(NII)	0.36	0.35	0.34	0.35	0.35	0.37	0.38	0.38	0.38	0.39	0.4	0.41
Average Profit	0.5	0.51	0.51	0.53	0.54	0.55	0.57	0.57	0.58	0.6	0.62	0.62

OII= other interest income

And

$$\text{HHI (NONII)} = 1 - \left\{ \left(\frac{FL}{\text{NONII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{OF}{\text{NONII}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\text{ONONII}}{\text{NONII}} \right)^2 \right\}$$

Where;

FL= fees on loans and advances

OF=other fees

ONONII= other non- interest income

TABLE 8: AVERAGE DIVERSIFICATION LEVEL AND PROFIT

FIGURE 13: AVERAGE LEVEL OF DIVERSIFICATION (2008-2019)

Figure 13 shows that average profits have increased during 2008 to 2019 (24%), at a steady rate. The year 2009-2010 saw no growth and then increases by 3.92% in 2011 and 1.9% in 2012. There was an increase of 1.85% in the year 2013 and 3.6% in 2014. The year 2015 saw no increase and then increased by 1.75% in 2016 and 1.16% in 2017 followed by a 3% increase in 2018. The year 2019 saw no growth.

HHI (NONII) too increases during the 12-year period 2008 and 2019 by 25%. HHI (NII) increases by 13.9% over the studied period. Out of the two income stream mixes, non-interest income is seen to be steadier and more stable. The growth in average profit is seen to be evidently associated with it. This is further confirmed by (Stiroh K. , 2004b), that diversification into non-interest based activities lead to increased banks' revenue and reduced risk.

The stability of profits of UK Retail Banks could be explained due to the stability of non-interest income diversification level over the studied period. In order to be financially stable, UK Retail Banks took this shift towards non-interest-based activities from their traditional means of generating income.

The growth of product diversification and its relationship with profits, NII, NONII and NOI for each year is shown in Table 4.

<i>£(bn)</i>	<i>2008</i>	<i>2009</i>	<i>2010</i>	<i>2011</i>	<i>2012</i>	<i>2013</i>	<i>2014</i>	<i>2015</i>	<i>2016</i>	<i>2017</i>	<i>2018</i>	<i>2019</i>
<i>NII</i>	40	61	70	98	102	105	107	105	106	107	107	108
<i>NONII</i>	56	62	77	100	123	128	129	126	128	128	130	131
<i>NOI</i>	96	123	147	198	225	233	236	231	234	235	237	239
<i>PROFITS</i>	35	55	80	102	106	106	108	109	110	111	111	114

TABLE 9:TRENDS OF PROFITS, NONII, NII AND NOI 2008-2019

FIGURE 14:NONII, NII, NOI AND PROFITS TRENDS (2008-2019).

As can be clearly seen from the graph, net interest income increases at an increasing rate over the 12-year period reaching its maximum of 108 bn in the year 2019. The NONII increases over the period and reaches its maximum at

£131bn in 2019. This growth in profits is associated with the UK banks' decision to diversify into non-interest-based activities, which out of the two income streams appears to be more steady and stable. This scenario goes in line with (Stiroh K. , 2004a), where diversification into non-interest based activities increases banks' profitability and reduces the volatility of banks' returns. This scenario is further supported by (DeYoung, 2001), findings that banks generate increased portions of their incomes from non-interest based activities.

It can be seen that non-interest income relies on interest income earning activities. It is also noticeable that the two income streams growth move in the same direction and can be affected by economic shocks. If the interest-based revenue stream respond to the same shock, then a high correlation between the two income mixes would be seen. The results show a high level of correlation between the two income mixes and therefore substituting or eliminating one is not possible. There exists a diversification benefit where a growth in one type of income is associated with similar growth in the other type of income. However, as the banks shift its focus more towards fee-based income, diversification benefits seem to diminish. This result is supported by (DeYoung, 2001), findings that interest and non-interest income should work alongside (high correlation) rather than replacing or substituting each other. It is now worthwhile to see the correlation between the studied variables.

5.10.2 CORRELATION ANALYSIS

The Table 5 shows the correlation between the studied variable at 95% and 99% significance level.

Correlations

		HHI	NON II	NII	NOI	EBIT	ROT A	ROE
HH I	Pearson Correlation	1	.203	.181	.524* *	.448*	.193	.305
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.160	.188	.003	.011	.172	.065
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
NO NII	Pearson Correlation	.203	1	.818* *	.551* *	.435*	.165	.247
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.160		.000	.002	.013	.210	.112
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
NII	Pearson Correlation	.181	.818* *	1	.607* *	.519* *	.086	.340*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.188	.000		.000	.003	.338	.044
	N	5	5	5	5	5 5	5	5
NO I	Pearson Correlation	.524* *	.551* *	.607* *	1	.773* *	.051	.308
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.003	.002	.000		.000	.402	.063
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
EB IT	Pearson Correlation	.448*	.435*	.519* *	.773* *	1	.015	.492* *
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.011	.013	.003	.000		.470	.005
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

RO TA	Pearson Correlation	.193	.165	.086	.051	.015	1	.374*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.172	.210	.338	.402	.470		.030
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
RO E	Pearson Correlation	.305	.247	.340*	.308	.492* *	.374*	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.065	.112	.044	.063	.005	.030	
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).								
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).								

TABLE 10: ZERO-ORDER CORRELATION OF STUDIED VARIABLES

It can be commented from the table above that Non Interest Income has a strong positive correlation with Net Interest Income at 99% significance level ($r=0.818$, $\text{sig}=0.000$). There is a positive correlation between NII and NOI at 99% significance level ($r=0.607$, $\text{sig}=0.000$). There is also a positive correlation between NONII and NOI at 99% significance level ($r=0.551$, $\text{sig}=0.002$). So it can be interpreted that the UK Retail Banks rely more on NII in order to reduce the operating expenses. NONII works in line with the NII and provides banks with greater financial stability, so it is worthwhile for banks to have these two income mixes work alongside rather than being substituted. All the variables in the table above correlates positively ($0 < r < 1$) and ($\text{sig} > 0$). Therefore, there is a positive relationship between the product diversification level (HHI) and the financial performance measures. It can be interpreted that a one unit increase in HHI results to a corresponding increase in ROTA, ROE, EBIT and NOI.

Correlations								
Control Variables			NOI	EBIT	ROTA	ROE	HHI	NII
NO NII	N OI	Correlation	1.000	.710	-.048	.213	.504	.327
		Significance (1-tailed)	.	.000	.409	.153	.005	.055
	E BI T	Correlation	.710	1.000	-.064	.441	.408	.314
		Significance (1-tailed)	.000	.	.381	.014	.022	.063
	R O T A	Correlation	-.048	-.064	1.000	.349	.165	-.087
		Significance (1-tailed)	.409	.381	.	.044	.215	.340
	R O E	Correlation	.213	.441	.349	1.000	.269	.249
		Significance (1-tailed)	.153	.014	.044	.	.097	.115
			Correlation	.504	.408	.165	.269	1.000

	H HI	Significance (1-tailed)	.005	.022	.215	.097	.	.449
	NI I	Correlation	.327	.314	-.087	.249	.027	1.000
		Significance (1-tailed)	.055	.063	.340	.115	.449	.

TABLE 11: PARTIAL CORRELATION WITH NONII CONTROLLED

Correlations								
Control Variables			NOI	EBIT	ROTA	ROE	HHI	NON II
NI I	NO I	Correlation	1.000	.675	-.001	.136	.530	.117
		Significance (1-tailed)	.	.000	.497	.259	.003	.288
	EB IT	Correlation	.675	1.000	-.034	.392	.421	.022
		Significance (1-tailed)	.000	.	.435	.026	.018	.458
RO TA	Correlation	-.001	-.034	1.000	.368	.181	.166	
	Significance (1-tailed)	.497	.435	.	.035	.193	.214	

RO E	Correlation	.136	.392	.368	1.000	.264	-.059	
	Significance (1-tailed)	.259	.026	.035	.	.102	.390	
HH I	Correlation	.530	.421	.181	.264	1.000	.097	
	Significance (1-tailed)	.003	.018	.193	.102	.	.322	
NO NII	Correlation	.117	.022	.166	-.059	.097	1.000	
	Significance (1-tailed)	.288	.458	.214	.390	.322	.	

TABLE 12: PARTIAL CORRELATION WITH NII CONTROLLED

Tables 11 and 12 show partial correlation coefficients, controlled for NONII and NII respectively. These are compared with the zero-order correlation to see how the results differ.

Table 11 shows that when NONII is controlled, EBIT would have a positive correlation with NII of 0.314, ROE will have a positive correlation of 0.249, but it will have a negative correlation with ROTA of -0.087.

Table 12 shows that when NII is controlled, NONII would be positively correlated with all performance measures EBIT, ROTA and ROE with $r=0.458$, 0.214 and 0.390 respectively.

It could therefore be interpreted that removing NONII would bring a lower ROTA meaning it will reduce the banks' profitability in the UK Retail

Banking. This supports (DeYoung, 2001), findings that interest and non-interest income should work alongside for greater profitability.

5.10.3 REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Regression Analysis using the diversification level (HHI) as a predictor of NOI is conducted and shown in Table.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.524 ^a	.275	.244	25.670

a. Predictors: (Constant), HHI

TABLE 13: REGRESSION OF HHI AND NOI

The coefficient of determination is the Adjusted R-squared and shows how the profitability of UK Retail Banks varied with the variations in HHI. From the Table 6.1, we get the Adjusted R-squared value of 0.244, meaning that HHI accounts to 24.4% of the variance in NOI with $r=0.524$ and $p\text{-value}=0.006$.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5985.195	1	5985.195	9.083	.006 ^b
	Residual	15815.305	4	3953.8265		

Total	21800.500	5			
-------	-----------	---	--	--	--

a. Dependent Variable: NOI

b. Predictors: (Constant), HHI

TABLE 14: ANOVA FOR HHI AND NOI

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	49.570	21.802		2.274	.032
	HHI	32.720	10.857	.524	3.014	.006

a. Dependent Variable: NOI

TABLE 15: COEFFICIENTS FOR HHI AND NOI

The linear regression equation can be written as:

$$\text{NOI} = 49.570 + 32.720\text{HHI}$$

Where 32.720 is an estimated change in NOI corresponding to a change in HHI level. P-values of 0.032 and 0.006 measures how significant the results are and how significantly are they from 0. 49.570 is the y-intercept. This is the predicted value when HHI is 0. It could be interpreted that on average and everything else constant, a one unit increase in HHI would increase the NOI by 32.720. Also, on average and everything else constant; one standard deviation increase in HHI results in 0.524 increases in NOI.

Regression Analysis using the diversification level (HHI) as a predictor of EBIT is conducted and shown in Table:

Model Summary

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
2	.448 ^a	.167	22.19456

a. Predictors: (Constant), HHI

TABLE 16: REGRESSION OF HHI AND EBIT

The coefficient of determination is the Adjusted R-squared and shows how the profitability of UK Retail Banks varied with the variations in HHI. From the Table 16, we get the Adjusted R-squared value of 0.167, meaning that HHI accounts to 16.7% of the variance in NOI with $r=0.448$ and $p\text{-value}=0.022$.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
2	Regression	2965.672	1	2965.672	6.020	.022 ^b
	Residual	11822.367	4	2955.59		
	Total	14788.038	5			

a. Dependent Variable: EBIT

b. Predictors: (Constant), HHI

TABLE 17: REGRESSION OF HHI AND EBIT

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
2	(Constant)	85.191	18.850		4.519	.000
	HHI	23.032	9.387	.448	2.454	.022

a. Dependent Variable: EBIT

TABLE 18:: COEFFICIENTS FOR HHI AND EBIT

The linear regression equation can be written as:

$$\text{EBIT} = 85.191 + 23.032\text{HHI}$$

Where 23.03 is an estimated change in EBIT corresponding to a change in HHI level. P-values of 0.000 and 0.022 measures how significant the results are. 85.191 is the y-intercept. This is the predicted value when HHI is 0. It could be interpreted that on average and everything else constant, a one unit increase in HHI would increase the EBIT by 23.032. Also, on average and everything else constant; one standard deviation increase in HHI results in 0.448 increases in EBIT.

Regression Analysis using the diversification level (HHI) as a predictor of ROTA is conducted and shown in Table:

Model Summary

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
3	.193 ^a	.037	5.92981

a. Predictors: (Constant), HHI

TABLE 19: REGRESSION OF HHI AND ROTA

The coefficient of determination is the Adjusted R-squared and shows how the profitability of UK Retail Banks varied with the variations in HHI. From the Table 8.1, we get the Adjusted R-squared value of 0.003, meaning that HHI accounts to 3% of the variance in NOI with $r=0.193$ and $p\text{-value}=0.344$.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
3	Regression	32.712	1	32.712	.930	.344 ^b
	Residual	843.903	4	210.97		
	Total	876.615	5			

a. Dependent Variable: ROTA

b. Predictors: (Constant), HHI

TABLE 20: ANOVA FOR HHI AND ROTA

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
3	(Constant)	13.043	5.036		2.590	.016
	HHI	2.419	2.508	.193	.965	.344

a. Dependent Variable: ROTA

TABLE 21: COEFFICIENTS FOR HHI AND ROTA

The linear regression equation can be written as:

$$\text{ROTA} = 13.043 + 2.419\text{HHI}$$

Where 2.419 is an estimated change in ROTA corresponding to a change in HHI level. P-values of 0.016 and 0.344 measures how significant the results are and how significantly different are they from 0. 13.043 is the y-intercept. This is the predicted value when HHI is 0. It could be interpreted that on average and everything else constant, a one unit increase in HHI would increase the ROTA by 2.419. Also, on average and everything else constant; one standard deviation increase in HHI results in 0.193 increases in ROTA.

Regression Analysis using the diversification level (HHI) as a predictor of ROE is conducted and shown in Table.

TABLE 22: REGRESSION FOR HHI AND ROE

TABLE 23: ANOVA FOR HHI AND ROE

TABLE 24: COEFFICIENTS FOR HHI AND ROE

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
4	.305 ^a	.093	.055	9.91096

a Predictors: (Constant), HHI

The coefficient of determination is the Adjusted R-squared and shows how the profitability of UK Retail banks varied with the variations in HHI. From the Table we get the Adjusted R-squared value of 0.055, meaning that HHI accounts to 5.5% of the variance in ROE with $r=0.305$ and $p=0.129$.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
4	Regression	242.436	1	242.436	2.468	.129 ^b
	Residual	2357.449	4	589.36225		
	Total	2599.885	5			

- a. Dependent Variable: ROE
- b. Predictors: (Constant), HHI

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
4	(Constant)	9.787	8.417		1.163	.256
	HHI	6.585	4.192	.305	1.571	.129

a. Dependent Variable: ROE

The linear regression equation can be written as:

$$\text{ROE} = 9.787 + 6.585\text{HHI}$$

Where 6.585 is an estimated change in NOI corresponding to a change in HHI level. P-values of 0.256 and 0.129 measures how significant the results are and how significantly different are they from 0. 9.787 is the y-intercept. This is the predicted value when HHI is 0. It could be interpreted that on average and everything else constant, a one unit increase in HHI would increase the ROE by 6.585. Also, on average and everything else constant; one standard deviation increase in HHI results in 0.305 increases in ROE.

The above four models find a statistically significant linear relationship between the product diversification level (HHI) and the financial performance indicators ROTA, ROE, EBIT and NOI. The study therefore concludes with the help of Herfindahl- Hirschman Index that on both the aggregate and individual level, UK Retail Banks are moderately diversified. There is a strong positive correlation between the HHI and the financial performance indicators and a statistically significant linear relationship between the HHI and ROTA, ROE, EBIT and NOI. **The study therefore concludes with the help of Herfindahl- Hirschman Index, Correlation and Regression that product diversification improves the financial performance of the UK Retail Banks for the studied period 2008-2019.** This study opposes the findings of European Banks by (Mercieca, 2007), that the product diversification has a negative relationship with the financial performance. However, this study does go in line with the findings of (Canals, 1993), who analysed the profits of banks and found that the increased profit and hence improved performance was due to the increased revenue from other business units (diversification).

5.11 Conclusion

In this chapter, we presented the results of our primary and secondary data and analysed it. In the next section we will discuss our findings of the data.

6. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

6.1 Understanding the effect of product diversification on the financial and non-financial performance of UK Banks

Diversification, in its literal sense means a bank entering into an activity (fee-based), other than its traditional means of earning (loans and deposit-taking) to generate income. Common wisdom holds that diversification would bring bank increased revenue and reduced risk, but does it? This reduced risk and

increased revenue/profit is a result of the positive relationship between the different activities or business lines. So, when banks diversify across other lines of business; there is still a degree of expertise present. This means that when banks diversify, they actually use their current resources to expand into other activities. So when banks diversify they get a competitive advantage through economies of scale and by using banks current expertise and abilities across non-identical or dissimilar product lines. The assumption that diversification brings increased revenue is probably more attainable when banks expand into homogenous lines of business.

Diversification in Retail Banking had a positive effect on the profitability of UK Banks and now we move on to understand its effect on the non- financial performance.

With diversification, banks decided to rely on more than one income stream to gain profitability. Though it did have a positive correlation with banks' profitability, it did lead to an adoption of aggressive sales-led culture which is considered to be the root cause of Financial Crisis of 2008. What this culture did was to shift banks' focus towards short-term goals of aggressive selling which in turn lead to increased profitability and competitive atmosphere in the industry of who holds the maximum market share. However, this happened at the cost of poor customer satisfaction, mis-selling of products to consumers and operating on unethical and immoral standards. We will now investigate some examples of aggressive sales culture across the top 5 banks. Since the interviews were conducted under Chatham House rules, the findings will be presented in anonymity. However, we will be using some examples from published works and those will be well referenced.

- One interviewee reported that “...we weren't really encouraged to value customers, for banks customers were just cash-cows.”

This mirrors the comments made by an employee of HSBC to the Future of Banking Commission in 2010 where he reported that “*..we had to sell, whether it was for the customer or not.*” He further reported that it would have been better to sell if they knew the customers’ needs but that was overlooked as everyone was trying to meet their targets.

Which?’s survey of 66 HSBC employees revealed similar findings where 41% of them reported to be pressured to sell because of culture and 33% reported to mis-sell because of manager’s pressure.

Some interviewees reported that:

- “ *...we had daily targets to meet and were publicly shamed to have not met them*”.
- “ *...daily target meeting was a norm at start of the day and the day usually ended with shame walk, with name-calling and trash thrown on if the targets weren’t met*”.

This mirrors Which?’s survey where 46% of the 371 employees from top 5 banks reported that some of their colleagues have mis-sold to meet their daily targets and 40% of these employees reported that the unreasonable targets drove them to sell even when it was not appropriate.

A former RBS employee reported something similar in (Martin, 2014) that a monster of a sales culture was invented where employees were measured according to rigorous targets. This was further conformed by Which’s survey of 71 RBS employees who felt in a similar manner. 51% of them reported to have mis-sold just to meet their daily targets and 32% reported their discomfort in doing so.

Some interviewees further reported that:

- “...once I was heavily incentivised to mis-sell PPIs and home insurances...”
- “...the atmosphere was hellish, we had to sacrifice our morals to keep our jobs...”
- “...a few of us were told to cater customer needs and weren't paid incentives while our peers were being paid to sell, **sell their morals!!**”

These comments mirrored the testimonies of employees from RBS reported in Guardian in 2005 where two tellers had cabbages placed on their tables within public view. They reported to be upset with the action but were only allowed to remove it once someone opened an account with them. This further mirrors views of 71 RBS employees. 32% of whom were uncomfortable with bank's approach to sales and 43% reported to sell despite not being appropriate.

Though this aggressive culture brought immense profitability but became the major cause of Financial Crisis of 2008 and in turn compromised with banks' reputation, ethics, and trust amongst the public.

6.1.1 Trust

Trust is a fundamental requirement for any successful organisation. . (Saparito, 2004) survey of 217 bank managers and 1093 customers found that trust is the key in order to maintain a good customer relationship and to prevent customers from switching to customers.

The 2008 crisis and subsequent scandals like PPI that followed really shook public's trust in the banking system. Which's survey of consumers reported that 8 in 10 customers had no faith in the banking system and many said that bankers do not act in consumer's interest. A consumer went on to say that “..PPI is just another chapter, there will be something else. It's there, it's behind the scenes and I think that something else will crop up, some other scandal and it will be like here we go again.”

Majority of the consumers felt that problems with banks run deeper than a few individuals making wrong decisions. 62% of the consumers felt that banks will be ineffective in delivering cultural change.

Banks in particular are based on trust considering the fact that we trust them with our money. Therefore, banking requires confidence from public that banks are not taking undue risks and are acting ethically. The Edelman 2013 Global Trust Barometer showed that out of all the business sectors, public has very low trust in the banking system mere 22% in 2013 after surveying 31,000 people in 26 countries. The Barometer found that the lack of trust was driven by poor performance and perception of unethical behaviour. 78% of the people in UK reported to have been aware of the prior year's banking and financial services scandals with 59% pointing out that the cause of the scandals was behaviour especially corruption and poor corporate culture.

A consumer was reported saying “*there is no limit to ‘do you want insurance?’ every time I went to the branch I had to repeat myself ‘I already have the insurance’*”.

Source: Edelman © August 2013 The Financial Brand

FIGURE 15: CAUSES OF FINANCIAL SCANDALS

The survey asked the consumers what they thought were the drivers of recent financial scandals. Consumers linked 59% of the issues with internal and culture issues which is within business control. They reported that 23% of the issue is driven by compensation and bonuses corporate culture, 25% corporate corruption and 11% conflicts of interest which are all within business control.

Moreover, trust in banking was further eroded amongst bankers themselves where 50% of Lloyds staff expressed their unhappiness because of the pressure to sell, followed by Barclays at 51%, RBS at 48% and Santander at 52%.

Many bankers expressed their discomfort to the author by saying:

- *“sales is always the priority in terms of performance”*
- *“I was made to feel worthless when I couldn't make enough sales”*
- *“it was a sell or go atmosphere, either sell or quit the job”*
- *“hit the target or lose your bonus”*

70% of senior bankers believed that there are significant cultural problems in the industry and 78% believing that the industry will benefit from the cultural change.

6.1.2 Employee Satisfaction

Although there are no standardized surveys within the UK Banking industry, yet how satisfied are employees can be found through various studies by Which? and interviews of various employees in many cultural change studies.

Which? studies showed that employees were pressured into selling against their morals and will where 37% of the respondents were not comfortable with the pressure to sell and 43% did not enjoy the challenge of selling. The study showed that more than 50% of the employees in top 5 banks were pressured to sell either by culture or their managers which shows immense displeasure with their jobs. This is explained by the absence of retail banks in Sunday Times top 100 companies to work for.

This mirrors with the author's interviewees who pointed out their discomfort in being pressured to sell and doing things against their morals.

The 2012 study found that the top 5 banks were still operating in an "aggressive sales-led" culture. Some of the key findings were:

- 56% of Lloyds staff reported to be **pressured to sell because of culture**, where RBS reported 35%, HSBC 41%, Barclays 33% and Santander 29%.
- The **pressure to sell by manager** still existed in Lloyds 46%, RBS 31%, HSBC 33%, Barclays 30% and Santander 25%.
- Employees were **pressured to sell against will** in Lloyds 45%, RBS 43%, HSBC 39%, Barclays 35% and Santander 23%.
- **Employees were uncomfortable with bank's practices** in Lloyds 37%, RBS 32%, HSBC 33%, Barclays 27%, and Santander 14%.

6.1.3 Ethics in UK Retail Banking

Banks were seen to be acting unethically and immorally pre and post the financial crisis period, examples being Mis selling of PPI, tax evasion and selling garbage for the price of gold. So I will look into the literature on culture and unethical behaviour. The banking industry is not only about money: it also involves a lot of number crunching. And, research suggests, even basic math increase people's likelihood of engaging in unethical practises. Research (Wang, 2014) finds that number crunching put people in a "calculative mindset" that makes them more likely to focus on a quantitative approach to solving a problem, overlooking moral consequences. After engaging in a calculative task, people were more likely to succumb to the greed of higher margins by acting more selfishly or dishonestly. Thus, the mere act of calculating can activate a

calculative mindset that outweighs moral concerns. (Trevino, 2014) summarises the literature on the causes of unethical behaviour in an organisation. It concludes that it is a leader who should play an important role in promoting a moral culture and promote its employees to take more ethical decisions when faced with temptation. This is in contrast with the existing culture of ‘moral disconnection’ where employees do not see their unethical behaviours as ‘wrong’ because they have to achieve their targets and whatever they do affects their pay which leads me to analyse literature on ‘how pay effects performance’ or how the ‘pay-structure’ effects performance.

Following the crisis of 2008, one of the major concerns that unearthed was the ethics in the banking system. A survey conducted in 2013 with 4,207 respondents regarding the ethical standards in British Banking found that 65% agreed that there is existence of ethical problems in the UK banking system, whereas 30% were unsure. Despite the claims by most banks to have developed better ethical standards, the public faith was not restored as the survey also found that 36% of the respondents disagree that banks were switching to more ethical culture and 52% of the respondents were unsure if that was actually happening.

- When asked to the interviewees about their opinion on ethical standards in their respective banks, one interviewee responded “ *...the atmosphere is too fast-paced. There is a race to meet targets which often results in mis-selling*”.
- Another interviewee added “ *...the pressure to meet targets has doubled. We did focus on customer needs for few years after the crisis but have reinstated to aggressive selling to meet the targets*” ...
- However, another interviewee had a different response “ *...following the crisis, the focus shifted to serving customer needs, sales targets were discarded and customers needs became priority...* ”

- Though the responses from the interviewees were mixed, a survey by the Ethical Consumer Magazine (2013) opposed the claims of UK bank being ethical. Their scorecard ranked banks based on honesty, customer service and ethical standards. The top 5 banks were at the bottom of the league table whereas challenger banks like Metro Bank and Nationwide topped the league table with exceptional scores of 77 and 76. Despite the top 5 banks claims to be ethical, they were in the lower quartile of the league table meaning majority of the public was receiving below average customer service as well as unethical despite having a majority 85% market share of UK Retail Banking.
- The results raise serious concerns about the efficiency of the British Banking system as 85% of the banking operates on unethical culture and provides below average customer services to most of the population. The top 5 banks will benefit well if they learn from challenger banks like Metro Bank and Nationwide.

The findings goes in line with the studies of (Dietz, 2004) (Smith V. , 1990) (Weeks, 2004) who concluded that banking is about forming a relationship and that positively correlated with banking performance. Trust is the key in order to maintain a good customer relationship and to prevent customers from switching to competitors (Saparito, 2004). Bank employees' were not fond of bank being risk averse, too bureaucratic and not at all customer focused. Employees' however remained loyal to their jobs due to their love for their respective branches and not the bank itself (Weeks, 2004).

(Nayak, 2008) Change in culture to creating confident customers. Banks are now more focused towards shareholder value creation. Employees must learn customer service skills which are monitored and reinforced through performance related pay and appraisals. Successful achievement of targets is crucial for managers. Their salary, bonus, career progression, status and job

security rely on their ability to achieve required results within the performance culture.

The diversification of income streams unearthed one of the major drivers of financial crisis i.e. culture and though it benefitted the banks financially, it had an adverse effect on the non-financial performance indicators like trust, employee satisfaction and ethics in the UK banking as evident from previous literature and interviews.

INNER DYNAMICS

The 'sales-led' culture which was considered to be the core reason for financial crisis obviously raised doubts in public's mind about the worthiness of these institutions. The collapse of major banks alarmed the public that their money is not safe. This culture adversely affected the banking reputation amongst general public. This adverse reputation was a **THREAT** to the banking system and banks had to shift their focus to being a Customer-oriented culture as an **OPPORTUNITY** to regain the lost confidence. There have been various regulatory changes ever since the financial crises and the establishment of BSRC to ensure the conformity of standards by banks (**STRENGTH**). Despite the regulatory changes, banks continued the sales-led culture and the LIBOR scandal raised public doubts of bank's non-conformity of regulations (**WEAKNESS**).

OUTER DYNAMICS

There are high barriers to entry, since it costs a lot to establish a bank leading to a lack of competition in the industry and lack of substitutes available (**PORTER'S FIVE FORCES**). Since the customers are not well informed

(low financial capability), they are not in a position to select between products and identify the best deal for themselves.

PAY-OFFS

Shareholders demand increased return on investments over a short term (3year investment cycle) meaning CEOs have relatively short decision making horizons. This means that if the results of cultural change are not forthcoming in the next few years, they'll put increased pressure on executives to focus on more aggressive means to get increased returns.

Employees are low-paid and widespread job cuts increases their insecurity meaning staff might be under pressure of meeting increasing sales target in order to sustain. Sales –based bonuses are just a way of enforcing a sales-led culture.

GRAMMAR

➤ **MACRO CULTURE**

The core reason for the failure of banks was identified as the rise of a sales culture within the banking industry. What's intriguing is that this sales culture was not limited to one organisation; it was replete throughout the industry. Though it gave bankers a shared way of looking at the problems they faced, but they overlooked the long-term risks. Problems escalated and hence lead to financial crisis. Since the culture was so ingrained, seniors continued business as normal up until 2012 when LIBOR scandal raised doubts and a pressure on banks to address their culture. It is now recently that banks have abandoned this sales-led culture and seeking to switch to a better 'customer-oriented' culture.

The focus is on leaders at the top of the organisation to emphasize on creating common values. This would focus on creating a need for change, articulating common behaviours and working on leadership issues. In the cascade down program the need for senior leaders to get involved in the culture change

process is emphasised and is focused on encouraging them to not forget humanity. So when the need for change is inculcated in senior leaders, they will be able to cascade it down to the organisation. Transformational leadership workshop would be a great idea to engrave leadership standards in the senior leaders for them to pass on to their organisation.

Another approach would be reinforcement through everyday process (bottom-up to constantly reinforced culture). Instead of focusing on top leaders and expecting them to cascade down the new culture to organisation, it would be better to focus on all members of an organisation and seek to reinforce widely shared sets of values.

Third approach could be to build a culture from scratch. This would work for banks which were made up of parts of other financial organisations such as TSB and Virgin Media. E.g. Shawbrook's processes that would reinforce culture remained part of the business it is made up of.

TONE FROM THE TOP

Establishing tone from the top would ensure correct values are expressed and embodied by the CEO. It should also involve the senior management who should 'live the values'. In this way senior managers would become culture enablers who would cascade the value to the organisation. In order to do that senior managers would rely on experience designed to cut them off from the previous culture by looking at its dark side. Truth and reconciliation style workshops would be helpful where they would be shown videos of the wrongdoings of bank and encourage them to discuss the core values of bank and its significance to them.

A good way to move from a sales-led culture would be the change in remuneration package. Sales-based bonuses should be eliminated and more

focus on customer satisfaction should be embedded. Customer surveys e.g. “how did we do?” and possibly reward the employees with maximum compliments with a bonus would drive the employees to be more customer focused.

It should be noted that employees should understand the culture of the bank instead of being reminded and forcefully made to follow. Customer-focused culture should be embedded in the banking culture not pervasive throughout the banks. e.g. Metro Bank’s workplace architecture to reward systems were designed to consistently reinforce a customer centric culture.

The use of ‘Balanced Scorecard’ to assess an employee’s performance would be a better approach. In the past, sales were an important aspect. Over the recent years, customer-orientation has taken over. It would be a good idea to work as a balance of both meaning the outlook of bankers is more likely to be balanced.

Challenges

The old culture is still embedded within the banks’ employees. They have spent decades working on a sales-led culture and a shift to being customer-driven makes it difficult for them to change their underlying beliefs and assumptions. It can create a sense of concern amongst employees, whether the skills they have gained over the years in a sales centric culture, would be relevant in a new culture of customers and integrity. Also a large scale shift often leads to job cuts or change management; this could lead to employees being uncertain about further culture change initiatives.

Banks may face integration challenges if they have merged with different parts following different cultures. Also employees may not be willing to take responsibility for changes. This was seen when retail divisions were seen blaming investment divisions for their involvement in scandals like LIBOR.

Cultural change is not a fast process; it might take a generation to change it. Amidst all the scandals and crisis executives are seen focusing on cultural change. However, if their focus shifts, especially when shareholders demand increased returns, banks might return to their old culture of increasing short-term shareholder returns even before achieving the milestone it has worked for. Banks have to follow certain rules and regulations post the crisis and it needs to be integrated in their activities, however it might overload the organisation and regulatory and compliance demands might actually lead to more rationalisation rather than a better culture.

Commenting on its successfulness is too early because it will take the British Retail Banks a generation to change the aggressive sales cultures which lead to the mis-selling of PPI and costed the industry £38.5bn in fines and compensation. A study by Cass Business School found that messages from the top executives about cultural change are still not reaching front line staff. Pointing to a sharp rise in complaints about banks to the Financial Ombudsman Service from 75,000 in 2008-09 to more than 400,000 in 2013-14, the report says banks have a lot still to do.

Rebuilding trust in the industry will take time; it won't be long until the public restores their trust in the banking industry. However, banks need to make sure they do not get involved in further scandals like the one which has just come to light (manipulation of commodities and foreign exchange markets) because this would not restore public trust. British Retail Banking has still a milestone to achieve.

6.2 FINANCIAL CRISIS- WHAT WENT WRONG?

The financial crisis without a doubt altered the dynamics of UK Retail Banking and made the problems evident to public, policymakers and regulators. We will look at the financial crisis in 3 stages:

- Immediate crises 2007-2008 (ensuring the continuity of banks),
- 2009-2012 (aggressive sales-led culture became evident), and
- 2012-present (continuity of bad behaviours (LIBOR) despite regulatory changes).

➤ **2007-2008**

Prior to the crisis, the UK financial institution relished a decade of continuous growth. Since the growth was based on a shaky foundation, it could not last long and the first disastrous impact was noticed with the failure of Northern Rock in 2007. This was followed by prolonged warnings from consumer groups and evidences of mis-selling of PPI. However, the disastrous impact was not limited to Northern Rock as Lehman Brother collapsed the following year, followed by a bailout of RBS and Lloyds by the UK government. This brought doubts on the funding positions of Universal Banks.

➤ **Journey from Crisis to 2012**

Following the crisis, a time of ‘learning and rectifying’ started. This included a progression of examinations and ensuing reports by the Future of Banking Commission, the FSA, the Treasury Select Committee, and the ICB. These reports identified issues that led to the collapse of a financially stable institution followed by remedial actions. In the meantime, fines started to show up. The inspection related with these fines disclosed the wrong behaviour inside the banks which went way past the mis-selling of PPI. This included poor handling of customer complaints, mis-selling of investment products and tax hedging products and money laundering. It was clear that there is a fundamental problem within the roots of the banking culture and very little or no steps were taken to change their practises.

➤ **2012-present**

The news of manipulation of LIBOR rate left the public baffled, because this time misbehaviour happened after the bailouts and the self reflection period. It was evidence that despite all the fines and warnings banks have not changed their ways.

WHAT NEXT??

A clutch of important reports into the continuing crisis in banking appeared during this period. These incorporated the Salz audit of Barclays and the reports coming about because of the Parliamentary Commission on Banking Standards (PCBS). The last prompted a progression of new laws to direct UK banks. What's more, the vast majority of the UK banks propelled huge scale change programs. LIBOR was a turning point as banks started to accept that 'fundamental change' is needed.

An example of this change is reflected in an example of the interview of Antony Jenkins, chief executive of Barclays, after taking over from Bob Diamond in 2012 following the LIBOR scandal.

He told the Financial Times (Arnold, 2014) that *“completely overhauled the way performance is measured and how people are incentivised and nobody is paid to sell anything in the branches any more”*. *“They are assessed on how they serve customers”*. *“We have developed a system at Barclays to measure both what people have to deliver – based on our balanced scorecard – and how they deliver it. Overall compensation is a composite of the two and importantly if someone achieves their goals but does it in way that is not compatible with our culture then they will fail to hit their target.”*

6.3 Macro Culture

Following the crisis, multiple inquiries into the failure of banks unearthed a rise of a sales culture in the retail banking a major reason for the Financial Crisis of 2008. What's interesting is this sales culture was not limited to one organisation, instead it was depleted throughout the banking industry. Hence, it is accurate to consider it as a macro culture that ran through out the industry. This resulted in bankers across the industry focusing on short term gains and thus engaging in increasing profitability at the cost of customer needs and long-term risks. The problems quickly accumulated, leading to many of the factors at the root of the financial crisis. However, because the wide macro-culture of sales was so ingrained into bankers, it remained difficult if not impossible for most bankers to really call it into question. There was also the pressure that to raise concerns about the sales culture could result in the person losing their job.

(Salz Review 2013) identified cultural shortcomings as a problem that led to the LIBOR rigging scandal. The review insisted a transformational change to restore the lost confidence and reputation amongst the public. Barclays had become too sales and profit driven and overlooked the interests of customers. Barclays lost its purpose and there was a strong drive to win as the bank got dominated by investment banking business which possessed a culture of winning. This reinforced focus on short-term financial performance which formed the basis of bonus in remuneration. 'The more the sales, the more the bonus' cliché took over serving customer interests. The report however recommends steps to rebuild reputation: setting high standards and transparency; board's effectiveness; new culture and values; strong, value-driven incentivised staff and risk culture framework and control functions.

Trust is a key component of the long-term performance of the banks. However, scandals like PPI, rigging LIBOR and tax evasions have undermined the public's confidence in the banking industry. (Alain Cohn, 2014), suggests that the 'sales-driven' culture weakens the honesty norm meaning that measures to

re-establish an honest and moral culture is very important. Evidence from the employee of HSBC says that ‘they had to sell whether the customer wanted it or not; they were not concerned about customers’ needs as they had a target to achieve and thus sold whatever they could’. This is an example of dishonest behaviour of banks. If banks become oblivious of the fact that they do not cater customers’ needs then it would be very difficult for public to restore their confidence in the banking system.

Some of the reports provide evidences of ‘sales-driven ‘culture by the employees of some of the major banks. Former RBS executive reported the ‘sales-based bonuses has been created which is leading to intense competition amongst employees to meet targets and sell products to customers even if they do not need it’. Whereas an employee of Halifax reported the ‘introduction of cash or cabbage day where employees who meet their targets were incentivised and those who could not were made embarrassed in front of everyone by giving them cabbages’. This form of incentive leads to competition amongst employees and more specifically an ‘unhealthy’ competition. Being competitive is good but when the competition gets unhealthy then results take over morals thereby leading to unethical practises in an organisation. The evidences suggest that it was the culture that led to the UK banking system’s train wreck. The increased competition drove employees to sell more in order to increase their wealth instead of banks and this is why it is recommended that indeed there should be competition but ‘healthier’. Banks should shift from being ‘sales-driven’ to being ‘customer-driven’ and then introduce competition but this competition would focus on ‘who served better?’ ‘Who provided what the customer needs?’ and any unethical or immoral practises should be immediately penalised. This would promote a healthier competition which in turn would lead to a safer and stable banking system.

The literatures and examples of evidences above highlight the adoption of ‘sales culture’ within the banking system and how it triggered the Big Bang of Financial Industry. Literature shows that this sales-led culture only created havoc and should be erased from the grammar of the banking industry. Literature recommends banks to go back to being ‘customer-centric’ and prefer morals over results. This would ensure a safer and stable banking system that would benefit both the customers and the UK Banking Industry.

6.4 The phase of denial

The news of the financial crisis reached out to the broader public and the public became aware of the macro sales culture. Despite the crisis, the senior bankers were reluctant to acknowledge many of the problems as 5 years down the line until 2012, senior bankers carried their banking operations as normal and expected the problems to just fade away as the time goes by. This resulted in top 5 banks who controlled the majority of UK Retail Banks market share to continue with their normal practices as late as 2012.

Following 2012, the news of fixing of LIBOR rates and the PPI scandal unearthed which in turn led to policy makers and regulators pressuring banks to address their culture. The pressure from public, policy makers and regulators made the banks rethink their macro sales culture. The banks committed themselves publicly to abandon the macro sales culture and work towards a culture that catered service over sales. However, the macro culture of sales remained strong.

6.5 The paths to reform

Having established that the macro culture needed to be transformed, the banking industry then took three different paths to reform.

- The first path was taken by top 5 banks who sought to change the industry through internal cultural change initiative. They introduced tone from top and sought that by creating the right tone from the top and then cascading it downwards would develop a culture that is more customer centric and encourages integrity.
- The second path was taken by institutions who perceived themselves as having a culture that was not infected with aggressive sales focus. These institutions saw their major challenge as preserving and fine-tuning their already existing culture.
- The third and final path to reform was the involvement of new competitor banks to come and establish their culture from scratch. They sought to build a novel culture brought from other industries and/or other countries and cater it to customer needs.

These three paths to reform has had some impact on the banking industry as a whole. With the entry of new competitor banks, customers now have a choice and the top banks have to compete in order to maintain their majority share. The most important path which will bring a massive change in the macro culture of the industry is the transformation of major banks since these banks control the 80% of the UK Retail Market and have a massive impact on how the banking culture develops within this banking industry.

6.6 ROLE OF CULTURE

One of the main factors for the crisis of banks has been identified as ‘culture’. Aggressive sales culture within retail banking, lead to the mis-selling of financial commodities. Whilst there has been legislation in place to address the ‘harder’ issues, ‘softer’ systems like culture has not been addressed and left on banks to solve themselves.

➤ **THE CONFUSION**

The former chief executive of Barclays, Bob Diamond, defined culture as how employees behave “when no one is watching.” Culture is something that emerges from the tone that senior individuals set within an organisation”. There are many reports that addressed culture but every report has a different understanding of culture. While some focus on norms, beliefs and values others focus on areas such as governance and standards. Some linked it with incentive structure and how performance is measured. Though, all the reports agree that culture is the core reason but it is difficult to interpret their definition of ‘culture’. However looking at a more tangible aspect like remuneration structure is preferable.

➤ **LONG PROCESS AND THE RESPONSIBILITY OF BANKS**

According to Financial Conduct Authority ‘culture is a matter for banks not UK regulators’ and to further explain their stance they went on to say that regulators are responsible for sound financial system and not the day to day running of business. Reports do suggest that culture is the root cause of crisis but leaves it on to the banks to solve it themselves and its assessment to Banking Standard Review Council. However, there is an agreement that this culture change is a long process and it might take a generation to achieve it.

➤ **MISPLACED OPTIMISM**

Banks tend to be overconfident about their own institutions in compared to their peers. According to a survey by The Economist 71% of the executives think that their bank outperforms the industry and a survey by Deloitte found that executives assume that it would take their banks 2 years on average to address

the cultural issues in their banks, whereas it will take 3 years on average for their competitors to do the same thing.

➤ **MULTIPLE LEVERS**

Reports identify a wide range of levers for change including governance, remuneration, code of conduct and many more diffusing levers which are outside the tool kit used in culture programmes such as HR and leadership. So in order to address the culture change in banks, conventional tools won't be enough. Attempts should be made to change more strategic issues like leadership, governance and risk management.

➤ **Top to Bottom OWNERSHIP**

Boards and senior executives are mainly responsible for cultural change. Reports place great stone on 'tone from top' and highlight the role of CEO as 'enablers of change. However, middle management should be responsible for embodying cultural change. Cultural change is mostly driven off-track by the staff in the middle of the organisation. Many banks have mission statements, code of conduct which is meaningless as they are not monitored. Culture must be enforced in the everyday behaviours through the line supervisors.

➤ **REGULATORS AS SUPPORTERS**

Regulators are not the drivers of cultural change, they are mere supporters. Regulation is not an answer. Regulators are there to set limits which should be

maintained. Banks themselves are the drivers of cultural change and also institutions like BSRC.

➤ **UNCERTAIN METRICS**

While the reports identify the urge for cultural change, there was no understanding of how to measure it. There are no rigorous metrics to test culture. While some recommends using gender diversity, customer satisfaction and compliance as metrics to track culture, others recommend stakeholder surveys. BSRC recommends a set of areas in which metrics may be developed.

DIMENSIONS	DESCRIPTIONS
Tone from the top	Board and Senior Management are starting points for setting core values and expectations of risk culture, and their behaviour must reflect the values being espoused
Accountability	Relevant employees at all levels understand the core values of the institution and its approach to risk, are capable of performing their prescribed roles, and aware that they are held accountable for their actions in relation to the institution’s risk-taking behaviour.
Effective Communication and Challenge	A sound risk culture promotes an environment of open communication

	and challenge in which decision-making processes encourage a range of views.
Incentives	Financial and non-financial incentives support the core values and risk culture at all levels of the institution

TABLE 25: THE LAMBERT REPORT RECOMMENDATIONS OF HOW TO MEASURE CULTURE.

6.7 Transforming the culture

Transforming the macro culture within the banking industry is likely to be a slow and difficult process. Most of the interviewees reported that “*cultural change is likely to take generation to achieve.*”

Stephen Green, chairman of HSBC, took a similar view: “*I think culture is incredibly important because it sets the tone ultimately for the values of the organisation... I strongly believe you cannot encapsulate everything you need to do in rules and regulations, therefore a focus on the value sets and behaviour in an organisation is... key.*’

I think the most important lesson from this crisis is an old lesson and not a new one, namely that rules may well be... necessary [but] are equally clearly not sufficient. No business, certainly no banking business, can afford to do without a board-led, senior management-supported, ethical approach to behaviour; to understand that there is a purpose to the business that you do, which is not simply measured by short-term profitability, is profoundly important, and unless that culture is there in an organisation, no amount of rule setting and no amount of careful compliance is going to be an adequate substitute.’

The fact that banks have committed themselves to transform their cultures has led to some improvements in the outcome of banking sector. They have made

progress in eliminating incentives based on rigorous sales. However, despite this claim customer complaints has not gone quite down yet.

Although from a prudential stand-point most banks have shown improvement, there have not been similar progress in terms of customer complaints. The number of complaints increased exponentially between 2010 and 2014 where the maximum complaint received for financial services was 512,167 in the year 2013/14. The complaints did go down in the years following 2014 however it has still not reached the pre-crisis era which was 123,089 and 127,471 complaints in 2008/09 and 2009/10 respectively.

In the first half of 2020, the most complaints opened were for 4 of the top 5 banks HSBC, Barclays, Santander and Natwest almost amounting to 53% of the total complaints received. The total complaints received were 829,870 out of which 83% is related to advising, selling, and arranging of protection services.

Despite a rising number of complaints to Financial Ombudsman Services, it is evident that most of the banks have been increasingly efficient in resolving the queries. It is noteworthy that an increase in complaints to Financial Ombudsman Services does not necessarily mean that there is a deterioration in the quality of services provided by banks. Up until 2015 almost 66% of the complaints were associated to past misconducts like PPI which have been resolved. In the first half of 2020 almost 83% of the complaints were related to inquiry about protection services while the remaining complaints were mostly associated to general administration complaints and information regarding charges on product performance.

The increasing complaints may be a result of lack in trust but most of the interviewers were reported saying ... *“an increase in complain is not proportional to poor conduct”* and *“...consumers are now more aware of their ability to complain due to the increase in adverts and ongoing promotions by claims management companies”*

However, it is evident that complaints are going down and it might go further down if banks continue to resolve queries the way they claim to be doing and improving their practises.

<u>BANKS</u>	<u>CURRENT ACCOUNTS (CUSTOMER SCORE)</u>
METRO BANK	82%
FIRST DIRECT	82%
NATIONWIDE	74%
BARCLAYS	66%
LLOYDS BANK	64%
HSBC	62%
SANTANDER	61%
NATWEST	61%
BANK OF SCOTLAND	59%
RBS	46%

Source: Competition and Markets Authority

As seen in the table above, Metro Bank stands at the first place along with First Direct with 82% customer score. This was followed by Nationwide with a 74% customer score. It is noteworthy that the top 5 banks are further down on the League Table with RBS being at the bottom not even meeting the average score, scoring only 46%. The other 4 of top 5 banks hit above average scores but

considerably lower than the banks on top in the league table. Barclays scored 66%, Lloyds scored 64% while HSBC and Santander just managed to get above average scored of 62% and 61% respectively.

The scores show that despite the claims of top 5 banks improving their customer service, their customer satisfaction is either below average (RBS) or barely above average (HSBC and Santander). What is interesting is that these scores go in line with the number of complaints received by Financial Ombudsman Services which goes on to show that the customers of top 5 UK Retail Banks are receiving either average or below average customer services. However, both the results go against the claims of interviewer who claimed that the increase in complaints could be a result of increased ads from claim companies. It is recommended to top 5 banks to take a deep look at Metro Bank, First Direct and Nationwide who are scoring high in their levels of customer services despite not holding major market share of UK Retail Banks.

Changing customers' perspective is not something which can be achieved rapidly. Instead, it will take a generation to build a customer focused culture.

6.8 Challenges facing the cultural shift

The old culture is still embedded within the banks' employees. They have spent decades working on a sales-led culture and a shift to being customer-driven makes it difficult for them to change their underlying beliefs and assumptions. It can create a sense of concern amongst employees, whether the skills they have gained over the years in a sales centric culture, would be relevant in a new culture of customers and integrity. Also a large scale shift often leads to job cuts or change management; this could lead to employees being uncertain about further culture change initiatives.

Banks may face integration challenges if they have merged with different parts following different cultures. Also employees may not be willing to take

responsibility for changes. This was seen when retail divisions were seen blaming investment divisions for their involvement in scandals like LIBOR.

Cultural change is not a fast process; it might take a generation to change it. Amidst all the scandals and crisis executives are seen focusing on cultural change. However, if their focus shifts, especially when shareholders demand increased returns, banks might return to their old culture of increasing short-term shareholder returns even before achieving the milestone it has worked for.

Banks must follow certain rules and regulations post the crisis and it needs to be integrated in their activities, however it might overload the organisation and regulatory and compliance demands might actually lead to more rationalisation rather than a better culture.

The macro culture of sales can easily derail the cultural change initiative by banks and this was quite evident when interviewing. The interviewees pointed out the challenges faced in implementing cultural change initiatives.

“initially, it was hard to understand what was our focus (service or sales).”

“honestly I was scared to be humiliated again when started to focus on service and not pushing sales”. Some reported of demands from investors for profit and internal blame shifting overloaded the banks with change initiatives.

Author: *is cultural change possible with management’s expertise?*

Interviewee: *the organisation was overloaded with too many initiatives and blame games were played in events of mistakes.*

Author: *do regulators need to intervene and solve the issues if you don’t get the culture right?*

Interviewee: *yes we need a mix of both. If regulators intervened without cultural change, it would not have been effective and cultural change initiative alone won’t solve the issues.*

According to the evidence collected, in order to resolve these issues some pressure from regulators is required. In addition, what has been witnessed is that tone from the top despite being essential is not enough. The message always gets lost when its cascaded down the organisation. What is needed is how the change processes are adopted in front line of the banks. Listening to front line staff and acting on their feedback will be essential in measuring progress.

There are vital drivers of change in macro-culture present. Boards of large banks continue to pay significant attention to cultural change issues. New entrants create some competitive pressure. However, these factors are fragile and could easily disappear. The agenda of boards could easily shift elsewhere. Competitive dynamics in the industry could also easily fall back into the long-run norm of the industry of being negligent. The sustained pressure for transforming the culture within the industry could disappear just as quickly as it appeared. At the same time as their being relatively fragile drivers of culture change, there are still significant barriers to change within the broader industry. These include pervasive short termism, the existence of a highly imperfect market, poor employment conditions and slow moving shifts in trust. To address these industrywide issues, there is clearly a need not just to change the culture within specific organisations, but a greater need to transform the culture of the entire industry.

6.9 Analysis of Problems

The detailed analysis of the triggers to Financial Crisis of 2008 unearthed 'culture' as the main reason for the failure. Though the banking industry relished years of profitability through diversification yet it had an adverse effect on its non- financial indicators like trust, customer satisfaction and ethics.

The author after analysing the data collected highlighted the following **issues** in the banking system and categorised them as follows:

- **Economic Issue**
- **Market-Place Issue**
- **Psychological Issue**
- **Structural Issue**
- **Governance Issue**
- **Incentives Issue**
- **Punishment Issue**
- **Oversight and Regulation Issue**

1. Economic Issue

- **Boom and Bust Cycle**

Sub-prime lending is the practise of lending to borrowers with low credit ratings. These loans carry above-average interest rates because banks carry high default risk on these loans (FICO scores less than 670). Sub-prime lending is considered to be the main contributor of 2008 crisis as this was the result of aggressive sales culture.

Since bankers were pressured to sell to increase their profitability, bankers sold sub-prime mortgages to consumers with below the acceptable FICO scores. This in turn led to consumers being unable to pay off their mortgages and hence resulted in the crisis leading the government to bail them out.

This issue was resolved by Bank of England that monitors micro and macro prudential risks.

- **Moral Hazard**

The aggressive sales-led culture initiated sub-prime lending which then led to the 2008 crisis. Banks did not bare the risk as they were backed by the national

government and taxpayer's money. This means that if banks did not have the back up, they would have been less aggressive in their risk-taking decisions.

This issue was resolved by alternative mechanism for dealing with failed banks. Bail-in was introduced to provide relief to banks on the brink of failure by requiring cancellation of debts owed to creditors and debtors. This was the opposite of a bail-out where failed banks were backed by government and taxpayer's money. This was introduced for banks to be more cautious in their risk-taking strategies.

(Edmonds, 2011), made several recommendations for UK banks to be able to absorb losses:

- Ratio of equity to risk weighted assets (RWA) of the large banks to be at least 10% and 13% if the regulators have concerns about the bank's risk mitigating abilities.
- All banks with headquarters in UK to maintain Tier 1 leverage ratio of 3% (4.06% of larger banks).
- Globally systemically important banks with headquarters in UK needs to have capital of core equity and bail-in subordinated debt of 17% of RWAs.

2. Market-place Issue

- **Lack of Competition**

Retail Banking in the UK is highly concentrated. The top 5 banks (Lloyds, Barclays, RBS, HSBC and Santander) accounts for 85% of the current accounts in the UK. The remaining market is made up of Nationwide, TSB and Co-operative Bank accounting for 12% of the UK Retail Banking Market. There are some new challenger banks in the market like Metro Bank which

accounts for 0.24% of the market and is slowly and gradually establishing its mark in the domestic Retail Market.

As evident, although the market is made up of many players; the top 5 banks bring most of the business to the market. Since, these banks have dominated the current account market for years, the Current Account Switch Guarantee was introduced in 2013 by the Government to make it simpler for consumers to switch current accounts and also to increase the competition between the banks. There have been 6 million current accounts switches since the service was introduced in 2013.

For years, the Retail Market had been lacking the competition and the Current Account Switch Guarantee was introduced to provide a simple, reliable and stress-free way to make the switch. This ensured that consumers have multiple choices and the banks to do their best to retain old customers while creating incentives to attract new ones.

- **Complex Products and poorly informed customers**

The 2008 crisis and subsequent scandals like PPI that followed really shook public's trust in the banking system. Which's survey of consumers reported that 8 in 10 customers had no faith in the banking system and many said that bankers do not act in consumer's interest. A consumer went on to say that *"..PPI is just another chapter, there will be something else. It's there, it's behind the scenes and I think that something else will crop up, some other scandal and it will be like here we go again."*

Majority of the consumers felt that problems with banks run deeper than a few individuals making wrong decisions. 62% of the consumers felt that banks will be ineffective in delivering cultural change.

Banks in particular are based on trust considering the fact that we trust them with our money. Therefore, banking requires confidence from public that banks are not taking undue risks and are acting ethically. The Edelman 2013 Global Trust Barometer showed that out of all the business sectors, public has very low trust in the banking system mere 22% in 2013 after surveying 31,000 people in 26 countries. The Barometer found that the lack of trust was driven by poor performance and perception of unethical behaviour. 78% of the people in UK reported to have been aware of the prior year's banking and financial services scandals with 59% pointing out that the cause of the scandals was behaviour especially corruption and poor corporate culture.

A consumer was reported saying “*there is no limit to ‘do you want insurance?’ every time I went to the branch I had to repeat myself ‘I already have the insurance’*”.

Financial products were overly complex, making them hard to understand for customers. Customer needs were not catered to. Customers were not given the information they needed to make informed choices neither did most of them had the financial literacy to make wise choices.

FCA investigated the product lines and banks were fined for some products. Banks voluntarily introduces simpler product for customers that cater customers needs. Banks even volunteered to provide financial literacy to customers in order to attract more customers and thus regaining the lost trust.

3. Psychological Issues

- **Denial**

The news of the financial crisis reached out to the broader public and the public became aware of the macro sales culture. Despite the crisis, the senior bankers were reluctant to acknowledge many of the problems as 5 years down the line until 2012, senior bankers carried their banking operations as normal

and expected the problems to just fade away as the time goes by. This resulted in top 5 banks who controlled the majority of UK Retail Banks market share to continue with their normal practices as late as 2012.

Following 2012, the news of fixing of LIBOR rates and the PPI scandal unearthed which in turn led to policy makers and regulators pressuring banks to address their culture. The pressure from public, policy makers and regulators made the banks rethink their macro sales culture. The banks committed themselves publicly to abandon the macro sales culture and work towards a culture that catered service over sales. However, the macro culture of sales remained strong.

4. Structural Issue

- **Ownership Model**

Shareholders continue to demand short term returns thereby resulting in pressure for risk-taking behaviour. In events of crisis, mistakes would be borne by shareholders not employees or executives.

There is no resolution to deal with this issue as yet.

The sales-led culture was mostly associated to inappropriate investment banking demands and this culture bled into the retail banking culture.

This issue was resolved through ring-fencing of investment and retail banking (Edmonds, 2011) however it was never enacted as the Vickers Report recommended *de minimis limit* under which the requirements for ring fencing won't apply.

5. Governance Issues

- There was a lack of understanding by the senior management and board of the risks taken at lower level of the banks. This resulted in high levels

of risk taking without oversight. This is resolved by increased monitoring of risk and conduct by FCA followed by compliance within banks.

- There was a lack of understanding and connection with longer term interests of shareholders. Often high levels of risk were taken with gains being syphoned off by high level employees and losses born by shareholders.
- Bank executives were of view that all they needed to do was comply with regulations. This led to poor practises which was outside the bounds of compliance being acceptable. This is resolved by increasing monitoring of conduct rather than compliance by FCA.
- The lack of diversity at senior levels gave rise to a herd-mentality which meant that decisions were not challenged, and ridiculous risks were taken. These issues are resolved by (Walker D. , 2009)'s recommendations in corporate governance areas of remuneration, governance of risk and the functioning of board.

6. Incentives Issue

Banks and executives were incentivised for taking unnecessary risks for increased returns which mostly resulted in taking risks without considering its costs. High level of compensation was given for poor performance or for forced sell when customers were forced to buy products they did not really want or have knowledge of.

Banks were seen to be acting unethically and immorally pre and post the financial crisis period, examples being Mis selling of PPI, tax evasion and selling garbage for the price of gold. So, I will look into the literature on culture and unethical behaviour. The banking industry is not only about money: it also involves a lot of number crunching. And, research suggests, even basic math increase people's likelihood of engaging in unethical practises. Research

(Wang, 2014) finds that number crunching put people in a “calculative mindset” that makes them more likely to focus on a quantitative approach to solving a problem, overlooking moral consequences. After engaging in a calculative task, people were more likely to succumb to the greed of higher margins by acting more selfishly or dishonestly. Thus, the mere act of calculating can activate a calculative mindset that outweighs moral concerns. (Trevino, 2014) summarises the literature on the causes of unethical behaviour in an organisation. It concludes that it is a leader who should play an important role in promoting a moral culture and promote its employees to take more ethical decisions when faced with temptation. This is in contrast with the existing culture of ‘moral disconnection’ where employees do not see their unethical behaviours as ‘wrong’ because they must achieve their targets and whatever they do affects their pay which leads me to analyse literature on ‘how pay effects performance’ or how the ‘pay-structure’ effects performance.

UK banks had a ‘sales-driven’ culture and that means ‘the more the sales the more the bonus’. This remuneration promotes unethical behaviour within the employees as they are driven to increase their individual wealth rather than the bank’s wealth. (Obloj, 2014) in their study examines a large number of loan decisions and concluded that the sales-based bonus is not in the financial interests of the bank. Employees were seen to be manipulating the sales in a way that reduces the bank’s wealth but increases theirs. One example of such manipulation is offering the loan at a lower rate which would attract customers and thus improve their sales. They concluded that for banks with managers who have ‘firm specific human capital’, the losses are higher indicating ‘adverse learning’.

Since this ‘sales-driven’ culture promoted unethical behaviour and also reduced wealth for the banks, it would be worthwhile to look at literature on culture and financial crisis. (Spicer, 2014), concluded that ‘an aggressive sales culture’ was

a major contributor to the financial crisis. The report found out that regulators have left it on banks to change their culture themselves and the banks have responded to it by initiating the cultural change process. They have refocused their attention to being customer-driven. This might take a generation to achieve and a consistency at all levels is necessary to keep this change intact. (Lui A. , ‘Greed, Recklessness, Dishonesty: and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK banks between 2004 and 2009’,, 2015) used a multiple case study approach to examine five UK banks: Northern Rock, the RBS, Barclays, Lloyds and HSBC between 2004-2009. In her paper she upheld both her hypothesis of the banks moving from a customer driven culture to a sales driven culture and that the UK banking culture between 2004 and 2009 was of greed, recklessness and dishonesty. (Fortado, ‘The yin and yang of introducing a sales culture: the Amalgam Bank Case’,, 2014), explored the introduction of a ‘sales culture’ at one of the top ten US banks (Amalgam Bank). Though the sales increased but brought along slowed service and irritated customers. Sales quotas were unrealistic and staffs were silenced by managers if they raised concerns. This resulted in unhappy and unmotivated staff, unhappy customers and unfair management practises but increased sales.

Bank’s unethical practises and sales-driven culture lead to financial crisis which in turn lead to the lost confidence among public. (Cohen, ‘Governance as the driver of culture change and risk management’ , 2015), explores the governance failure that led to reputational damage and then discusses what the banks have to do to restore the lost trust. She suggests the importance of cultural change and corporate governance process to support it. She recommends pervasive adherence to a set of values which sets pay and promotion and continuous monitoring of the process of embedding values. This monitoring would make the banks stay focused on their cultural change regime and not get distracted to making short-term gains.

Following the increased pressure to sell, FCA issued guidance on financial incentive to sell in 2013 identifying the characteristics of poor practise. This included sales incentive based on sales volume, hard to manage incentive schemes, and a lack of punishment for poor quality sales. It even identified the incentive system to decrease the likelihood of mis-selling, rolling sales targets and balanced scorecard. However, a subsequent study in 2014 found that all banks have significantly changed their practices and the increased pressure to sell which existed earlier was dealt with performance management of staff. This study opposed from the recent interviews conducted by the author who found that the pressure to sell and performance-based incentives still exists.

Few front-line interviewees reported:

- “ *...we had daily targets to meet and were publicly shamed to have not met them*”.
- “ *...once I was heavily incentivised to mis-sell PPIs and home insurances...*”
- “ *...daily target meeting was a norm at start of the day and the day usually ended with shame walk, with name-calling and trash thrown on if the targets weren't met*”.
- “ *...the atmosphere was hellish, we had to sacrifice our morals to keep our jobs...*”
- “ *...a few of us were told to cater customer needs and weren't paid incentives while our peers were being paid to sell, **sell their morals!!***”

7. Punishment Issues

There was an underlying issue of lack of individual responsibility where individuals were taking great risks and sometimes fail without being held accountable for the costs.

Also when employees saw wrong practices, they did not have proper channels for raising concerns as they were working in an aggressive environment where if they didn't take risks and sell, they were publicly humiliated.

- 56% of Lloyds staff reported to be **pressured to sell because of culture**, where RBS reported 35%, HSBC 41%, Barclays 33% and Santander 29%.
- The **pressure to sell by manager** still existed in Lloyds 46%, RBS 31%, HSBC 33%, Barclays 30% and Santander 25%.
- Employees were **pressured to sell against will** in Lloyds 45%, RBS 43%, HSBC 39%, Barclays 35% and Santander 23%.
- **Employees were uncomfortable with bank's practices** in Lloyds 37%, RBS 32%, HSBC 33%, Barclays 27%, and Santander 14%.

The study showed that the aggressive sales-led culture was engraved within the British Banking Industry and how despite the claims from top 5 banks to have reformed, the progress of change was not visible in the studied year and subsequently resulted in lack of public trust.

8. Regulation Issues

The tax structure rewards banks for taking on greater amounts of debt, resulting in a lack of equity to cushion the bank if failure occurs.

Credit ratings agencies had conflicts of interest and would often not provide accurate ratings of investment products or institutions.

Auditors had conflicts of interest and did not do their duty of outline major risks being run by banks.

Lack of common professional standards meant bankers were not held together by common morals or norms.

6.10 Conclusion

In this chapter, we identified the triggers to the financial crisis and found how diversification of income streams to relish increased profitability unearthed an aggressive sales-led culture. This macro culture of sales remained a stubborn part of industry who denied accepting the problems and resulted in further scandals like PPI which further deteriorated public trust in the banking industry.

The study identified with the help of Herfindahl- Hirschman Index that on both the aggregate and individual level, UK Retail Banks are moderately diversified. There is a strong positive correlation between the HHI and the financial performance indicators and a statistically significant linear relationship between the HHI and ROTA, ROE, EBIT and NOI. The study identified with the help of Herfindahl- Hirschman Index, Correlation and Regression that product diversification improves the financial performance of the UK Retail Banks for the studied period 2008-2019.

The diversification of income streams unearthed one of the major drivers of financial crisis i.e. culture and though it benefitted the banks financially, it had an adverse effect on the non-financial performance indicators like trust, employee satisfaction and ethics in the UK banking as evident from existing literature and interviews.

In order to address these changes and transform the culture, pressure needs to be maintained. The industry members needs to be patient with the change and

understand that change requires more than tone from the top. The industry needs a change in the macro culture within the UK banking industry. In the next chapter, the author looks at the progress made in the recent years and propose resolution for the addressed issues in this chapter.

7.CONCLUSION

7.1 Background

Retail Banking is the heart of UK economy. The greater part of the nation becomes a customer of the bank at a very early age and forms a relationship of trust with it. Traditionally, banks had a simple business model. Customers would rely on banks to access loans and other services while carrying out their day to day activities of making deposits and payments. However, due to excessive competition from the financial intermediaries who were tremendously profitable, UK banks decided to switch to the Universal Banking Model in order to be financially stable. German Banks who were still using traditional banking model were seen to be less profitable and less variable (Hoggarth, 1998).

As the banks reached out past the generally straightforward plan of action of the past, retail sector faced increased burden from shareholders for increased returns. As a response to this challenge, banks created an ‘aggressive sales’ culture. Banks started to forcefully promote new financial products to clients which in turn lead to "tellers" inside bank offices beginning to consider themselves to be “sellers”. This shift without a doubt brought expanded benefits, more scope of commodities and increased access to borrowings. Nonetheless, this accompanied a cost. Banks became adamant of the risks in lending. They planned low quality products and promoted them to clients independent of its suitability. It wasn’t until 2007 that banks begin to evidence the implications of this aggressive sales culture. The collapse and near-miss of

some of the major banks (through public bailouts), the miss-selling of Payment protection insurance (PPI) and billions set aside in compensation and fines for wrong-practises shook the public's confidence in banking system and by 2012 brought the British Retail Banks in crisis.

One of the major reasons for the failure of the UK Banking System is the adoption of a 'sales' culture. This is a set of embedded organisational norm and practises where short-term goals are preferred over long terms i.e. encouraging employees to focus on making short term sales at the expense of longer term customer satisfaction (providing them with the products they actually need within the bounds of integrity and ethics).

Originated in 1980s as an 'embedded' culture to UK Retail Banks, senior executives were of view that front line colleagues were not sales driven and hence not selling the financial products that banks offered. So, the idea was to promote these products to customers in every transaction. Banks even went on to change the way their branches looked; newer branches were designed to make a conversation between a staff and customer more natural. Questions like 'would you like something else' came in and introducing clients to new banking products e.g. loans, credit cards and services like PPI. Banks started to use 'incentives' as a positive reinforcement to boost sales. Performances became public through whiteboards, where staff with leading sales was rewarded while laggards were punished. Retail Bank went on to declare their commitment to building a sales-led culture. The underlying assumption was that this sales-oriented culture would lead them to operate and sustain in an increasingly aggressive market, whilst maximising profits and increasing returns to shareholders.

7.2 Purpose of this research

7.2.1 AIM

The aim of this research is to explore an issue at the very heart of the Financial Crisis and the series of scandals like PPI that followed: ‘culture’ and propose a strategy for a safer, reliable, and sustainable banking sector.

7.2.2 RESEARCH QUESTION

How could a ‘regulated sales-led’ culture save the British Retail Banking from yet another Financial Crisis?

7.3 Methodology

The author used a Mixed-Method Approach for this study. Since the literature is limited with studies on culture, this study proposes to do an exploratory research to analyse the culture with varying levels of depth and form a basis for future conclusive studies. And the author used a causal research design as it helps to generalize the findings of a larger population (in this case the UK retail banks).

The onion process identified the following design process used

➤ Research Philosophy: **Pragmatism**

The author believes that Pragmatism will be a significant philosophy for this research. The author aims to develop a regulated sales-led culture for a stronger and sustainable banking sector and that requires an in-depth analysis of the ‘pre-and post-financial crisis’ banking culture whilst analysing their financial performances during that eras. The literature has various studies choosing either positivism or interpretivism philosophy and that according to the author is a gap. A sound financial system cannot be built unless what is wrong with the existing practise is not identified, so it’s significant to support inductive approach with deductive thinking to provide a balanced perspective.

➤ Research Approach: **Abductive Reasoning**

The author is taking **Abductive Reasoning** approach for this research because there is possibly more than one explanation of the highlighted phenomenon (aggressive sales-led culture) and the author wishes to observe and test all the explanations if they are true in order to generate the best strategy for a safer, reliable and sustainable banking sector

- Research Methodology: **Case – Study**
- Data Collection Methods: **open-ended question interviews and secondary sources.**

7.4 Key Findings

Objective 1: To understand the sales-led culture, banks were operating in and identify the triggers to banks' failure.

We identified the triggers to the financial crisis and found how diversification of income streams to relish increased profitability unearthed an **aggressive sales-led culture**. This macro culture of sales remained a stubborn part of industry who denied accepting the problems and resulted in further scandals like PPI which further deteriorated public trust in the banking industry.

The diversification of income streams unearthed one of the major drivers of financial crisis i.e. culture and though it benefitted the banks financially, it had an adverse effect on the non-financial performance indicators like trust, employee satisfaction and ethics in the UK banking as evident from existing literature and interviews.

Objective 2: To evaluate how a sales-led culture-initiated product diversification and its effect on the financial and/or non-financial performance of UK retail banks.

The study identified with the help of Herfindahl- Hirschman Index that on both the aggregate and individual level, UK Retail Banks are moderately diversified. There is a strong positive correlation between the HHI and the financial performance indicators and a statistically significant linear relationship between the HHI and ROTA, ROE, EBIT and NOI. The study identified with the help of Herfindahl- Hirschman Index, Correlation and Regression that product diversification improves the financial performance of the UK Retail Banks for the studied period 2008-2019.

Objective 3: To compare and contrast results from objective (2) with the financial and/or non-financial performance of UK retail banks after the cultural shift to being ‘customer-centric’.

The diversification of income streams unearthed one of the major drivers of financial crisis i.e. culture and though it benefitted the banks financially, it had an adverse effect on the non-financial performance indicators like trust, employee satisfaction and ethics in the UK banking as evident from existing literature and interviews.

In order to address these changes and transform the culture, pressure needs to be maintained. The industry members needs to be patient with the change and understand that change requires more than tone from the top. The industry needs a change in the macro culture within the UK banking industry. In the next chapter, the author looks at the progress made in the recent years and propose resolution for the addressed issues in this chapter.

Objective 4: To propose a strategy where regulators, policy makers and banks work together to build a strong and stable financial system.

- Regulators need to think beyond competition: it was concluded that though competition is a good initiative, but it cannot be relied on to create better practices. Banks need to improve their internal practices and regulators should oversee it as regulations and cultural change initiatives need to work together to create better practices.
- Regulators can use behavioral economics to enhance good competition in the banking industry.
- Regulators need to keep a close eye on the internal processes to ensure customers are aware of what they are sold and if banks are doing relevant checks before giving out loans.
- Regulators need to go beyond senior management and observe the selling practices and experience of employees in branches. Regulators can use ‘mystery shoppers’ to look at the actual selling practices. this can bring various issues into light relating to poor practices and customer treatments.
- The policymakers should help develop an independent organization which will report its findings directly to policy makers annually not based on senior manager’s perception of culture but the culture which is at place in branch and what it means for customers and employees.
- Banks need to ensure that the front line staff are managed well as this has a direct impact on customer service.

- Banks should reconnect with its purpose. Their primary focus should not be to make money for shareholders, instead they should focus on social and economic purpose of bank. They should not lose their morals just for increased profitability instead they should provide sustainable value for shareholders by doing the right thing.

The author believes that an independent body should be made that bridges the gaps between banks, regulators, and policymakers. This body should report its findings directly to policymakers and policymakers should then make the findings public to restore the lost trust of public and a sound financial system.

- This body should ensure that the cultural change continues by building on the work that has already been done and focus on encouraging further progress. Banks should cooperate by providing the necessary resources.
- This body should be independent of the banks to avoid conflicts of interests. This means current or retired bankers can not be part of this body and the members of this body can not leave to work in one of the large banks.
- Most interviewees mentioned the message being lost in tone from the top. This body should work closely with the front-line staff to get an essence of the working environment and then compare it with the fancy words of culture written by senior manager. This will give the real picture of the culture and hence the problems in the system.
- The aggressive sales-led culture provided banks with immense profitability and though it helped banks with financial perspective, lack of non-financial metrics resulted in collapse of the banking industry. This

body will not collect data through surveys. In fact, this body will fill the gap in the literature and industry by using ‘in-house ethnography’. Bank insiders would be trained and asked to go around the banks and collect evidences of their culture. Under the mentorship of professional ethnographer, a report will be produced that will give the real picture of bank’s culture and not a rehearsed culture (in cases of in-depth interviews).

- The independent body should then focus on reviewing evidence gathered through in-house ethnography and other sources like customer complaints and whistleblowers to identify the potential risks to banks and ask banks of their strategies to mitigate those risks.

This body will report directly to policymakers and work in conjunction with banks and regulators to develop a strong and stable financial system.

7.5 Limitations and suggestions for future research

This thesis used a case study research method to explore the major trigger of financial crisis and primary data is only collected through in-depths interviews.

The understanding of the culture in depth requires in-house ethnography and that is the major limitation of this study as it does not give a rich picture of the culture yet. Another limitation is that the analysis is only based on data obtained from interviews and the secondary research.

There are many potential areas for future research. The future academics and researchers can research on:

- How failures in corporate governance led to the failures in the UK banking system?
- How competition affects the stability and profitability of the UK banks?

- How structural changes affects the stability and profitability of UK banks?
- Is nationalization of banks a solution to restore public trust on the banking system? A comparative study with banking in China.
- Financial Crisis and what have we learned from it. Are we heading towards another crisis?
- How has the culture in UK Retail banks changed post the crisis period and is it any better? Using In-house ethnography.

The author would also recommend doing the same research using ‘in-house ethnography’ method to get a much richer picture of the banks’ culture.

7.6 Conclusion

This chapter summarizes the background to this research, methodology used and the research findings from this thesis. The contributions to this thesis are also highlighted at the end.

8.RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 Introduction

In chapter 5, we highlighted various issues affecting the British Banking Industry and concluded that these were all triggered by an aggressive sales-led culture that unearthed because of diversification of income streams to relish increased profitability. Various inquiries have identified potential issues which need to be changed, some of which is addressed through legislation. The banks have taken it upon themselves to transform their culture through various cultural programmes. It has been observed that cultural change cannot be achieved rapidly and may take decades to bring favorable outcomes. In this chapter we

will recommend some resolutions that may be effective in addressing the underlying issues identified in this thesis.

8.2 What have we learnt so far?

More than a decade has past since the Financial Crisis of 2008. We established that there was a widespread problem of ‘aggressive sales-led culture’ in the UK Retail Market and banks have since sought to address the issue in hand to restore public trust in the industry. The transformation of culture has been a long journey so far and the journey is not over yet as it might take another decade to re-engineer the banking practices. Though long and tedious, the cultural change initiative has been a learning opportunity for the banks alongside regulators and policymakers. The author identified a number of lessons in this process.

- **Short termism**

The financial crisis of 2008 unearthed culture as the phenomenon that triggered bad practices. The tendency towards short termism will not be beneficial for creating a meaningful cultural change. In order to bring about an effective culture, time and focus is needed. Short-term fixes to the culture may give quick pay-offs but won’t be effective in the long run and would eventually lead to failure. All the interviewees agreed that the cultural change will take another 5 or 10 years to achieve through continuous efforts and reinforcement. Some interviewees were of view that though cultural change is the responsibility of bank but they should not be the only one responsible. An effective cultural change will come about with reinforcement from regulators as well. A senior banker said “ *we need both culture and intervention.. intervention without culture won’t work and culture itself won’t work*”. It has been deduced that short-termism is the enemy of cultural change and a safer culture can only come about with continuous efforts and reinforcement.

- **Tone from the top**

The Lambert Report pointed out that tone from the top is necessary in order to achieve a better culture. However, many interviewees argued that while tone from the top is necessary but it is not sufficient. There have been many reports that found that message from the top got lost in the middle and was absent in the front line. There were many reports in the past explaining employees dissatisfaction with pressure to sell and in order for cultural change to be effective, front-line's experience of work should be made better. Employees should be aware that the aggressive sales practices do not exist in reality and are not just replaced with some fancy words. If this is not in place, cultural change initiatives within the industry will be derailed.

One front-line interviewees reported that *“we have targets now but its not the same. Customer service is the king now.”*

- **Effective metrics**

This is a potential issue and needs to resolve as there are no effective metrics to measure culture. However, stakeholders said that a range of metrics are being used to track culture. Banks are relying on a small set of metrics to measure culture i.e. employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction and annual employee surveys. These metric are not effective enough to give an accurate picture of culture. Since banking system is going through cultural change, a mix of effective quantitative and qualitative metrics will provide insight into the real picture of culture within the banking industry.

- **Identifying problems**

The banks can benefit taking inspiration from other industries who focuses on identifying problems and reward those who found them. By identifying the problems, owning them and rectifying them in a timely manner will restore public's trust in the efficiency of the banking system. This will create an

impression in public of banks being proactive in resolving small problems which if not dealt timely could become a major phenomenon.

The inspiration could be taken from the fact that employee's dissatisfaction was at its peak during the crisis and despite various surveys identifying employees' discomfort over pressure to sell, not much was done in that regards. This eventually became a huge problem and if could have been handled timely would not have corrupted the culture as much.

There is a lesson to learn from this for banks and even regulators. Banks have opened a forum where employees can complain, and the senior managers address the issue. However, banks can go one step further and introduce a confidential line where employees can freely complain with anonymity. External forums from regulators can provide channels for whistle-blowers. By building this culture of openness, transparency and pROTActiveness to potential issues banks will regain public trust and confidence.

- **Addressing the Macro-Culture**

It has been established that banking needs change in macro culture because of the challenges facing the industry. Big banks have sought to transform their culture, while banks who weren't affected much are just fine tuning their culture because of their confidence on the culture. But this is not enough as individual bank's transformation will not be enough to change the macro culture. There needs to be new norms and practices established to show what good banking look like. This should be incorporated not only by big banks but all the banking industry including regulators, challenger banks, employees, and consumers in order to transform the macro culture as evidence by different industries like retail.

Regulators are of view that increasing competition will improve customer outcomes. The new switching regime introduced is a great progress, however on

its own it's not enough. Despite poor practices and adverse customer satisfaction, the top 5 banks still hold their majority shares in the market which shows that there is a negative correlation between customer satisfaction and market share. Even though new competitor banks came with better practices and culture and even score amazingly on customer satisfaction and ethics, their market share is insignificant to make any difference to the macro culture or the retail bank industry. The only way to transform the macro culture is for big banks to right their culture through reinforcement by regulators.

The author will now propose recommendations to banks, regulators, policy makers and the BSRC on the progress they can make through these lessons.

8.3 Recommendations to Regulators

Regulators are of view that increasing competition will improve customer outcomes and lead to a better culture. Since the banking industry lacked competition for over 100 years, this is a good idea to encourage competition amongst banks to serve customer needs. However, this is not the case as despite the adverse customer satisfaction banks like Barclays, HSBC, Lloyds, RBS and Santander still continue to hold majority shares in the UK Retail market almost amounting to 85% of the current accounts in the UK. This represents a customer inertia where despite clear and better products are offered by competitor banks, consumers still choose to stick to their original choice of banks. The personal switch regime though is simple and effective but still the top 5 banks maintain their dominance over the years. Also, its not clear if competition actually creates better practices as most of the new banks originated in early 2000 and that created an aggressive sales-led culture in the banks to hold their dominance and increase their profitability and this was the major driver of the 2008 crisis.

- So, it can be concluded that though competition is a good initiative, but it cannot be relied on to create better practices. Banks need to improve their

internal practices and regulators should oversee it as **regulations and cultural change initiatives need to work together to create better practices.**

One of the main reasons for lack of good competition is customer inertia. This is evident from the low level of switching from one bank to another. Since there is financial illiteracy amongst public, it is difficult for them to compare the products and choose the best option for them. Regulators can play an important role by making the transparent information available to consumers. In order for competition to work behavioral economics need to be in place which will help in understanding customer's needs. Various studies on behavioral economics found that customers will be drawn towards better decisions. Insights from behavioral economics can be used to enhance customer's wellbeing.

➤ **Regulators can use behavioral economics to enhance good competition in the banking industry.**

Post the crisis period, regulators were quite keen on non-financial indicators to better the banking industry. One such indicator was customer satisfaction. Though its good but it's limited with what the regulators are trying to achieve. Bankers can easily manipulate the results by acknowledging the query and resolving it through a small pay-off before the complaint reaches FCA. Customer complaints could possibly address potential issues which never reached FCA. One of the reasons for 2008 crisis was widespread sub-prime lending which customers eventually were not able to pay off. Similarly, customers may be satisfied with taking on loans because of reduced initial rates but unable to pay once the interest rates rises. This in turn results in bad debts.

- **Therefore, regulators need to keep a close eye on the internal processes to ensure customers are aware of what they are sold and if banks are doing relevant checks before giving out loans.**

Regulators should oversee tone from the top. There have been various findings where the senior bankers at the top say something else (which is always right and customer focused) which differs from what's happening at the branch level. This has been an issue since the crisis and if that branch level employees had a channel to raise their concerns, the banking culture would not have corrupted as much.

- **Regulators need to go beyond senior management and observe the selling practices and experience of employees in branches. Regulators can use 'mystery shoppers' to look at the actual selling practices. this can bring various issues into light relating to poor practices and customer treatments.**

What's happening at branch level gets lost especially when they go through a hierarchy. All employees including senior bankers should be able to approach and communicate their concerns to the regulators.

- **This will ensure that messages don't get lost and regulators are well informed of the concerns and what is happening in the banks.**

Regulators can play a vital role in helping the banking industry flourish instead of taking a hands-off approach. They can ensure the regular tracking of banks based on described standards and make it transparent for public to see the banks' progress and if the banks are actually making improvement.

The author proposes a **regulated sales-led culture** where regulators and banks work together to create a stable financial system since many interviewees have

been reported to say that though cultural change is the responsibility of banks but regulation is needed to create better practices.

8.4 Recommendation to Policymakers

Though the banks have committed to transform their culture, yet the results won't be visible that quick. Many interviewees reported that cultural change is a long process and may take decades. Policymakers need to understand this and accept that though the new scandals will emerge, but they could be the by-product of prior practices.

- **The policymakers should help develop an independent organization which will report its findings directly to policy makers annually not based on senior manager's perception of culture but the culture which is at place in branch and what it means for customers and employees.**

8.5 Recommendation to Banks

Banks need to ensure that there is a consistency in their practices and avoid changing their culture every other year. Banks should have a set of values which they should stick to for decades. It also needs to be consistent with their business model.

Since banks have placed greater responsibility on senior bankers to drive cultural change, it would be a best practice to hold them accountable for any malpractice. The Financial Crisis of 2008 made public upset as none of the senior managers were held accountable for their actions. This goes on to show to the public that bankers are taking undue risks as they are backed by government and causing moral hazard. Banks should hold CEOs and Chair accountable for any further malpractices.

Banks have tone from the top culture. However, it is often a concern that the message gets lost in the middle. Some of the interviewees reported that they have seen a positive change in culture and that their experience has become pleasant where they are rightly managed and appraised. Some even reported to be proud of working for their bank.

On the other hand, some interviewees reported that the targets have just been renamed but their purpose remain the same “*sales target have just been relabeled as customer service targets*”. Banks need to ensure that cultural change programs are making the front-line staff’s experience better, not worse.

Banks need to ensure that the front-line staff are managed well as this has a direct impact on customer service. Since front line staff are the direct contact of consumers, they are mostly at the receiving end of customer’s anger. Banks should prioritize front-line staff and make sure they are aware of the culture they are expected to operate in. The front-line staff should feel encouraged and empowered and any proposals to the new culture should be communicated effectively.

Lastly, banks should reconnect with its purpose. Their primary focus should not be to make money for shareholders, instead they should focus on social and economic purpose of bank. They should not lose their morals just for increased profitability instead they should provide sustainable value for shareholders by doing the right thing.

8.6 Establishing an Independent Body

The author believes that an independent body should be made that bridges the gaps between banks, regulators, and policymakers. This body should report its findings directly to policymakers and policymakers should then make the findings public to restore the lost trust of public and a sound financial system.

1. This body should ensure that the cultural change continues by building on the work that has already been done and focus on encouraging further progress. Banks should cooperate by providing the necessary resources.
2. This body should be independent of the banks to avoid conflicts of interests. This means current or retired bankers cannot be part of this body and the members of this body cannot leave to work in one of the large banks.
3. Most interviewees mentioned the message being lost in tone from the top. This body should work closely with the front-line staff to get an essence of the working environment and then compare it with the fancy words of culture written by senior manager. This will give the real picture of the culture and hence the problems in the system.
4. The aggressive sales-led culture provided banks with immense profitability and though it helped banks with financial perspective, lack of non-financial metrics resulted in collapse of the banking industry. This body will not collect data through surveys. In fact, this body will fill the gap in the literature and industry by using 'in-house ethnography'. Bank insiders would be trained and asked to go around the banks and collect evidences of their culture. Under the mentorship of professional ethnographer, a report will be produced that will give the real picture of bank's culture and not a rehearsed culture (in cases of in-depth interviews).
5. The independent body should then focus on reviewing evidence gathered through in-house ethnography and other sources like customer complaints

and whistleblowers to identify the potential risks to banks and ask banks of their strategies to mitigate those risks.

This body will report directly to policymakers and work in conjunction with banks and regulators to develop a strong and stable financial system.

9. References

- Acharya, V. H. (2002). Should banks be diversified? Evidence from individual bank loan. BIS Working Papers No 118.
- Alain Cohn, E. F. (2014). Business culture and dishonesty in the banking industry.
- André Spicer, J. P. (2016). *A report on the culture of British Retail Banking*.
- Anthony Salz, R. C. (2013). Salz Review: An Independent Review of Barclays' Business Practices.
- Arnold, M. (2014, November 26). *Financial Times*. Retrieved from Financial Times: <https://www.ft.com/content/01583a7c-74c7-11e4-a418-00144feabdc0>
- Arora, S. a. (2009). Internal determinants for diversification in banks in India an empirical analysis. . *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*.
- Author. (2021).
- Baele, L. D. (2007). „Does the stock market value bank diversification.
- Bandyopadhyay, A. (2010). Understanding the Effect of Concentration Risk in the Banks' Credit Portfolio.
- Bebczuk, R. a. (2008). Financial crisis and sectoral diversification of Argentine banks.
- Benkhoff, B. (1997). Ignoring commitment is costly: new approaches establish the missing link between commitment and performance. 701-726.
- Berry-Stölzle, T. L. (2011). Determinants of corporate diversification. *The Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 381-413.
- Böve, R. D. (2010). Do specialization benefits outweigh concentration risks in.
- Brummer, A. (2014). *Bad Banks: Greed, Incompetence and the Next Global Crisis*,. London.
- Brummer, A. (2014). *Bad Banks: Greed, Incompetence and the Next Global Crisis*. London.
- Buch, C. D. (2010). Cross-border diversification in bank asset portfolios. .
- Buono, A. F. (1985). When cultures collide: The anatomy of a merger. . 477-500.
- Busch, R. a. (2009). Income Diversification in the German banking Industry.
- Cabiles, N. (2012). Credit Risk Management through Securitization.

- Canals, J. (1993). Competitive strategies in European banking.
- Carretta, A. F. (2010). . The “day after” Basel 2: do regulators comply with banking culture?
- Chiorazzo, V. M. (2008). Income diversification and bank performance.
- Chreim, S. (2006). Managerial frames and institutional discourses of change: employee appropriation and resistance. 1261-1287.
- Cohen, M. (2015). ‘Governance as the driver of culture change and risk management’. *Journal of Risk Management in Financial Institutions*, .
- Cohen, M. (2015). ‘Governance as the driver of culture change and risk management’. *Journal of Risk Management in Financial Institutions*.
- Cornett, M. O. (2002). Bank performance around the introduction of Section 20. *The Journal of Finance*.
- Creswell, J. a. (2007). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*.
- Curran, J. a. (2001). *Researching the Small Enterprise*, Sage Publications,.
- D’Souza, C. a. (2003). Does Diversification Improve Bank Efficiency?
- David, C. a. (2005). Banks’ Loan Portfolio Diversification.
- Demsetz, R. &. (1995). „Diversification, size, and risk at bank holding compnies.
- Deng S.(E.)and Elyasiani, E. (2008). Geographic diversification, bank holding company value, and risk. *Journal of Money, credit and banking*, 1217-1238.
- DeYoung, R. R. (2001). Product mix and earnings volatility at commercial banks.
- Dietz, J. P. (2004). Service climate effects on customer attitudes: An examination of boundary conditions. *Academy of Management Journal*,, 81-92.
- Dooley, D. (2007). *Social Research Methods*.
- Douglas H. Frank, T. O. (2014). Firm-specific human capital, organizational incentives, and agency costs: Evidence from retail banking.
- Edmonds, T. (2011). *The Independent Commission on Banking: The Vickers Report*.
- Evelyn Hayden, D. P. (2005-2006). Does diversification improve the performance.
- Fang, Y. H. (2011). Institutional development and its impact on the performance effect of.
- Fisher, C. (2003). *Research and Writing a Dissertation for Business Students*, 1st Edition,.
- Fortado, B. a. (2014). ‘The yin and yang of introducing a sales culture: the Amalgam Bank Case’.
- Fortado, B. a. (2014). ‘The yin and yang of introducing a sales culture: the Amalgam Bank Case’,.
- Fraser, I. (2014). *Shredded: Inside RBS, the Bank That Broke Britain, Edinburgh: Birlinn Limited*.
- Gallo, J. A. (1996). ‘Commercial bank mutual fund activities: implications for bank risk and profitability. *Journal of Banking and Finance*,.
- Goetz, M. (2012). Bank Diversification, Market Structure and Bank Risk Taking.
- Hargie, O. S. (2010). Interpretations of CEO public apologies for the banking crisis: attributions of blame and avoidance of responsibility.
- Harris, L. (2002). The learning organisation—myth or reality? Examples from the UK retail banking industry.
- Ho, K. (2009). . Liquidated: an ethnography of Wall Street.
- Kamp, A. P. (2004). Do Banks Diversify Loan Portfolios?

- Kerr, R. &. (2012). From symbolic violence to economic violence: The globalizing of the Scottish banking elite. 247-266.
- Knights, D. &. (1997). 'How would you measure something like that?' 371-388. 371-388.
- Knights, D. &. (1998). 'What happens when the phone goes wild?': staff, stress and spaces for escape in a BPR telephone banking work regime. 163-194.
- Knights, D. &. (2012). Managing masculinity/mismanaging the corporation. .
- Kumar, M. V. (2009). The relationship between product and international diversification.
- Kwan, S. (1998). Risk and Return of Banks Section 20 Securities Affiliates. FR.
- Lepetit, L. N. (2008). The expansion of services in European Banking.
- Lui, A. (2015). 'Greed, Recklessness, Dishonesty: and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK banks between 2004 and 2009'. *Journal of Banking Regulation*.
- Lui, A. (2015). 'Greed, Recklessness, Dishonesty: and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK banks between 2004 and 2009'. *Journal of Banking Regulation*,.
- Lui, A. (n.d.). Greed, recklessness and/or dishonesty? An investigation into the culture of five UK Banks between 2004-2009.
- Manning, R. D. (2010 Q4). *Evolution of the UK banking system*.
- Martin, I. (2014). *Making it Happen: Fred Goodwin, RBS and the Men Who Blew Up the British Economy*.
- Mason, E. H. (2005). Deriving Credit Portfolio Diversification Properties from.
- McCabe, D. (2009). Enterprise contested: Betwixt and between the discourses of career and enterprise in a UK bank. 1551-1579.
- Mercieca, S. S. (2007). "Small European banks: Benefits from diversification.
- Mester, L. (1992). „Traditional and non-traditional banking:.
- Michel, A. (. (2014). The Mutual Constitution of Persons and Organisations: An Ontological Perspective on Organizational Change. .
- Michel, A. (2012). Transcending socialization: A nine-year ethnography of the body's role in organizational control and knowledge workers' transformation.
- Morgan, D. K. (2003). Geographic Diversification in Banking and its Implication for Bank.
- Mortgage Strategy*. (2012, December 7). Retrieved from <https://www.mortgagestrategy.co.uk/issues/online-december-2012/which-research-bank-staff-still-under-heavy-sales-pressure/>:
<https://www.mortgagestrategy.co.uk/issues/online-december-2012/which-research-bank-staff-still-under-heavy-sales-pressure/>
- Nayak, A. &. (2008). Infantilized adults or confident consumers? Enterprise discourse in the UK retail banking industry. 407-425.
- Neuman, W. L. (2000). *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*, 4th Edition, Boston, Allyn and Bacon.
- Reichert, A. W. (2008). The integration of banking and commerce.
- Roland, K. (1997). Profit persistence in large US bank holding companies.
- Santomero, A. &. (1992). Evidence in Support of BROTAders Banking.
- Sanya, S. a. (2011). Can banks in emerging economies benefit from revenue diversification? *Journal of financial services research*.

- Saparito, P. A. (2004). The role of relational trust in bank–small firm relationships. *Academy of Management Journal*, 400-410.
- Saunders. (2003). *Research Methods for Business Students*.
- Saunders, A. W. (1994). What Could We Gain? What could we lose?
- Schertler, A. B. (2006). Heterogeneity in lending and sectoral growth.
- Schneider, B. P. (1980). Employee and customer perceptions of service in banks. 252-267.
- Sibel Yilmaz Turkmen, I. Y. (2012). Diversification in Banking and its Effect on Banks' Performance.
- Smith, R., Staikouras, C., & Wood, G. (2003). Non-interest income and total income stability.
- Smith, V. (1990). . Managing in the corporate interest.
- Spicer, A. G. (2014). A report on the culture of British retail banking.
- Stiroh, K. a. (2006). The dark side of diversification.
- Tabak, B. F. (2010). The Effects of Loan Portfolio Concentration on Brazilian.
- Templeton, W. S. (1992). The Effect of Nonbank Diversification on Bank Holding Company Risk. *Quarterly Journal of Business and Economics*, 3-17.
- Trauth, E. (2001). *Qualitative Research in IS: Issues and Trends, Illustrated Edition*,. IGI Publishing.
- Trevino, K. d.-G. (2014). '(Un)Ethical Behavior in Organizations'. 635-60.
- Trochim, W. a. (2006). *The Research Methods Knowledge Base, 3rd Edition*. Atomic Dog Publishing Inc. .
- Walker, D. (2009). *A review of corporate governance in UK banks and other financial industry entities*.
- Wang, L. C.-b.-Z. (2014). The social and ethical consequences of a calculative mindset.
- Weeks, J. (2004). Unpopular culture: The ritual of complaint in a British bank.
- Wright, P. L. (1990). Teller job satisfaction and organization commitment as they relate to career orientations. 369-381.
- Yin, R. (2009). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods, 5th Edition*,. Sage Publications.

10.APPENDIX

10.1 CONSENT FORM

Project Title: BRITISH RETAIL BANKING SHIPWRECK: IS 'REGULATED SALES-LED CULTURE' THE SOLUTION?

Name of researcher: Tahir Ahmed

PARTICIPATION IN THIS RESEARCH STUDY IS VOLUNTARY

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction;	Yes/No
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind;	Yes/No
- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and my identity will remain anonymous in any reports or publications resulting from the study;	Yes/No
- I understand that I am free to contact researcher involved in the research to seek further clarification and information;	Yes/No
- I can request a copy of the transcript of my interview and may make edits I feel necessary to ensure the effectiveness of any agreement made about confidentiality;	Yes/No
- I consent to be a participant in the project;	Yes/No
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the project;	Yes/No

**Please retain a copy of this consent form.*

By signing this consent form, you are indicating that you fully understand the above information and agree to participate in this study.

Participant name:

Signature: _____ **Date** _____

Interviewer name:

Signature: _____ **Date** _____

Contact Information

This research was granted ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee.

If you have any further questions or concerns about this study, any comments to make now or later, or if you would like a copy of the published results of this study, please contact:

Researcher: Tahir Ahmed Email: [REDACTED]

10.2 Information for Participants

BRITISH RETAIL BANKING SHIPWRECK: IS 'REGULATED SALES-LED CULTURE' THE SOLUTION?

Tahir Ahmed

Doctorate in Business Administration, University of the West of Scotland

Information for participants

Thank you for considering participating in this study. This information sheet outlines the purpose of the study and provides a description of your involvement and rights as a participant, if you agree to take part.

1. What is the research about?

The aim of this research is to explore an issue at the very heart of the Financial Crisis and the series of scandals like PPI that followed: 'culture' and propose a strategy for a safer, reliable and sustainable banking sector.

2. Do I have to take part?

Participation is voluntary. If you do decide to take part I will ask you to sign a consent form which you can sign and return in advance of the interview or sign at the meeting.

3. What will my involvement be?

If you agree to participate an interview will be arranged at a place and time convenient to you. The interview would last about 40-60 minutes.

4. How do I withdraw from the study?

You can withdraw at any point of the study, without having to give a reason. If any questions during the interview make you feel uncomfortable, you do not have to answer them, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time for any reason.

5. What will my information be used for?

I will use the collected information solely for doctoral academic research purpose.

6. Will my taking part and my data be kept confidential? Will it be anonymised?

The records from this study will be kept confidential and will be destroyed once the study is completed. Your data will be anonymised – your name will not be used in any reports or publications resulting from the study. All digital files, transcripts and summaries will be given codes and stored separately from any names or other direct identification of participants. Any hard copies of research information will always be kept in locked files.

**If you are happy to take part in this study, please sign the consent sheet attached*

10.3 QUESTIONNAIRE

Topic 1: Your background and your organizational context

1.1. Background

- Could you please let us know about your personal background and current role?
- How is to work for an organization like [name of the organization]?
- What difference in terms of culture did you notice in contrast with prior organizations?
- Your organization's cultural context and the trigger events associated with culture changes.
- What is the (actual) culture? The desired culture? Is culture being measured in any way?
- Is there a culture change initiative underway at your organization?
- Which factors, actors or events have played a decisive role in the decision to engage this cultural initiative?

Topic 2: Cultural change initiatives at your organization

2.1. Content and design

- What cultural change initiatives are currently taking place at your organizations?
- Could you describe its most tangible elements (e.g. cost, level of commitment/endorsement from the top, number of employees concerned by the change program, expected impact)?
- Could describe the key practices or the content of this change?
- How is cultural change linked to other aspects of the organization (such as performance assessment, pay, and structure)?

2.2. Deployment

- How is the culture change initiative actually being deployed? Who is in charge of deploying it?
- What is the time line? Where are you now?
- How do you measure progress? What kind of indicators are you using to track progress?

2.3. Impact

- What kind of impact or influence is the change program or culture having in the organisation? How do you measure its impact?
- How do you justify or demonstrate to different audiences that cultural change has happened?
- What are the main successes related to this initiative?

2.4. Barriers and enablers of cultural change

- What do you regard as the main challenges or barriers related to this change initiative?
- What are the main factors facilitating this cultural shift (if any)?

Topic 3: Cultural change in your industry and at your competitors

- What are the benchmarks or best practice examples you have?
- How does your own organization compare to the competitors? How would rank yourself within the industry?
- Which competitor do you regard as a clear leader/laggard in this domain?
- What are your views on how the industry as a whole has progressed in relation to cultural change since 2008?

Topic 4: Industry regulation and cultural change

- What are your perceptions of regulation in this industry?
- Which regulatory organizations are the most relevant and important to your work?
- How does regulation relate to culture?
- Do regulators help support your process of cultural change?
- In your opinion, can regulation be conducted more effectively?
- How could regulation better support cultural change in your organization?